

Abstract

A complete relativity in all phenomena, with relative scale invariance in physical laws, is postulated and discussed.

Postulates are followed with definitions of new terms which may be used in the current and follow-up papers written in the context of the theory. In order to conform to this physics, a redefinition and generalization of some terms and factors already in use have also been presented. This includes, and is followed by, hypotheses on fundamental nature and mechanics of phenomena, based on observations and postulates of the theory, with some exact solutions provided.

In conclusion, the theory suggests that everything must be completely relative in order to exist and everything must evolve in order to conserve this relativity.

Complete Relativity: Nature of observables

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1 Introduction

From the perspective of a mathematician, both, the theory of Quantum Mechanics (QM) and the theory of General Relativity (GR), are brilliant and beautiful works of art. These works truly deserve all the respect they've got, and more. However, from the perspective of a physicist, today they're not satisfying enough. That is because they are obviously incomplete, and actually wrong in certain propositions. The main problem of modern quantum physics is that it has gone too far with the abstraction, so much so that it probably should be referred to as Quantum Mathematics. GR, on the other hand, didn't go far enough in relativity, thus, the appropriate title today would be Relatively General Relativity.

A complete theory on fundamentals of nature, however, should provide a framework which can be used to qualitatively describe all phenomena, regardless of scale or energy. Complete Relativity with incorporated relative, rather than absolute, invariance to scale of physical laws has such power, opening a path to profound insights into nature and mechanics of reality.

The best approach to understand nature/reality is to combine and balance the power of mathematical language with experience and observation on all scales of energy and in the process approach problems from different perspectives, rather than limit interpretation to that of a mathematician, physicist or a biologist.

Mathematical elegance may be desirable in calculations, but elegance is neither abstract nor absolute in reality. To properly understand reality one should seek to understand the measured physical processes, rather than reduce reality to a mathematical formalism which is in agreement with measurements. Many times in history, such reduction has been proved to be an illusion, a blurry and limited picture of reality, rather than true description of it. Instead of searching solutions that would disperse the illusion, one can instead chose to convince itself that reality is an illusion. That may seem like a legitimate choice at first, however, as the power of observation grows, the illusion grows bigger, and it becomes harder and harder to cling on to the notion that the established beliefs

represent established or absolute knowledge. Again, a biased observer can chose to look in the directions that confirm the established illusion, turning a blind eye to the possibilities of revolution. Much can be, however, criticized in the established world of today, not just in established science, but that's not the aim here.

Here, the aim is to understand reality as much as possible, or, in other words, to disperse as much of the established illusion as possible. The theory is a result of research, experience, observation, computation and logic that followed, and confirmed, strong intuition suggesting that overly non-intuitive, abstract and absolute reality is just an interpretation chosen, consciously or unconsciously, by biased and limited observers. It is an interpretation that enabled progress in the past, however, clinging to it now is doing nothing but hindering the progress in science.

In this, and follow-up papers, I provide foundations, details and evidence for a new description of reality. In order to properly understand that reality, I have rewritten my works many times, just as scientific books have been rewritten many times in the past. Has modern science gave up on rewriting books? If so, its name too is no longer appropriate. Scientific Religion comes to mind. I am sure, however, that the giants, who today may be painted and sculpted as gods in this religion, wouldn't look at it with approval or satisfaction. These "gods" have brought revolution, progress. In other words, they've used science to disperse the illusion of science ruling the time. And if one has any respect for these "gods" one should not be afraid to, once again, *reduce* them to giants, or even better, to what they considered themselves to be - genuine scientists, seekers and messengers of truth. Such messengers may possess an insatiable curiosity, but they are, just as their truth, limited, in space and time. I am one such seeker and messenger of truth, perhaps not as great as the giants of the past, but certainly with a wider view, enabled by the previous seekers of truth. This here, is what I see, or, my interpretation of what can be *seen*.

2 Postulates

Here are the postulates of Complete Relativity (CR). They are all *entangled* and one may stem from the other, but not always in apparent way.

2.1 Everything is relative (everything is variable)

$$\Delta E <> 0$$

No system can be completely isolated at all scales of energy or reference frames. Everything existing must be absorbing and radiating energy at some scale at any time, but never in such proportions as to enable a non-zero possibility for absolute invariance of that phenomenon in time/space.

Maintenance of relative constancy requires energy.

$$\Delta E \neq \infty$$

There is no single, absolute and infinite universe (*Universe*). For any observer, there exists a finite number of observable universes with mutually entangled characteristics, exchanging energy between each other.

One could argue that the sum of all universes is infinite and that sum is a single absolute entity. However, such *Universe* is absolutely unobservable. In CR, all existence has to be relative and thus observable at some scales, unobservable at other scales. Infinities and zeros as absolute values are mathematical abstractions - in reality they must be relative, as any other value. This implies relatively simultaneous existence of energy at different scales of space/time.

Any physical entity having absolute properties would have to be absolutely isolated in order for these properties to remain constant. With no ability to change (exchange energy) such absolutely elementary entities would be unobservable. Thus, relativity is an intrinsic property of reality.

Any distinct form of energy may be considered as an universe, however, in the framework of CR, universe will generally represent a particular scale of energy. These are discrete (stable) vertical energy levels for relatively elementary particles (called gravitons in CR, not to be confused with gravitons in other theories - here, graviton represents a generalized particle). Any form of energy thus *belongs* to a universe of the scale of largest graviton(s) coupled to (or, highly entangled with) the system. Gravitons, however, can be [relatively] naked or uncoupled. Energies of the same scale may be considered as instances of the same universe, but, generally these should be considered as horizontally parallel universes as no two instances are absolutely equivalent at any time (physical constants are relative, oscillate and will be different between the instances, even if these differences may not be generally resolvable).

As transfer and transformation of energy require capacity for energy storage and speed of transfer/transformation cannot be infinite, structural quanta of any medium must have real size.

- Every universe must be *divisible* - *contained* within a larger universe and *contain* universes of smaller scale,
- universes of different magnitude (vertically parallel universes) are self-similar but evolutionary dominantly separated in time, entangled more in space,
- instances of a universe (horizontally parallel universes) are dominantly separated in space, usually entangled more in time,

- instances can acquire energy beyond the potential or rest energy of the associated level, but values between discrete energy levels are generally (albeit relatively) unstable and instances in between will generally evolve towards one or the other stable level.

Since existence requires continuous exchange of energy, any relative constants (energies) must be oscillations on some scale. None of these oscillations can be absolutely stable - even the oscillation itself must change relative to something. Thus, each form of existence (energy) will generally evolve, either progressively (towards higher energy levels) or regressively (towards lower energy levels). Evolution of energy generally includes oscillations and fluctuations but the periods involved may be too small or too large to be detected (or detectable) from some reference frames. Since energy cannot occupy space of absolute 0 size, reality requires three degrees of freedom, although, due to inherent limitations in observability (and other reasons), energies (gravitons) can be approximated as point energies (particles). However, inflation (change of a vertical energy level) of the particle may make that interpretation inappropriate from the same reference frame.

In most intuitive interpretations universes should not have more than 3 spatial dimensions (there is no space for them!), however, due to various scales of energy, space can and will be effectively divided into subspaces which may be relatively isolated but entangled with other scales. In that case, multidimensional manifolds with more than 3 dimensions may be used to describe reality. But one should be careful not to declare such entanglements (couplings) intrinsic and absolutely constant properties of reality - the strength of any entanglement must be variable in completely relative reality.

Here, one must distinguish between abstract dimensionality and physical dimensionality. Abstract dimensionality is relative to a coordinate system of choice. This system may or may not reflect any physical dimensionality. In example, one may use the Cartesian system to quantify dimensionality of objects in space, but this is generally not the dimensionality of that space. Physical dimensions are, in CR, volumetric (although not all observers will be able to observe them as such). Thus, one could argue that physical space is one-dimensional, in a sense that there is no physical distinction between the 3 degrees of freedom. Reality is, however, never experienced as absolute, it is not absolutely homogeneous and isotropic, energies can be relatively isolated or limited to particular regions or scales of space (which implies physical differences between different degrees of freedom). Thus, all these sub-spaces or scales of space may be interpreted as different physical dimensions, especially when these are mutually strongly entangled. In example, local space is generally entangled with local time so it is very reasonable to interpret the duo as two local physical dimensions (or two different scales of space). Note that complete relativity requires change so it requires

time, however, local coupling of space and time won't be observable in all cases. Relative invariance to space or time will thus exist, and may be interpreted as absolute due to limitations of observers, but absolute it is not.

In CR, the scale of a universe generally represents a discrete vertical energy level, analogous to horizontal energy levels in Quantum Mechanics (QM).

Relative to the difference in scale between observer energy and energy of observables, phenomena may be interpreted as physical (real) or mental (imaginary, or hallucinated) components of reality, however, every mental phenomenon must have a physical interpretation at some scale, and *vice versa*.

Due to required evolution, energy in a universe is constantly transferred and transformed. Due to finite speed of transfer and transformation, these changes will be continuous, however, due to finite observable resolution of space/time, on some scales changes will be interpreted as discrete.

Speed of transformation of energy may be interpreted as its speed in time, while speed of transfer as its speed in space.

Note that speed of transformation is proportional to the speed of transfer of entangled energy at some scale. Therefore, time clearly has a physical interpretation at some scale - ageing of phenomena is strongly correlated with the transfer of quanta of energy at some scale, and these quanta may be interpreted as carriers of change or carriers of time. Note also that transformation can occur at different scales, hence, multiple time dimensions exist with different speeds of information (energy) transfer (generally inversely proportional to scale).

- Relatively the same energies relatively oscillate between relative existence and relative non-existence,
- oscillation between vertical energy levels generally involves transformation of scale and exchange between angular momentum components (m,v,r),
- scales of relative invariance of physical laws are discrete, with exponential progression and may be separated by many orders of magnitude.

Relativity of everything indeed has the power to explain everything. Consider relativity in causality. In General Relativity (GR), it is always the clump-

ing of matter (energy) that curves space, however, if causality is relative - sometimes it is the matter-devoid curved space that should cause clumping of matter. Of course, one can insist that space is abstract and attribute the energy of space to exotic matter (i.e., dark matter) [curving abstract space] to conserve causal order, but is that the proper interpretation if one strives for deeper understanding of reality (and, especially, if this exotic matter cannot be resolved)?

Note that I do not argue that the exotic matter does not exist - quite contrary, if space can cause clumping then it must have energy and must be composed of some kind of matter on some scale (which, for us, may be unobservable directly), I argue against interpretations that conserve absolute abstraction of space or absolute preservation of presumed causal order.

Note also that the exotic matter hypothesis (by established interpretations) simply doesn't match observations - e.g., *cold* dark matter halos within galaxies should slow down the rotation of galactic bars but the expected slowdown is not there[1]. There are other problems too[2].

These can all be solved through decoupling of space and matter, allowing different densities of space within the galaxy. Equivalent exotic matter here may generally be *hot* but transforming to *cold* with coupling, not absolutely free-streaming, rather *orbiting* about the galactic centre as *static* particles [forming galactic space], as elaborated later.

This is not the only case of apparent violation of presumed causal order. And there are problems associated with finite speed of information transfer that's commonly coupled to causality. Quantum entanglement is one example where common interpretations simply discard intuition and reduce natural complexity to abstraction in order to preserve an absolute (scale invariant) speed limit.

In CR, causality is a special case of synchronization between correlated entities and both, causal order and speed limits, will be violated on some scale when considered absolute. Again, if information exchange is unobservable, excessive reductionism is an appealing interpretation but it only simplifies calculations, at the expense of potential deeper understanding of reality.

That does not imply that calculations should be complicated, certainly not if the aim is practical application and certainly not arbitrarily. But if the aim is to understand and progress in science, rather than to stubbornly adhere to mathematically simplest solutions possible, additional interpretations should be explored.

Proper solution in complete relativity is general correlation of past and future

states which may be localized to, or locally *absolutized* into, causality (generally, thus, any intuitive concept is only locally intuitive and any illusion may be localized into intuition).

Distance between past and future is relative. And distance between phenomena is never absolute 0. Every interaction is a relative interaction and is the manifestation of synchronization - specific correlation in space and/or time. Causality is simply a biased (polarized) interpretation of synchronicity at particular scale.

All interactions or forces in nature depend on distance and all involve correlation. This suggests that distance should be generalized to distance in correlation.

To conserve relativity (existence), forces cannot be exclusively attractive or repulsive and strength of force will sometimes be proportional, sometimes inversely proportional to distance.

Note also that non-existence of absolute 0 distances together with the non-existence of absolute point sources of energy (field source, or maximum, is not at the centre rather at a non-zero distance from it), avoids infinities, which are a common issue in physics (or, more precisely, in mathematics), usually discarded in an *arbitrary* way using a technique called *renormalization* (which, although based on good ideas - such as running coupling, sometimes probably could be translated as, more or less educated, guesswork[3]).

2.2 Everything is exchangeable

Absolute relativity in space seemingly introduces *problems*, such as one in relativity of containment. Consider two spheres different in scale and located (centred) at [relatively] the same point in space - how is it possible that a reference frame exists in which the bigger sphere is contained within a smaller one (non-dimensional rationality is relative)?

Conservation of relativity thus clashes with the conservation of rationality (intuition). Seemingly, either non-dimensional rationality is relative or one must be sacrificed for the other.

Here, finite speed of information transfer enables one elegant resolution - conservation of both by exchanging relativity in space for rationality in time (subspace). If the two spheres oscillate in time between two scales and one does not discriminate between space and time, both quantities are conserved (rationality in space, relativity in time). Thus, on absolute scale everything is conserved, but relatively even relativity can be sacrificed.

Multiple interpretations and multiple solutions are common in nature. This problem is no exception. Suppose that everything exists [relatively] simultaneously on different scales - a bigger sphere can then be relatively contained within a smaller one if the smaller one has its identical copy on some larger scale.

Note that, if everything must be relative, location and scale of existence must be too, therefore, everything should exist on different scales. This explains self-similarity of universes and suggests that planetary systems such as the Solar System are likely not only similar to atoms (certainly not by coincidence) - they could correspond to specific atoms in relatively equivalent (properly scaled) conditions (pressure/temperature), where the component waveforms have been localized. From some reference frames this may be interpreted as a change in discrete vertical energy level - they have been inflated from standard atoms or similar systems of even smaller scale. Evidence for this will be provided.

Note that, since existence is relative, existence of containment must be relative, so there also must exist a reference frame in which one cannot tell which sphere is contained within the other.

When integrated over time/space, such state may be interpreted as superposition or fusion of different states.

Unless one accepts the notion of multi-scale existence, it might seem that relativity of containment is generally not conserved, even in time. Consider the example of a chicken in an egg - there is no apparent oscillation, chicken may be growing inside the egg and will eventually get bigger than the egg but the egg is not getting smaller and is at no point inside the chicken.

However, another kind of relativity can solve the problem - the egg was once inside the adult chicken. This means there must exist a reference frame relative to which there is no distinction between the two chickens (relativity of identity). Such reference frame does exist and is enabled by the finite resolution (scale) of information carrier particles.

Effectively, both the chicken and the egg are oscillating over time. With absolute containment nothing would be able (required) to grow or decay - neither chicken nor any other universe, with relative containment everything must grow or decay (or oscillate between the two).

Complete relativity and its conservation in reality is what makes everything possible.

Apparently, both GR and QM allow [or are at least partially based on] the existence of an absolute rest frame [correlated] with constant speed c , completely

disallowing any faster means of information transfer on any scale.

Any absolute constant is an absolute reference frame. The more absolutism there is in the description of reality, the more illusionary it becomes. This description may be satisfactory for spatially and temporally limited observers, but even in such, at times evolution may introduce observable discrepancies which will require *recalibration* of supposed absolutism.

Assumptions like that make GR absolutely non-relative and in QM produce many non-intuitive phenomena in space which would otherwise be completely understandable. Even space in GR is non-intuitive in common interpretations - it has *plastic* geometry but no physical properties.

If one does not discriminate between space and time, one could notice that space and time are often inverted in QM. In example, quantum entanglement between distant particles can be local in time even though it appears non-local in space.

Note that conservation of quantum entanglement requires either relative non-transformation of energy or synchronized evolution between entangled properties. If the entanglement doesn't change, its speed in time is 0. Therefore, distance between two entangled particles in time remains the same (relative 0) even if they are separated in space. Such particles obviously must share a time dimension, and in CR, that is a physical dimension on some scale. Strength of entanglement here is then proportional to correlation in time.

However, there are no physical point particles in reality, therefore, distance in physical reality is not 1-dimensional, it's volumetric. Thus, correlating volumetric distance with entanglement, with increasing distance in space, the cross-section of the time dimension between two particles is shrinking in the middle but the volume (volumetric distance) remains constant.

Wave/particle duality with the change of scale (collapse/inflation of entangled compositional quanta) also becomes intuitive, and a reasonable explanation of quantum tunnelling (where it involves the change in scale/nature of force coupling). While energy/information transfer in space/time is limited, it is not limited absolutely, it is limited by the specific scale entanglement (it is now obvious that annihilation of matter and anti-matter must involve a change of scale) - due to relativity in density and pressure of space, speed limits will depend on [scale of density/pressure of] space the particle is sensitive to (the experience of space, or sensitivity to particular energy quanta, is relative).

Energy of larger scale is, of course, generally *composed of* (spatially/temporally entangled with) energy of smaller scale. Here, however, one must distinguish between *living* and *dead* bodies. If the collective of smaller scale energy is coupled to a graviton of larger scale the body is considered *living* and the speed limit for that body is different (generally smaller) than the speed limit for individual constituent particles (the difference being proportional to the difference between scales). If the collective is not coupled to a large scale graviton, the body is *dead* as a distinct large scale phenomenon and its speed limit is equal to the speed limit of individual constituent particles (this body is also generally less stable than the *living* body).

Superluminal particles must exist at some smaller scale, however, as noted before, observers are always limited in resolution and may not be able to directly detect them.

However, collapse of quantum entanglement (superposition of states) in one interpretation involves collapse and contraction of time dimensions between particles and speed of that contraction then inevitably becomes superluminal at some distance in space. This is then an indirect observation of superluminal transfer of information, even though, in some contexts contraction of time could be interpreted as contraction of space-time and from that reference frame information may be at rest.

If space is real, there is no reason for intrinsic coupling of matter and space curvature, therefore a reference frame must exist where there is no such coupling - *dark matter* can then be interpreted as direct evidence for real space.

It is intuitive for space to have relative density and pressure which can, as vacuum energy, attract particles that are sensitive to such density and pressure. And these particles may have their own space coupled with them. Reality thus becomes intuitive even on small scales - electron can have a realistic rotation (which, depending on interpretation and scale, may involve rotation faster than c , but not necessarily - as will be elaborated later), with a real radius.

With an atomic nucleus allowed to have its own rotating space the electrons do not emit energy when in a specific orbit, even in corpuscular form - they can be at rest relative to that space.

Relative electric permittivity (dielectric constant) and magnetic permeability of materials now make intuitive sense and can be correlated with properties of space of atomic nuclei [gravitons].

Current (absolute) vacuum electric permittivity and magnetic permeability would be no different - these are also properties of space, which, however, should not be considered absolute anymore.

One might argue that the existence of physical space has been disproved with experiments, however, that is not the case - specific interpretations of aether have been disproved[4]. While space in CR has some similarities with, what was originally called, aether, it is not the same phenomenon. One could consider the space in CR to have the same geometry as space in GR, however, with part of the energy of curvature in real density and pressure of space, instead of all energy being attributed to matter, making space nothing more than non-intuitive abstract geometry (absolutely flat with absence of matter). There are other differences though and GR requires modifications to become completely relative even if energy of space is attributed to exotic matter (e.g., implementation of scale-dependent *constants* and/or scale-dependent metric - running coupling).

If space has energy, then the energy between matter and space (or, generally, energy between one scale and the other) can be exchanged. One mechanism for this exchange is annihilation of energies. Annihilation, in general, may be interpreted as *vertical migration* (inflation or deflation) of particular existence from one scale to the other.

Note that inflation and deflation of energy can be accomplished through the exchange of components of [angular] momenta. In the transition between energy levels, such exchanges should be common. Note also that the nature of energy is generally not preserved between adjacent scales associated with discrete vertical energy levels, e.g., gravitational potential may be exchanged for electro-magnetic and *vice versa*.

2.3 Everything has an angular momentum (relative momentum-energy equivalence)

All energy can be correlated with intrinsic angular momenta of gravitons at some scale. Relativity in elementariness implies that any angular momentum is *composed of* (more precisely, coupled with) spin momenta of smaller scale.

Due to various scales of existence and intrinsic rotation of gravitons, everything existing has an angular momentum in some reference frames.

Note that this could be stated differently - a reference frame must exist in which an form of energy (observable) has angular momentum. This then implies that the observable universe is rotating, even though the centre of that rotation may be outside of it.

Capacitance of space allows transfer of momentum, but also its localization. Any mass (energy) at relative rest is a localized/stabilized momentum in form

of local spin momenta. The rest energy is thus localized kinetic energy at rest scale (a scale with such properties that ensure stability of rest energy) and a reference frame must exist relative to which the energy is in motion.

Individual momenta may entangle to form larger structures, and with enough energy, fuse to form larger momenta. Since momenta are quantized not every momentum is stable, and even the stable ones are only relatively stable with a difference in decay rates.

Obviously, rest mass is relative and will not be absolutely equal even between individual particles of the same species.

Of course, although momentum and energy are coupled, their equivalence must be taken relatively - not only are observers inherently limited, the observables/parameters are often reduced intentionally depending on the context. Thus, reference frames will exist where one quantity may be conserved, the other not, in some contexts one may change proportionally to the other, in other the relationship may be inversely proportional.

2.4 Everything is entangled on some scale (all correlation is physical on some scale)

All physically possible entities exist and are physically connected (entangled) on some scale (everything exists on various scales). In absolute reality this may imply everything was initially condensed into a singularity, but in relative reality this may be interpreted simply as natural manifestation of correlation, a consequence of required relativity (e.g., of abstractness). However, condensation into relative singularities is not impossible, will exist and will affect entanglements.

The strength of entanglement between two entities, in its basic form, depends on entangled energy or distance in correlation:

$$\propto \frac{1}{r^n} \propto \frac{\Delta E}{E}$$

where E is the total energy of entangled entity, ΔE is entangled energy, while r is distance in correlation (which will generally reduce to distance in space or time).

Due to inherent limitations of observers, some entanglements may be effectively impossible to break, while other may be impossible to observe.

Note that entanglement can be effectively invariant to distance in space if entanglement is physically manifested in time and [volumetric] distance in time (which, in some contexts, may be interpreted as distance in evolution) remains unchanged (e.g., if the observer cannot differentiate between entangled photons, distance in time is effectively 0 and so the information transfer, occurring with changes in entanglement, will effectively be infinitely fast).

Also note that the strength of entanglement is relative and can be asym-

metric (E may be different between entangled bodies, as well as ΔE). Entanglement strength is never absolute zero, but it is variable and non-resolvable amounts may be interpreted as relative zero amounts.

Strong entanglement is established when it becomes physically impossible for an observer to disturb the proportionality of ΔE and E . This occurs when applied energy is distributed on both, particles and the time (subspace) dimension connecting (entangling) them. At some point, however, applied energy may *produce* (inflate) new pairs of particles.

Note that strong entanglement is relative to an observer (scale of energy) and can be broken by a *less limited* one.

Changes in strength of entanglement with distance (derivatives of entangled potential) can be interpreted as forces acting on bodies. The interpretation, however, is relative itself, can be more or less direct - e.g., forces acting directly between bodies, or forces mediated by energy carriers of smaller scale (e.g., quanta of space).

2.4.1 Conservation of entanglement

Entanglement can be horizontal (between energies of similar scale) and vertical (between energies of different scale). Deflation of specific entanglement will generally be relatively synchronized with the inflation of another entanglement. Horizontal entanglement can even be relatively exchanged for a vertical one, and *vice versa*. In some cases, it is common for the deflation of the current entanglement to be synchronized with the [re]inflation of a previous entanglement, in which case the previous one may be interpreted as a *background* entanglement.

2.4.2 Correlation is fundamental

Reality on a fundamental level is a field of potential. This field can have positive and negative relatively localized excitations - with *induced* potential gradients, causing repulsion and attraction of correlated phenomena, respectively. The excitations exist on different scales, can couple to other excitations and form correlations of different complexity, which can then be correlated with different forces of different scale. The phenomenon of synchronicity can be interpreted as a manifestation of the most primitive force - where correlation is invariant to properties of correlated entities. Gravity, for an example on the other hand, is a bit more complex form of correlation clumping (correlating a specific property between entities - mass/energy). Note how this implies there is no absolute randomness. The phenomenon of synchronicity involves an excitation in the general field that is causing the *clumping* of correlated entities at a specific *point* in space/time. Thus, any clumping (attraction) or repulsion of correlated entities that is interpreted as random (due to inherent limitations of observers) is only pseudo-random. One could argue that reality requires such excitations to

conserve relativity but it is equally valid to say that excitations require relativity in order to exist. If one interprets gravity as emergent force then it obviously evolves from synchronicity.

Note, however, that any causality here is relative. In some interpretations of reality it is the excitation(s) that will be causing the clumping for example, in others the clumping will induce excitation(s). Excitations can exist both, in space and time. Consider two gravitationally bound bodies orbiting about the barycentre of mass. Where exactly is the excitation - localized to barycentre (and how localized)? And is the 3rd excitation necessary since the bodies themselves are excitations? Yes, the 3rd excitation does exist in some dimension but may be correlated with synchronicity, not directly with gravity (although the barycentre of mass is a special place in a gravitational field as well - an unstable one). However, if the two bodies will eventually merge, one could argue that the 3rd gravitational excitation exists but it is at some distance away in time. In that case, the excitation associated with synchronicity can be interpreted as a precursor to the 3rd gravitational excitation.

In other words, some excitation always exists but it may be *primitive* - e.g., not coupled to mass (and, thus, not coupled to gravity). Now, the coupling strength of synchronicity is obviously lower than that of gravity but it should probably have a much larger range. Therefore, in some distant past it may be that synchronicity brought the two bodies closer together, only for gravity to take over.

Polarization of excitations must be relative as well. This is why electromagnetic force exists, why gravitational potential can be (and is between scales) exchanged for electro-magnetic, and why the same person can attract some people, repel different people, and have no effect on others.

Note that it is common for 3rd excitations existing in time to eventually couple to mass and materialize in space. A child, for example, is a 3rd excitation - a product/combination of two parent excitations - mother and father, or sperm and an egg, or associated DNA. We are used to the notion of a child being caused by parents, but if a child (or its consciousness) on some fundamental level emerges from excitation associated with synchronicity, one could argue that the [future] child has attracted the parents in the first place. If the child is indeed associated in such way with synchronicity, then the [potential] child always exists - it is just not always materialized, e.g., due to some more complex and stronger correlation that may be causing repulsion.

Note also how relative is the interpretation of life. If consciousness is fundamental (in its most primitive form being an excitation associated with synchronicity) then any independent excitation is a potential lifeform. Indeed, I believe that any naked excitation (not coupled to mass) is a soul not coupled to a body, a potential precursor to a lifeform (soul-body coupling).

2.5 Physical laws are relatively scale invariant

In reality, distance is quantized, but the size of quanta is not absolutely constant. Energy generally oscillates between stable discrete energy levels. These energy levels can be horizontal (as described by QM) or vertical. Horizontal energy levels differ in the amount of energy but generally not in the order of magnitude, vertical levels generally differ by multiple orders of magnitude.

Although universes at different scales may be in different equilibrium states, applying energy, state on one scale can be made locally relatively equivalent to a state on another scale.

Here, state generally refers to scale relative pressure (or temperature) and density, which generally differ on average between vertical energy levels.

Temperatures and densities on standard scale are proportional to kinetic energies and densities of standard atoms, respectively, on a higher vertical energy level these may be kinetic energies and densities of planetary systems, on a lower energy level energies and densities of space (or field) forming entities.

Universes are self-similar, however, the values of *constants* and/or units of metric should differ between scales of gravitons.

Physical *laws* of nature are thus relatively scale invariant, with stable scales appearing at discrete points between intervals of generally exponential progression.

Elementary particles are strongly relative to reference scale. From a smaller scale they will evidently be composite and differ from each other, while from a larger scale they may even be unobservable (non-existent) individually.

2.6 Hidden variables always exist

With no absolutely elementary phenomena and with inherent (but not absolutely constant!) limits in observation, hidden variables must exist. Therefore, non-intuitive reality suggested by QM must be taken relatively. As stated already, treatment of all constants as relative constants can make QM much more intuitive, but it does not end there.

It should be noted that intuition too must be relative. If common intuition (e.g., one involving hidden variables) cannot be observed, it is valid to conceptualize non-intuitive reality (and declare this non-intuition as natural or intuitive from some reference frame), however, in the pursuit of truth, one cannot claim such reality is absolute - there are always possibilities for different interpretations.

One may, for example, use abstract two-dimensional entities to describe phenomena occurring in reality if the calculations consistently match the outcomes of experiments/measurements, but that does not imply that reality is absolutely two-dimensional or non-intuitive on a particular scale - it is not. Realistic and more intuitive interpretation is always possible[5] even if it may require hidden variables. If complete relativity implies such variables must exist, and, if one strives for deeper understanding of reality, it would be, not only counter-*intuitive*, but counter-productive to discard them simply because mathematics without them works and/or is more elegant (less complex). Especially considering the real possibility, implied by CR, that one might be able to relatively observe the hidden variable on another scale of a particular state. Furthermore, mathematics *working* today may not work tomorrow - any hidden variable is variable after all.

3 On stability of equations

Equations are very useful and powerful constructs of a mathematical language. They simplify descriptions, can lead to new insights on details and plausibility of hypotheses, but can also be very deceiving.

All dimensional constants are relative. Therefore, more constants the value of equation depends on, more unstable it is and its potential for illusion increases with distance from the scale the constants *belong* to.

Dimensionless constants are generally more stable and may be well preserved across adjacent scales, but even these should not be absolute.

With everything being relative, a presumption of absoluteness will eventually lead to discrepancies in measurement and misinterpretation of reality.

4 Definitions

Here are the definitions of terms and expressions that may be used here and other papers in CR context.

Note that some of these represent redefinitions (e.g., generalization) of standard or common definitions in use. Some contain additional hypotheses and important details, representing an integral part of the theory.

4.1 n_{th} order observer

In the context of quantization (measurement) of physical phenomena, observer is an entity performing the measurement.

The order of the observer is a relative sum of the number of interactions in the act of measurement which affect its result.

In example, a 1st order observer may be the information carrier (radiation) particle, 2nd order observer is then the radiation detector, etc.

Every observation is measurement, albeit not always a conscious one. Measurement affects all interacting entities.

4.2 *n*_th order interaction (*n*_th order action and reaction)

Consider the forces in Newton's law of gravitation:

$$F = \frac{d}{dt}p = \frac{d}{dt}(mv) = ma = G\frac{Mm}{r^2}$$

$$F_1 = m_1a_2 = m_1\frac{m_2G}{r^2} = m_2a_1 = m_2\frac{m_1G}{r^2} = F_2$$

Here, forces acting on bodies m_1 and m_2 are equal and have opposite direction, as expected for forces of action and reaction. Note that these are actions and reactions between bodies of mass at distance [in space].

In General Relativity there is no action and reaction between the two bodies directly, but effectively between continuous space (more precisely, geometry shaped by the energy of bodies) and a particular body (or energy, in general). And it is not an action and reaction at distance (distance between space and the body is assumed to be equal to absolute 0, only changes propagate at finite speed so the distance in time between changes in potential is not 0).

The two bodies have an effect on space (and vice versa) but they also affect, albeit indirectly in GR, each other.

In CR, it is obvious that even the interaction between quanta of space and quanta of bodies cannot be an action at absolute 0 distance, but this distance is generally orders of magnitude shorter than distance between the bodies and may be considered infinitesimal (relative zero).

Note that in both cases of formalism action/reaction is instantaneous, so even in Newton's gravity distance between the sources is effectively set to 0 for whatever is mediating the force, only the 1st order sources of interaction differ.

In Complete Relativity there are no absolute zero and infinite distances, suggesting that every action is action at a distance. But the key here is that distance is relative itself. It is correlation (of mass in this case) that is a primary reason for the manifestation of force but it is not the sole requirement. A carrier particle must exist on some scale, even though the interaction may be interpreted as non-local (as in case of Newton's gravity). Thus, even if distance is non-zero between particles forming space, that distance is traversed by mediating particles of some scale. In

other words, what is interpreted as non-locality is a consequence of inherent observer limitations - e.g., non-resolvability of space or mediators. Distance between interacting bodies may be greater than zero, but this is not interaction at distance if mediators are traversing that distance (one could argue that distance exists only in the absence of mediators). In some cases (e.g., quantum entanglement) correlation may seem invariant to distance in space, leading some to a conclusion that a mediator in such cases is an unnecessary complication (even unscientific, from non-holistic perspectives). In CR, however, this non-existence is equivalent to a mediator of 0 mass and infinite speed - leading to infinite range. Since such mediator is impossible in CR, the only solution is mediator (or, more precisely, associated dimension) scaling that is inversely proportional to distance in space. And such plasticity is generally present in a time dimension.

The sources of force of action and reaction are thus relative to scale - measuring on larger scale it may be more appropriate to attribute the sources to bodies, while on lower scale the quanta of space may be interpreted as such.

From a 3rd perspective one might consider the action between a force carrier particle in space (even if it is a bound *static* particle with potential energy) and a body as a 1st order interaction, and the interaction between two bodies as a 2nd order interaction.

One may also consider the 1st order interaction as relatively instantaneous, 2nd order occurring at some speed c , 3rd order at even some lower speed, etc.

In any case, there is no absolutely instantaneous, simultaneous and equal reaction to action (it requires quantum of distance equal to absolute 0, or, equivalently, infinite speed of carrier particles).

Absolute causality is an illusion. An *arrow of time* is a result of asymmetry in synchronization of highly correlated events.

The relativity of sources (force carriers) and distances has an important consequence on the law of action and reaction - it should be generalized:

$$\int_{t=0}^T [\vec{F}_1(t) + \vec{F}_2(t)] dt = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

Instantaneous action and reaction is thus a special case of action and reaction impulses, where the period of energy oscillation T is compressed to an instant - a single elementary quantum of time ($dt = T$), and the identity/strength of interacting forces is strongly localized (even absolutely in common interpretations,

where the value of zero is interpreted as an absolute constant):

$$\vec{F}_1 + \vec{F}_2 = 0$$

Note the equivalence of distance in time and space of different scales - in the 1st order interaction (GR) distance in space is 0, while in the 2nd order interaction (Newton) distance in time is 0.

Also note that, although not required, it is not forbidden for action and reaction to be relatively simultaneous, nor it is forbidden for reaction to precede action, allowing relativity of cause and effect - something that is, with absolutely invariant c (speed of information transfer), forbidden in GR and Special Relativity (SR), but required in CR.

In CR thus, causality is not absolutely fundamental nor intrinsic - it could be understood as a result of force, relatively emerging (or evolving) between correlated (entangled) phenomena decreasing distance in space and/or time. However, *proper* interpretation is that causality is simply a consequence of localization of synchronization of events in a polarized reference frame (the source of asymmetry).

Violation of [absolute] causality will exist on all scales of energy, but amount will differ between the scales. However, the amount has to oscillate too and will correlate with changes in the properties of space.

The equation (1.1) is equivalent to momentum pulse reflection:

$$\int_{t=0}^T [\vec{F}_1(t) + \vec{F}_2(t)] dt = \int_{t=0}^T \left[\frac{d\vec{p}_1}{dt} + \frac{d\vec{p}_2}{dt} \right] dt = \Delta\vec{p}_1 + \Delta\vec{p}_2 = 0$$

With $T > dt > 0$, action and reaction becomes a manifestation of energy oscillation.

However, entanglement can be relatively broken (reduced to relatively infinitesimal strength) and reaction may be delayed, may not affect the source of action or might not even occur (e.g., if the action is locally interpreted as reaction).

All bodies having rest mass possess capacitance and reaction to the source will eventually come, even if from another body, if that capacity is not in equilibrium state.

However, the reaction may be fragmented and carried by diverse force carriers following multiple different paths.

Such nature of non-apparent oscillation stems from different scales of energy quanta enabling diversity and evolution of complex forms of energy, its conduction and transformation.

Although generalization of interactive correlation is useful for understanding, generally, it may not be pragmatic. In the descriptions of transformations and interactions, more useful terms will be conservation of energy and conservation of momentum.

4.3 Superposition

Superposition is a relatively special state of a system which can be described as a combination (generally sum) of correlated (entangled) multiple base states.

Mathematically, superposition may be formulated as a sum of probabilities for particular states of particles.

In CR, speed of information transfer, and therefore, speed limits, depend on the scale of quanta of energy. This, together with CR interpretation of entanglement, allows for physical interpretation of superposition to represent intermediate states of oscillation between discrete states.

Superposition can thus represent a real state, although that state may be unstable and observer, due to inherent limitations, may not be able to observe (resolve) it. E.g., on the scale of standard electrons, spin momenta is generally measured as discrete (e.g., up or down, not something *in between*). This is usually because intermediate states are unstable in the context, and the measurement itself may collapse the system into a discrete (stable) state. Base states of superposition are context-dependent. In one example, two base states may represent two anti-aligned spin momenta. In another example, two base states may represent the nature of a particle (wave-like and corpuscular-like). If intermediate states cannot be observed, the values assigned to individual base states may be understood as probabilities for that state to be observed after measurement is performed. However, between measurements, the particles will commonly oscillate between base states and common physical interpretation will be the *averaged* superposition - e.g., in case of its nature, the particle may effectively exhibit both the corpuscular/localized and wavelike/delocalized nature simultaneously which may be interpreted as partial localization/delocalization. The interpretation in the form of *averaged* superposition is commonly a consequence of inherently limited observation/interaction.

However, instability is scale relative. An unstable state (such as the averaged superposition) on one scale may be interpreted as physically stable on another. This is generally a consequence of effective time dilation and exchange of nature of potential between vertical scales of energy.

4.4 Universe (U)

In relativity lacking theories, Universe may be understood as simply the sum of absolutely everything that exists, had ever existed and will ever exist. Thus, that definition refers to an absolute universe (Universe) - unobservable as a whole.

In CR, nothing is absolute, thus, existence of multiple universes is implied. Any universe is a relative, relatively finite and relatively observable, phenomenon, and may represent any distinct form of energy.

In physics, however, a different universe should either obey different physical *laws*, conform to different metric and/or physical *constants*. In the context of CR, thus, a universe, by default, refers to a particular scale of energy (that is, energy at, or about, certain magnitude). These scales are interpreted as discrete vertical energy levels and will correspond to rest energy magnitudes of *elementary* (or stable) particles on that level.

These universes are correlated and energy on one scale may represent past or future state, or a special state, of the correlated energy on another scale.

Note that, here, difference between vertical energy levels is generally such that physical constants differ significantly in value. The equations for determination of these levels are provided later.

For example, one vertical energy level represents the scale of standard atoms, the other represents the scale of planetary systems.

Note also that, even though these levels are considered discrete, the values of physical *constants* anywhere still should oscillate and may even differ horizontally (between systems of similar scale), however, such differences are probably generally negligible (although they may be detectable).

However, rules exist in the association of energy with specific scale (vertical energy level). A localized group of energies of particular scale, no matter how large, should only be associated with a larger scale [as well] if the group is spatio-temporally entangled with a distinct graviton of larger scale. This distinction is generally a distinction between a simple aggregate of entities and a collective of entities representing something more than the sum of these entities. In other words, it is the emergent phenomena that represent a likely signal for the coupling of the collective with a graviton of larger scale. The coupling may be periodic, occasional, stable or unstable, and, due to time dilation between scales or relativistic causality, the rate of emergence/decay of emergent phenomena can only be relatively synchronized with the rate of coupling/decoupling. On one scale transition may appear continuous, on the other discrete.

4.4.1 Polarization and scale of a universe

Universe will typically refer to a scale. If it refers to a specific particle or a system of particles, polarization may also be specified. There are two equivalent notations:

$$cU_{n.m} = cU(n.m)$$

n = vertical energy level (scale) of the universe (0 = reference universe)
m = scale of the (horizontal) sub-universe

$$\begin{aligned}
c &= \text{polarization} \\
n &\in \mathbb{Z} \\
m &\in \mathbb{Z}
\end{aligned}$$

In CR, space is relative and generally associated with a particular graviton (which, in CR, represents an evolvable particle, generally a superposition of sources of gravitational and electro-magnetic potential but it becomes more complex with emergence of phenomena between discrete vertical energy levels). I hypothesize that specific gravitons of one discrete scale (vertical energy level) form the space of a graviton of a larger discrete scale.

The n scales are then generally such that U_{-1} scaled energy quanta (gravitons) form the space (medium) of U_1 gravitons, while U_{-2} energy forms the space (medium) of U_0 , etc. In addition to space, gravitons may have associated bodies of mass of another scale, e.g., U_1 gravitons generally couple to bodies of mass (particles) of U_0 scale. However, this coupling is not intrinsic and gravitons not coupled to such body may be interpreted as naked gravitons.

This coupling is also not direct. Matter of U_0 scale is directly coupling to space-forming particles of an U_1 graviton, and these particles are of U_{-1} scale.

If m is specified, the $U_{n.m}$ denotes the sub-universe of scale m , larger than n but smaller than $n+1$.

If specified, charge c denotes the polarization, usually electric (two possible states of polarization).

In this and my other works, U_0 scale will generally represent the scale of standard particles such as standard protons and electrons, U_1 then represents the scale of stars and planets.

4.5 Standard particle

Standard particle (e.g., standard electron) refers to a particle as defined by the Standard Model in physics.

4.6 Elementary particle

CR implies relativity in elementariness. All particles, including those conventionally considered to be elementary, must have structure, even if that structure may be unresolvable for the observer.

However, since unresolvable properties effectively do not exist for the observer, the concept of elementariness is certainly useful. Even in cases where the structure can be resolved but is inaccessible, for pragmatic reasons it may be disregarded. Both, standard protons and electrons, for example, may be treated as elementary as the constituent particles are strongly confined.

Even on large scales, depending on context, relative equivalents of these may be considered elementary, even though their structure may be highly resolvable by the observer.

4.7 Existence

Distinct forms of existence are distinct forms of energy. All discrete quanta of energy are *produced* (inflated or deflated) with changes in momenta. Preservation of existence on particular scale requires energy, although all that energy may be provided already with localization to that scale. Apart from the energy localized in the particle, stability also depends on the pressure/density of the associated space, which is of different scale.

Any form of energy contains spin momenta at some scale and, in CR, even as a whole must have orbital momenta from some reference frames. Angular momentum (commonly denoted by L) is intrinsic to universes, however, it is not always observable, so its existence is relative as well. For *elementary* particles (on any scale) the observable momentum will commonly be angular:

$$L = mvr$$

where m , v and r are particle mass, velocity and orbital radius, respectively.

For a system of n entities, the momentum of the system is the sum of individual momenta (which, generally, should be interpreted as a vector sum):

$$L = \sum_{i=1}^n L_i$$

It should be clear that, like everything else, rotation is relative. Some claim that rotation is absolute because centrifugal and Coriolis forces always exist in rotational reference frames, however this is not absolutely true. Clearly, both forces are relative - the amount of force measured or felt depends on the sensitivity of the observer, whether the observer is a machine or not. For some observers, the force can be a relative zero. Therefore, rotation is relative as well. After all, didn't we use to believe that Sun revolves about Earth? Some even still claim the Earth is flat, and they are not absolutely wrong either - three-dimensional space can be translated to two-dimensional space and *vice versa* so one could legitimately ask is the two-dimensional image of Earth in their heads an illusion, or is the three-dimensional Earth an illusion. Whatever one believes the answer is, it is both, relatively correct and relatively wrong.

4.8 General oscillation

With no absolute constants, everything must oscillate, even oscillation itself.

Change of a variable in dimension x_i may thus generally be described with the appliance of the following operator:

$$\frac{d}{dx_i} = a_1 f(\omega_1 (x_i + \phi_1)) \left[1 + a_2 f(\omega_2 (x_i + \phi_2)) \left[1 + a_3 f(\omega_3 (x_i + \phi_3)) \left[1 + \dots \right] \right] \right]$$

f = oscillating function

a_j = amplitude of j^{th} order oscillation

ω_j = frequency of j^{th} order oscillation

ϕ_j = phase shift of j^{th} order oscillation

where, generally, $a_j < 1$ for $j > 1$.

Multiple dimensions are generally entangled, so f may be $f(x_i, \dots, x_n)$. Of course, not all oscillation will be resolvable in all space/time.

4.9 Frequency of existence

Existence is relative and it depends on the scale of a reference frame (one cannot have the ability to measure energy at any scale possible), but may also oscillate between energy levels.

Gravitons should relatively commonly oscillate between energy levels. For a particular order of general oscillation and its period T_x , frequency of existence of a graviton is:

$$f_x = \frac{1}{T_x} = \frac{1}{\Delta T_1 + \Delta T_0}$$

where ΔT_1 is the average lifetime on a larger scale and ΔT_0 is the average lifetime on a smaller scale. Generally, ΔT_0 may be $\ll \Delta T_1$, and T_x may be approximated with ΔT_1 .

In CR, gravitons of particular scale can and regularly do couple to gravitons of smaller scale (which are then forming the body of the system). There is then a distinction between living and dead forms of energy. A living form of energy is any entangled collective of mass (energy) of particular scale coupled to a graviton of larger scale. Since it is also assumed that at the time of decoupling (death) the large scale graviton inverts scale (and some other properties, e.g., spin), and this is usually followed by new coupling on the same or similar scale of the previous incarnation, frequency of existence becomes frequency of reincarnation of energy, which may be, in some reference frames interpreted as reincarnation of *life*.

Polarized humans tend to discriminate between living and non-living *things* based on convenience. I do not and I do not think nature generally does. I believe any collective of energies coupled to a graviton of larger scale is not only alive but conscious to certain degree - large scale graviton

here being the carrier of that consciousness or at least required for its emergence. It is only the amount (or detection) of consciousness and its introversion/extroversion ratio that will depend on a reference frame.

And if energies are oscillating between vertical energy levels (in the process, weakly or strongly evolving/transforming) the question of what evolved from what becomes relative (it must be relative in CR). It is then valid to say that atoms evolve from complex forms of life, just as *vice versa* is valid from conventional reference frames. Note that here, in case of progressive evolution and complex life of our scale, atoms represent planetary systems - even if, obviously, these are only relative equivalents to standard atoms in special states or at specific times. Here and in follow-up/complementary papers, I hypothesize and provide evidence that planetary systems are vertically excited atoms.

All this, however, does not imply complex life forms on Earth will evolve into celestial bodies - among other things, this would require enormous amounts of energy and that energy here is simply not available. Humans will thus reach a peak (some may have reached it already) and perhaps even start evolving regressively towards the atoms of smaller scale. Obviously, these peaks are different for different species. Whales probably represent the maximum peak reachable on Earth.

Oscillations and fluctuations are relative and will not be apparent in all reference frames. Sometimes, energy will be observed as a pulse or a relatively non-changing (weakly evolving) phenomenon.

Oscillations can also be disturbed and fragmented.

It is, however, not hard to observe energy in the form of a human being as a pulse of energy growing from conception to a maximum then decaying until death and dissolving after it. Note, that no form of energy grows from nothing or decays to nothing. Growth is synchronized with defragmentation or accumulation while decay is synchronized with fragmentation or dissipation of energy.

As gravitons oscillate in energy they will also oscillate inter-species. The coupling of evolved gravitons with human bodies is explored in more details in follow-up works (including the evidence for it). Universes are self-similar (which stems from complete relativity) and this is why the frequency of existence applies to what we perceive as particles from our perspective and to what we perceive as human beings as well.

4.10 Relativistic uncertainty (conservation of relativity)

Generally, particles are waves whose properties like position and velocity are more or less spread, or more or less localized. Some properties are entangled in such a way that localization of one property results in the spreading of the other. Besides position and velocity, commonly mutually entangled properties on par-

ticular scale are lifetime and energy, where a particle with higher energy has a lower lifetime. As all observation is physical on some scale, no measurement can be performed without affecting the subject of measurement. This measurement will affect the spreading of the measured property, producing the inverse effect on the entangled property. No localization can be absolute, therefore, measurements are inherently limited in resolution.

The entanglement of the spread of values is commonly formulated as the Heisenberg uncertainty principle.

The Heisenberg uncertainty principle:

$$\sigma_x \sigma_y \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar$$

Here, \hbar is interpreted as an absolute constant, and as such, in fixed metric, it is limited to a specific scale of energies (resolution).

Relativistic uncertainty is a generalization of that uncertainty:

$$\sigma_x \sigma_y \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar_n$$

$$\hbar_n > 0$$

where \hbar_n is a *constant* of uncertainty relative to scale n. The sigma (σ) values represent the spreading of entangled properties x and y.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow -\infty} \sigma_x \sigma_y = 0$$

In conventional quantum physics quantum fluctuations are correlated with the time-energy uncertainty (entanglement). These fluctuations can be interpreted as "attempts" of virtual particles to pop into existence. With enough energy (e.g., in a strong electric or gravitational field) virtual particles can become real particles. But do the "attempts" in reality only become real once there is sufficient energy to create a real (observable) particle? Well, the zero-point energy is not absolute zero. A logical interpretation is that some real energy fluctuation is present. In CR, existence is relative and the transition from an unobservable energy to an observable one is simply oscillation of [the existence of] energy between different scales. It generally involves exchange between angular momentum components and coupling of energy with momentum conservation - it is not a sudden emergence or inflation of physical existence from nothing (mathematical abstraction).

In QED virtual particles are understood as nothing more than lines in Feynman diagrams used to calculate integrals (as alternative calculations exist - not involving virtual particles), or intermediate mathematical abstractions. However, quantum fluctuations do produce real measurable effects (such as the Casimir effect). Now, one can claim that, even though the effects are real, mediators are not. But this is similar to the claims that the wavefunction has no physical interpretation, space is not real, or that particles do not exist until measured. Such absurd notions are a consequence of excessive reductionism that could even be associated with a God complex (*If I can't measure it then it doesn't exist!*) and the abuse of the Ockham's razor. Even if one believes that reality is a computer-like simulation, that simulation must be running on a real *machine* at some level so the abstract mathematics that describes the production of effects without involving a physical interpretation is not a complete description of reality. Regarding non-existence of particles prior to measurement, a caveat, however, is in order. The truth is that a phenomenon that is interpreted as a particle may or may not exist as such until measured. In that sense, in some cases one could argue that a particle didn't exist before it was measured, however, it should be clear that particle creation is relative - the measured energy did exist in some form prior to measurement. Whether our mathematical description of that form is accurate or complete is questionable, however, in any case where the lack of physical interpretation would lead to absolutism, physical interpretation must exist.

We can describe the behaviour of macroscopic fluids or waves mathematically, yet no one claims that these fluids or waves are not real. Why assume then that fluctuations on some smaller scale are different? Yes, mathematics does not require physical interpretation, and mathematics agrees with measurement, so the assumption can be justified if one is doing calculations to describe effects in a limited domain. But it is not justified if one is trying to understand reality and actually progress in science. Absence of evidence is generally not evidence of absence. In this case, however, even the absence is questionable. We know that the universe is showing strong self-similarity, thus, rather than assume that smaller scales are radically different, what we observe on larger scale can be interpreted as evidence that something similar exists on smaller scales.

In example, the time-energy uncertainty:

$$\Delta E \Delta t \geq h$$

can be interpreted as:

$$\Delta(mv^2)\Delta t = \Delta(mv^2)\Delta\left(\frac{2\pi r}{v}\right) = \Delta(mv)\Delta s \geq h$$

$$\Delta p \Delta r \geq \hbar$$

Exchange of the angular period or the period of oscillation t (e.g., by the increase in v and a proportional decrease in r) for energy may result in a jump to a higher discrete vertical energy level - appearance of energy on a larger scale (its spread beyond the inherent limit of resolution/stability on that scale). If the rest energy on that particular scale was previously considered as a relative 0, this may be interpreted as a relative violation of energy conservation, allowed as long as the increase in energy (inflation/spreading of E) is inversely proportional to particle stability (Δt) on that scale.

However, period of stability here is the period of angular momentum, and in reality, energy is obviously conserved - it has simply changed scale [of spreading]. In CR, any rest mass is only relatively at rest and should be interpreted as energy in conserved/localized momenta. Note that oscillation between entangled properties is common in reality.

Note here the absurdity of the absolute invariance of physical laws. It requires for the uncertainty principle to be applicable only to a specific range of energies. It could not be applied to the Sun for example (only to the elementary particles it is composed of), as the assumption that such large energy is a consequence of small Δt would imply a Δt effectively equal to zero, which obviously doesn't match reality. However, it is a fact that the lifespan of stars decreases proportionally to the increase in energy. Isn't that a convincing hint that the *emergent* phenomena like stars should be treated as particles are treated, albeit with a properly scaled value of inherent uncertainty (\hbar)?

It is obvious that virtuality/reality of particles is relative (not only in CR, but in SR/GR as well because both energy and time are relative and can differ significantly, between highly curved and flat reference frames for example). Virtual particles, thus, may not exist from some reference frames, but, as noted before, it would be absurd to claim that undetectable energies do not absolutely exist. In CR, existence is reference frame (scale) relative.

Note that the relativistic uncertainty is one formulation of the conservation of total, and the exchange of [the amount of] specific, relativity. Not only is the absolute precision or absolute localization impossible, since everything is multidimensional, confinement of [relativity in] one dimension results in the spreading of [relativity in] the other.

This relationship is common for the dimensions of space (wavelength) and time inverse (frequency), e.g., in flat space-time:

$$\Delta x \Delta t^{-1} \leq c_n$$

Which, for $c_n = c_0 = c$ reduces to the absolute reference frame of SR/GR.

4.11 Zero

Absolute zero value of any variable represents absolute non-existence of phenomena in physical reality. Zeroes associated with existing observables should then be interpreted as relative zeroes.

In example, if a form of energy behaves as a wave on one scale, its energy may be equalized with frequency, in which case it may be assigned zero mass, however that zero should be understood as relative to excited medium - at some scale there are particles with inertial momentum increased proportionally to that frequency. These entangled quantized excitements of the medium can get concentrated at times of coupling/absorption, at which point the condensate could be interpreted as a particle and may be more appropriate to use non-zero mass. Thus, the mass itself could be interpreted as an aggregate of frequencies (momenta) of smaller scale, but the wave or frequency could equally be interpreted as an aggregate of mass (inertial momenta) of smaller scale. Whether it applies to mass or frequency, the value of zero is relative.

4.12 Infinity

Absolute infinity has no physical interpretation. While absolute infinities are useful in mathematics, in physical reality, these should be interpreted as relative infinities.

Consider the relativistic Lorentz factor applied to mass:

$$m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

By the equation, at speed c , mass of the particle would have to be absolutely infinite, implying that absolutely infinite energy is required to accelerate the particle to c .

However, in CR, the speed limit c is relative to [structure of] space and, even in GR the speed limit is equal to c only in case of flat space geometry. Adding energy to the particle will, at some large but finite value, start to significantly affect the structure of space and particle could, with asymmetry in density, even exceed the speed c .

Speed c is also considered to be the speed of massless particles in QM. However, standard *massless* particles will also slow significantly below c in strong gravitational potential (although local observer would measure no slowdown as units of distance are decreased proportionally).

Also, constituent quanta of space are of particular scale and not all scales of energy are equally sensitive to these (pressure/density of space is relative), thus, speed c can be exceeded by energies of extremely small scale too (although such energies may be unobservable for a particular observer).

Although momenta in a universe will be inevitably limited, in CR, c cannot be an absolute constant. Even if c is interpreted as proportional to the ratio of units of distance in space and time and these units scale with geometry (as in GR) conserving that ratio, the geometry itself must be relative.

Absolute infinity is an insurmountable problem for reality. This is why every observer (reference frame) must be limited. For any observer thus there exist limits to existence (observable energy) - maximum and minimum size of observable phenomena. As the limits are relative, they are also variable, but cannot ever become absolutely infinite (which is even mathematically obvious - for any number there is a bigger number).

4.13 Graviton (quantum of energy, soul)

Graviton is a real or effective source of a general force field - a more or less polarized quantum of space at some scale.

Real gravitons are sources of general force, while effective gravitons are induced by real gravitons and are carriers of the force through the general field.

Generally, real graviton may be considered as an elementary particle, while effective gravitons form its space. Effective gravitons are, however, themselves composed of real gravitons of smaller mass, and the *parent* real graviton itself may form [a part of an] effective graviton in other reference frames.

Note that the graviton as defined here is a generalized particle and should not be confused with the graviton in conventional quantum physics. To make a distinction, the conventional graviton will be referred to as "standard graviton".

The real graviton radius represents either a maximum or minimum of the force potential, depending whether the force is decreasing or increasing with distance of the effective gravitons from the real one. The gradient of potential will depend on the shape (dimensionality, or complexity) and energy of effective gravitons so it can progress linearly as well, rather than exponentially. Effective gravitons can be of different species or flavour so their ranges will differ. This can result in relatively sudden transformation from exponential to linear progression.

The associated well of gravitational potential of a graviton may be considered its *private* space, however, that *privacy* falls off with distance.

Elementary graviton has an intrinsic spin momentum, which can be quantized from some reference frames. This spin momentum is also relatively quantized with *constituent* smaller scale spin momenta, forming smaller scale sources

of force (these are generally centres of quantum vortices, where most energy is concentrated inside graviton space). Thus, large scale spin momentum (of the graviton) is strongly correlated with small scale momenta.

Graviton is a relative composite of neutral and polarized components (which themselves are relative composites). Polarization can be in the form of spin polarization, or charge polarization, all with different degrees of complexity, depending on graviton species. Resolvability of components is decreasing with the increasing number of components and the strength of confinement. A graviton formed/inflated through annihilation of particles may generally behave as an elementary particle.

Physics of a fundamental theory on reality cannot be limited to particles of specific scale or a reference frame. From certain reference frames, even living beings are particles, and *vice versa*.

Distinction between living and non-living forms of energy is very relative and physics will necessarily merge with biology in a successful attempt to understand the universes (because nature is certainly not an absolute reductionist, no matter how hard one tries to convince itself otherwise). In other papers I hypothesize that real graviton is, considering its nature, also a quantum/carrier of consciousness and I find it appropriate to use the term "soul" as its synonym. As complex bodies evolve from *simple* particles (although what evolves from what is in CR, with relative causality, relative), the souls evolve as well. Thus, what is described here may be interpreted as a simple or *elementary* graviton, its complex form may be interpreted as a relative superposition and localization of smaller scale gravitons just like the complex bodies may be interpreted as relative superposition and localization of smaller scale components. Forces or interactions evolve as well, from *elementary* ones to complex ones. Thus, what is interpreted as simple gravitational or electro-magnetic force between two gravitons on *elementary* scale, may be more complex between complex gravitons. The standard nuclear strong force is an example of such more complex force. In case of life-forms on the scale of animals on Earth, complex forces/interactions may be mental forces/interactions between the souls whose components may have billions of degrees of polarization (in these, associated spectrum of energy levels may be interpreted as continuous rather than discrete). Naturally, these mental interactions/forces are stronger between strongly entangled souls, which can be interpreted as a consequence of shorter distance in some dimension of space (including time), just like gravity is stronger for spatially closer bodies.

In general, gravitons act as attractors for specific entanglements in time/space, guiding interacting entities towards a specific future state.

4.13.1 Physical interpretation

Assuming the scale of a graviton is U_n , constituent quanta of space forming the associated gravitational well will be of mass scale U_{n-2} . With an locally empty gravitational well, graviton is considered to be naked (as such, it may be interpreted as a *dark matter* particle of certain scale). However, attracted particles of scale U_{n-1} will be coupling with quanta forming graviton's space (U_{n-2} scale gravitons) and such couplings will be considered as coupled mass or real mass forming the body of the U_n graviton. Mass of the naked graviton may be referred to as imaginary (img) mass. Total mass of the body-soul coupling is then the sum of img and real mass. In some interpretations, however, real mass may be shielding the img mass, in which case total mass will effectively be equal to real mass.

Note that these couplings will generally result in change of momenta for U_{n-2} particles - exchange of some orbital momenta for spin momenta (which may generally be interpreted as mass inflation or localization of mass to the U_{n-1} scale).

Elementary graviton can be excited and exist on different vertical energy levels (scales), however, on some scales the neutral (gravitational) component may dominate, on others its nature may be dominantly charged (e.g., electromagnetic). While real gravitons induce gradients in vacuum density (or space curvature), space inside of a real graviton from an internal reference frame may be globally flat on average, with extremely low density and temperature of [what would be interpreted from that frame as] matter, in equilibrium. However, high curvature should be present at the membrane, which represents a discontinuity between internal space and external space that has different properties. The membrane is closed and, in relatively stable states, has such shape, distribution of potential and rotation that the net gravitational effect on internal energy is a relative zero.

While temperature and density are both low globally within the graviton, high temperatures and densities are possible and do exist on smaller scales. The *particles* inside may be in condensed states and grouped into quantum vortices (galaxies) of certain scale.

It should be clear, however, that even if in some reference frames the sole difference may be in scale, equivalence between gravitons of different scale should generally be understood as more or less relative. The internal composition presented here is a hypothesis based on observations of large scale structures. While the external effects of gravitons are important, internal structure of smaller scale gravitons may be unobservable and consideration of effects within the gravitons will usually be

of low pragmatic value. Thus, when referring to space associated with a graviton, one will usually refer to the space forming its well of potential (e.g., the gravitational well), not its internal space.

The ground shape of a simple localized graviton is generally a torus. Relativistic momenta may distort the shape of a graviton, however, shape and distribution of mass of a graviton generally depends on its excitation state (which in some cases may be defined by quantum numbers) and how well it is localized. Travelling as a wave, its mutually entangled mass will be distributed over larger regions (and may be interpreted as wave-like excitation of existing *static* potential of space), with potential density maxima corresponding to the maxima of [the square of] the associated wave-function.

For a highly polarized graviton, structure may be highly ordered, with oppositely polarized inner components separated towards different sides of the membrane.

Figure 1: General shape of a simple graviton in ground state (no radial/angular nodes in the waveform)

Shape of a graviton is shown in Fig. 1, where the surface of a torus represents its membrane.

As a discrete quantum of space, graviton must have an membrane. Note that it is relatively easy to maintain existing conditions inside the graviton, as accumulation of particles is extremely hard due to flat space and low-density of matter. Any particle having a momentum perpendicular to the graviton may be accelerated inside (in most cases, the trajectory of the particle may be simply bent about the graviton surface), but will be equally decelerated again on exit. Collisions inside will be hard even if existing and passing particles are of the same scale, but if existing particles are of smaller

scale (discrete vertical energy levels differ in energy by multiple orders of magnitude), accumulation becomes almost impossible. In that case, graviton is relatively transparent (transparency is dependent on energy scale).

Note that polarization will be generally shaping a graviton into a *2-dimensional* ring, while neutralization is expanding it to a more spherical shape. To conserve volume, expansion will be decreasing the thickness of a torus, converging to a *2-dimensional* sphere [surface].

Recent analyses[6] have shown that the shape of the *local* universe is consistent with that of a torus[7]. Considering its characteristics, by the definition of a graviton here, the observable universe may be a part of a [large scale] graviton. More recent studies even provide evidence for the rotation of the observable universe - *fossilized* in the asymmetry of galactic spin momenta[8], further going in favour of the hypothesis.

If distances between galaxies (large scale quantum vortices) are increasing, this graviton is increasing its internal flatness and must be changing shape.

How is the neutral gravitational energy of a graviton exchanged with charged (e.g., electro-magnetic) energy in the transition between energy levels? Different interpretations are possible, but this should involve changes in momenta components. All components of graviton momenta are effectively exchangeable between vertical energy levels. Changes in vertical energy levels require energy transformation and thus may generally involve annihilation of particles on some scale as annihilation does imply transformation, as well as inflation and deflation of momenta components.

Since elementariness is relative, one can assume that the charge and spin magnetic momentum of an *elementary* charged particle stem from separation and difference in momenta between oppositely charged constituent particles. Since speed of information transfer is relative (in CR, it depends on scale), both orbital velocities of constituent charges and difference in velocities between constituent opposite charges may be converging to infinity with decreasing scale. And this velocity/difference can be annihilated *into* mass/radius.

Note that relativistic energy can have different interpretation between scales. E.g., interpretation of velocity may be effectively scale variant. On one scale, velocity, or difference in velocity, generates mass (mass is relativistic), on the other it generates charge (charge is relativistic). High orbital velocity of standard quarks is considered to be the main contributor to the rest masses of standard protons. High orbital velocity of constituent particles of quarks and electrons may be the main contributor to their charges and spin magnetic momenta.

Charged gravitons, in addition to gravitational field *tubes* (which have ring-like and spherical eigenstates), possess both electric and magnetic field *tubes*. What are magnetic field tubes?

In CR, magnetic field lines are relative lines, in reality they are tubes, or toruses (which may be deformed).

These tubes can be interpreted as induced polarized effective gravitons perpendicular to the primary graviton, or polarized dimensions of space (polarized subspaces) for a charged graviton. They can also be interpreted as tubes of entanglement between charged gravitons.

If the primary graviton is of U_{n-1} scale, space in the associated magnetic field *lines* is formed by particles of U_{n-3} scale. More complex forces with multiple degrees and species of polarization can be correlated with mutually entangled different species of potential, or fields of potential, with forces mediated through different species of dimensions of space (or entanglement). All of this is evolvable and nature of force can change over time. More complex forms should be more plastic but no *law* of nature is an absolute law.

4.13.2 Wave-like behaviour

Each and every graviton must have a rest mass greater than absolute 0. Rest mass, however, is only one part of its total energy, a part that can be correlated with its *intrinsic* (stable) frequency (even in a localized/corpuscular form, the waveform is still there - even if unresolvable by the observer). However, a graviton can be excited and delocalized, and this excitation [of frequency] will form the other part of its total energy. In a delocalized (wave-like) form, graviton will generally spread in a spherical wave-form, with its rest mass usually spread isotropically across the spherical shell. However, in case the graviton has a non-zero total spin, the other part of energy will be more localized on the sphere and the spreading of that energy will be proportional to its wavelength.

The density of energy across the waveform is proportional to the probability of localization (wavefunction collapse) at that point - once the graviton is absorbed/coupled to external mass/energy. Thus, even if the graviton waveform is spreading in all directions, the point on the sphere with highest energy concentration can be interpreted as the direction of propagation relative to the point of emission.

The higher the frequency and the more spin-polarized gravitons (e.g., photons) there are in coherent superposition the behaviour will be less wave-like and more corpuscular-like.

In any case, the waveform is composed of particles (excitations) of smaller-scale, but they are strongly mutually entangled (distance in space between them may grow, but distance in time is conserved) and strongly confined to the waveform (this is why the absorption on some scales cannot be partial - as evident by the strong frequency dependence of photon absorption in atoms).

Waves, however, do not necessarily represent spreading gravitons. Space is generally a fluid-like medium (with pressure/density gradients), the disturbance of which can result in production of Rayleigh or ocean-like waves. In such waves

there is no strong entanglement between constituent excitations - collapse of the waveform to a single *point* (complete singular absorption) is usually highly unlikely, partial energy absorption is common. Such waves can be considered massless relative to the medium, but, again, not absolutely - as the excitations (space-forming gravitons) are quantized on some scale and represent absorbed energy from the source of disturbance - not part of the rest mass of the medium.

Difference thus exists between a graviton that is travelling (expanding) as a wave and a medium-forming gravitons that are oscillating *in situ* even if the medium-forming gravitons are of the same scale as the constituent small-scale gravitons of the expanding graviton waveform. This difference is in the form/strength of the entanglement between the components of the wave. In other words, even if the components are relatively equal, one wave is transporting them as a discrete quantum of energy of larger scale, the other as a continuous spectrum of energies of smaller scale.

4.13.3 Space-forming gravitons

Space-forming gravitons of an U_n graviton are of U_{n-2} scale. These space-forming gravitons are hypothesized to *orbit* the centre of the larger (U_n) graviton. If the U_n graviton is completely naked, all the U_{n-2} gravitons are uncoupled/non-localized and may form radially standing waves (the semi-major orbital radius is relatively constant) of angular velocity equal to c_{n-1} .

In example, for an graviton of U_1 scale (e.g., one coupled to Earth's body), the angular velocity of space-forming gravitons is equal to c_0 , which is equal to the standard speed of light (c), 2.99792458×10^8 m/s. Is the orbital motion the proper interpretation for the motion of non-coupled space-forming gravitons? When uncoupled, these gravitons are dominantly (1st order) entangled with the large scale graviton (U_n) and may be constantly spiralling between the U_n graviton radius and their own range. However, one interpretation of this spiralling motion is orbital precession.

Once localized (with coupling to real mass), some (or most, depending on the amount of coupling real mass) of the angular velocity is exchanged for spin momentum, thus, the orbital velocity of the coupling becomes lower than c_{n-1} (e.g., Keplerian).

Even though graviton orbitals may be spherical, coupling of space-forming gravitons usually occurs on the equatorial region of that orbital. This is because localization is proceeding through steps (which can be interpreted as energy levels of complexity or graviton dimensionality).

Thus, the graviton first collapses to a ring-like form, before localizing to a specific body within that ring. In equilibrium, inclination of the orbital is fixed, but the whole orbital rotates with the velocity equal to the orbital velocity of bodies.

Consider Earth, for example. Its non-coupled space-forming gravitons are rotating (*orbiting*) at the standard speed of light, but their orbitals themselves are rotating at the speed of Earth's body at the orbital radius (rotational period of the orbital thus currently being equal to about 24 h for orbital radii equal or lower than the Earth's surface radius). With the inclination fixed and step-like localization, all couplings (incarnations) of the same graviton may occur along a specific ring (even though the decouplings may not). In one interpretation, multiple entangled gravitons or components of a graviton are involved, where one graviton [component] remains uncoupled. The entanglement is relatively broken once one [component] couples to a body of real mass, but is then restored after decoupling (so the graviton [component] returns to the same orbital - which can be interpreted as *background entanglement*). The two components could be interpreted similarly to the group and phase components of momenta. One spins at the speed of light and rotates with the body, the other may be at rest relative to the orbital but oscillates radially, and it is this component that is coupling with bodies. Localization probability distribution will then depend on its frequency - number of angular nodes.

Note that as the soul (graviton) is coupled to a body, its size/energy in space is well defined (less spread) but its location in time is more spread so the two can be correlated through the uncertainty principle. Consider, for example, souls coupled to human bodies. While the adult bodies remain of relatively fixed size in space, their location through time can vary considerably and is much less predictable. If the spread of the body represents (or, is proportional to) the spread of the soul, this suggests that the body fixed at one location will have to continuously increase its spread (weight or energy) to satisfy the uncertainty. This could be correlated with the fast growth of embryos, fixed in an egg/uterus which itself is usually relatively fixed. It can also be correlated with the continuous spread and growth of trees, which are fixed to one location for life. This can then be generally correlated with health - bodies that do not grow in energy and also do not move are at the highest risk of death (forced spread of energy through decomposition and decay). There are inherent limits to both, growth and motion, however, these limits and rates of ageing (time dilation) differ between different species and subspecies of life.

Both, evolution and development of organisms, probably involve quantum or quantum-like entanglement at different scales[9], an entanglement whose stability generally depends on pressure/temperature associated

with particular scale - not necessarily the standard pressure/temperature (correlated with kinetic energy of standard atoms/molecules).

The space-forming gravitons have different ranges (energies) and density of these gravitons falls off with distance (generally exponentially). Different interpretations exist for why these particles remain in orbit or confined, rather than being radiated away. In any case, the non-zero positive rest mass implies they have a range. Confinement to that range can be interpreted as a coupling to positive pressure either of the enclosed mass-energy or traversed mass-energy by the wavefront.

Effectively, the enclosed mass for them represents an effective or relative black hole so they cannot travel further and instead form a relative equivalent of a photon circle correlated with conventional black holes (where the surface tension is 1/2 of the surface density in a thin-shell approximation, in GR framework[10]). Depending on case, this may require running coupling. In any case, they could be considered as representing a part of the large scale graviton (U_n) - they are, in any case, entangled with it and are spatially extending its presence (in a wave form, spin momentum is certainly a more appropriate interpretation than an orbital momentum). This can be interpreted as a physical manifestation of the quantum wavefunction of the large scale graviton, where its location probability decreases with distance (square of distance, usually).

Note that, in spacetime metrics, gravitational acceleration can be interpreted as a density of space per the area of time. Usually the time is multiplied by c so the time dimension becomes equivalent to space. In CR, however, the value of c is scale dependent. In any case, obviously, a space-forming graviton also represents a quantum of a time dimension. The strength, or intensity, of the gravitational coupling is proportional to the density of space (number of space-forming gravitons per the area of coupling). If a large scale graviton is not well localized (the number of radial nodes is greater than zero), multiple gravitational maxima will exist in a gravitational well. This, coupled with different dimensionality of space-forming gravitons associated with different maxima can solve the gravitational anomalies, commonly attributed to *dark matter*.

The entanglement between the graviton of a larger scale (U_n) and U_{n-2} gravitons can be lost (e.g., when the U_n graviton itself is delocalized or changes scale), which is then interpreted as decoupling of the U_n graviton from local space and the body of real mass that may exist in the well. The fate of U_{n-2} gravitons will depend on the local environment and whether they are localized or not. Generally, however, the stability of the gravitational well is reduced.

Due to their standing (*static*) nature and confinement to a particular po-

tential well associated with a *parent* graviton of larger scale, the space-forming gravitons will generally be referred to as *static* particles.

4.13.4 Effects of graviton interaction and oscillation

The constituent quanta of one graviton will weakly interact with constituent quanta of another graviton. However, in case of stronger entanglement the two may form a superposition in space and probability for interaction may increase.

Superposition is, of course, relative, and if gravitons are of different scale, orbital radii of constituent quanta will be different.

What happens to the gravity of a graviton confined within another graviton, assuming both are of similar energy (of the same or similar magnitude)? It is possible that extroverted gravity simply becomes the sum of gravity of all gravitational sources, however, relative confinement of inner gravity (inner effective gravitons) is possible as well. The reason for this is the non-zero mass of effective gravitons, which implies limited range of gravity. Thus, those with shorter range can be confined within the radius of an outer graviton.

Note that the outer graviton, although considered as another distinct graviton, may be entangled with the inner one and the two could be considered as maxima of potential of a single, albeit less localized, graviton.

In the extreme case of confinement, the outer real graviton may be effectively shielding the gravity of the inner real graviton.

It may be even possible for some effective gravitons with longer range to be *assimilated* by the outer graviton but probability for that should be proportional to their mass and, thus, inversely proportional to their range.

Confinement must be relative, however, and some inner gravity should always *leak*, with highest probability at the poles. The same effect can be produced even with a single graviton oscillating between different radii, assuming field information transfer is slower than graviton oscillation. This then suggests that gravity may be generally stronger at the poles of spherical bodies, even in perfectly spherical (non-rotating) ones (if such could exist). However, if the general form of a graviton is torus-like, as hypothesized, openings on the poles may generally have non-zero radii and lower gravity than otherwise expected on the poles, may be more likely. This should be even more pronounced in polarized gravitons where converging magnetic field lines concentrate particles along the magnetic field lines between the poles.

In other work, I hypothesize that large scale gravitons (which may be inflated from smaller scale) are commonly involved in the formation of stars and planetary bodies. The inflation (or initial over-inflation followed by deflation and stabilization at the new energy level) of a graviton is relatively synchronized with the clumping of real mass (ordinary matter) and makes the process of formation much faster and possible even in cases of strongly diluted real mass (like in the Kuiper belt of the Solar System, for example).

Mass in planetary bodies should then be differentiated not only vertically, but horizontally as well, with lower density at the poles and possibly even with tubes (tunnels) connecting poles of large scale gravitons, or different horizontal energy levels in case of a single oscillating graviton - although these tunnels in terrestrial bodies may have to be filled with fluids to ensure long-term stability.

Note that Earth's surface gravity is greater on the poles, but that is a consequence of the reduction of the surface radius due to redistribution of mass towards the equator. Directly below poles mass density is lower than elsewhere. Are there tunnels below? Long-lived tunnels, except near gravitons, seem unlikely due to generally increasing pressure with depth, however, fluid density should be increasing with depth as well. High polarization and angular momentum of the wall material can increase the stability of such tubes but this is not expected in terrestrial bodies. Long term stability could be ensured with appropriate density of energy levels and relatively frequent oscillation of large scale gravitons as this provides multiple density maxima. Lateral density gradient (with increasing density away from the pole) also decreases pressure on the tube and such gradients are likely for rotating bodies (note that Earth rotated much faster during formation). Otherwise, tunnels may be only periodically recreated (solids remelt). I suspect that on bodies like Earth the fluids involved should be [salty] water and magma, with dominant fluid probably depending on the pole. Land should be depressed at the entrance where water is involved, however, it may be elevated on the pole where magma is involved. Interestingly, the subglacial topographic depression in Antarctica known as Wilkes land anomaly (elsewhere hypothesized 480 km wide impact crater, which would make it the largest impact crater on Earth) was directly antipodal to Siberian Traps (largest known volcanic event in the last 500 million years) during the Permian-Triassic boundary (Siberian Traps are considered to be the primary cause for the Permian-Triassic extinction, largest mass extinction on Earth). It is questionable whether impacts alone can cause such large volcanism on the other side of the planet (although they can certainly cause widespread earthquakes and smaller volcanism). However, the recreation of tunnels with graviton oscillation (likely correlated with impacts) could result in such phenomena at antipodal locations - [enhancing] depression on the side of impact (water entrance/exit), bulges or traps at the side of magma expulsion (masking the depression). If Earth is modelled as a living being, different products on entrance and exit are expected. As tectonic plates move with time, the locations on the surface should move as well. I believe that all major mass extinctions are correlated with recreation of the tunnels. The Siberian Traps are already considered to be a result of a mantle plume which effectively is a *temporary* creation of a tunnel between the

planet's core and surface through which magma flows upwards. Antipodal volcanism is common to large craters of the Moon and Mars[11] and there are other examples of antipodal relationships on Earth involving large igneous provinces and hotspots (Yellowstone, for example, is antipodal to French Southern and Antarctic Lands). All of these may be correlated with oscillation of large scale gravitons and associated temporary recreation/reactivation of tunnels. In fact, deep mantle plumes may not be possible without it. In a complementary paper I also hypothesize that both volcanism and impacts occur during major mass extinctions. In fact, energy level changes cannot be absolutely spontaneous and large impacts can be interpreted as relative triggers of energy level changes of large scale gravitons. If graviton is, at the time of impact, oriented in such way that its axis of rotation is aligned with the impact site, and this should be likely at least for impacts occurring near the poles (possibly nearer magnetic ones if these are present) and/or stronger impacts, then the impact can be correlated with antipodal volcanism. In that case, the seismic energy generated by the impact further stimulates the flow of fluids through the tunnels, increasing the effect on surface (the impact does create chimneys of stress connecting the impact source with the antipodal location[12]). Generally, however, impact sites may not be aligned with the graviton axis and the magnitude of extinction then should be proportional to the alignment. The exceptional magnitude of Permian-Triassic extinction thus can be explained as a result of unusually high alignment.

4.13.5 Acquisition of matter (coupling with matter, acquisition of smaller scale energy quanta)

A naked (uncoupled) U_n graviton will effectively attract particles of U_{n-1} scale (with the attraction mediated by the space-forming U_{n-2} gravitons). There are now two possibilities on the effect of total gravity:

1. with inflation and coupling of an U_n .space constituent U_{n-2} graviton with an U_{n-1} particle (U_{n-1} graviton, which may be naked or coupled to real mass itself), one graviton is shielding the other, energy equal to the energy of the U_{n-1} particle is confined and there is no increase in gravity of the well with acquisition of U_{n-1} matter,
2. there is no shielding and total gravity of the well is increased with acquired matter.

Note that the 1. possibility may be interpreted as one particle giving mass to the other. Regardless of the outcome, the interaction could affect the range of gravity of the system. Constituent gravitons of space of U_{n-1} gravitons are of U_{n-3} scale which are orders of magnitude less massive, thus, with no significant shielding, the range of gravity is extended (with a caveat - range extension, or the strength of coupling, is [energy] scale relative).

Note that each graviton has finite capacity for coupling - number of constituent quanta is not infinite, however, with range extension the initial capacity can be increased.

Note also that the violation of energy conservation in case of shielding is relative - even though gravity may be unchanged (relatively) the total energy is conserved by confinement and will be released with decoupling.

Since real graviton represents a maximum of gravitational potential it will form a discontinuity in the system. Electro-magnetic nature of a graviton will concentrate polarized matter in the equatorial region, while neutral matter can start concentrating in the centre with collisions.

Real mass may be attracted and enter the central region through one or the other pole and collision in the centre can result in concentration. Another possibility for central concentration is acquisition of mass through equatorial regions during the contraction (localization) of the graviton, when the real mass (e.g., dust) can be accelerated towards the centre.

Gravitons forming space may be referred to as *static* (also, being directly undetectable, virtual) graviton neutrinos when they carry neutral gravitational force (should not be confused with standard neutrinos), or *static* (also, virtual) photons when they carry electro-magnetic force.

Coupling of standard matter (e.g., standard atoms) with the gravitational well of a large scale graviton is then the coupling of *static* graviton neutrinos and *static* photons with this matter.

However, for a large body (composite of atoms) in the gravitational well it is convenient to consider it coupled with the effective graviton of larger mass, rather than with individual small scale *static* particles.

In that case, mass and velocity of the effective graviton are total mass and average velocity of coupled *static* gravitons, respectively, while the effective graviton forms the toroidal [large scale] quantum of space which the coupled standard matter is traversing in its orbit about the real graviton. Here, thus, the energy of this large scale effective graviton is proportional to the intensity of the gravitational coupling with matter.

If the whole observable universe is a part of a large scale graviton, galaxies and planetary systems may be a result of inflation and coupling of its constituent quanta. One of my hypotheses is that at least one discontinuity (e.g., between inner and outer core) within a planet represents an large scale graviton energy level and, thus, also [at times at least]

the radius of a real graviton that has been inflated from the scale of a standard atom, or even a much smaller scale. This is further explored in follow-up/complementary papers.

Energy of a gravitational field can be lost, either with the escape of real mass together with the coupled static (virtual) gravitons, or with the disturbance of the field that results in annihilation of virtual gravitons. Note however, that a product of annihilation also has a finite range, and the lost energy can be compensated. If, however, the lost energy is not compensated, the large scale graviton (U_n graviton) associated with the field may change horizontal energy level, once the certain threshold of lost energy is reached. At some point, a change in vertical energy level may also occur, which can be interpreted as death of the local soul-body coupling, unless the decoupling is temporary (i.e., a temporary loss of consciousness). Relativity in causality applies here as well - the change in U_n energy level may precede loss of energy of smaller scale.

4.13.6 Rings revealing graviton presence

Rings of matter have been observed about space bodies of various sizes. In conventional theories, longer-lived rings are only possible when tidal forces are present, preventing the material to coalesce into a single body. Rings of material beyond the Roche limit of a body are thus unexpected and difficult to explain. However, such rings have been observed, e.g., about the trans-Neptunian body Quaoar[13]. The presence of a naked large scale graviton can easily explain such rings. Since the average location of gravitons is generally not random, orbital resonance could hint at the presence of a large scale graviton (which may be interpreted as a ring of dark matter). The matter composing the ring is then not only orbiting the central body but the naked graviton too. If this graviton has a ring-like form, spiral motion of constituent matter about the graviton is likely too (similar to the spiral motion present in Saturn's F ring).

In conventional theories on gravity and planetary formation, it would take a significant amount of time for a ring to coalesce into a single body and any sudden changes are not expected. However, if the ring suddenly collapses into a single body, this would be clear evidence for the presence of a large scale graviton collapsing (localizing) from an orbital to orbiting spin momentum.

It appears that evidence for this already exists[14].

This would also result in transfer of energy from the ring (graviton) to the central body of the system. If the orbital radius changes too then the process should also imply transfer of energy between different systems.

4.13.7 Supermassive evidence

Some celestial bodies have masses too large to be explained by conventional formation theories. In example, a massive planet orbiting a tiny star can be a big problem[15] due to limited amount of dust in formation rings. This can be easily explained with massive large scale gravitons. If the dark matter mass (associated with the graviton) is on the order of total mass of the body, its real mass content (and thus required dust for formation) could be low.

Graviton mass in ice-worlds (Neptunian planets), gas giants and stars may be an order of magnitude higher than coupled real mass. In case of terrestrial worlds, *vice versa* is probably true.

Conventional theories on planetary formation have troubles explaining how larger bodies actually form from dust grains[16].

Another problem for conventional theories is the fast formation of these bodies, e.g., supermassive black holes or galaxies in the early universe. Inflation and deflation (collapse) of gravitons should be a relatively fast process and this can then explain any sudden and fast accumulation or concentration of mass, like fast collapse of formation discs - in case of formation of planetary bodies, or early appearance of supermassive black holes[17] (for which real mass content, compared to graviton mass, could be negligible).

4.13.8 Finite energy

Since absolute point sources of energy are impossible, maximum field strength of a graviton is at a non-zero distance from centre. Thus, equations producing infinities for field sources are simply not valid *below* a certain radius (radius of a graviton in this case).

For distances greater than the graviton radius, graviton can be approximated as a point source of force, while below that radius force drops to relative zero - for any point inside, for an ideal non-rotating graviton (with a uniform mass distribution) and no other gravitons inside.

Thus, the equation of force (approximation) is then, in example of Newtonian gravity:

$$F = \delta_{ij} \frac{GMm}{r^2}$$

$$i = \frac{r - r_0}{|r - r_0|}, j = 1$$

r_0 = graviton radius

r = distance from graviton centre

δ_{ij} = Kronecker delta

Obviously, if there are any sources of gravity below r_0 and these are not balanced by other forces (e.g., centrifugal), the graviton would collapse. To prevent this collapse, a repulsive force must exist - either *fictional* (e.g., provided by the graviton angular momentum) or *real* (in case of specific entanglement, e.g., charge). In reality, both should be present to some degree. Near the graviton radius, point source approximation is not valid anymore and its relativity should be taken into account, as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Force of a graviton

With no absolute zero distances there are no absolutely infinite densities either and mechanisms will exist preventing absolute collapse. One of these, as mentioned already, can be rotation (angular momentum), which is probably one reason why it is intrinsic in *fundamental* sources of energy.

Thus, in all sources of forces of attraction there must exist a production of effective repulsion, which will cancel attraction at some distance/scale.

4.13.9 Graviton flavour

Since all particles have mass, all are prone to the oscillation of flavour between couplings. Different flavours can be interpreted as different discrete local vertical energy levels. Generally, 3 major flavours exist for any particle (not counting the flavour corresponding to a naked graviton), and a non-localized particle (graviton) may be considered to be in a superposition of the 3 basis states. There is no change of average energy during flavour oscillation, however, there is a change in the scale of the *gravitational imprint* (due to change in graviton radius) proportional to the mass associated with certain flavour. At the time of graviton localization, assuming there is enough energy, rest mass of the graviton can be changed, when it will, depending on the current flavour, settle in one of the 3 mass eigenstates.

The gravitational imprint has gravitational mass and should be associated with the img mass of the graviton, which is equal to the total mass for a naked (uncoupled) graviton. While this mass should not change for inertial motion (lacking acceleration) it may change with graviton localization or acceleration relative to local space. Generally, acquired energy will be a sum of img and real mass, where proportions will depend on interpretation and local conditions. Due to different scales involved between img and real mass, depending on a reference frame, changes in one may appear sharp/discrete, in other slow/continuous.

The gravitational imprint can be interpreted as a curvature of space, or dark matter, of scale U_{n-2} for a graviton of U_n scale. Gravitational imprint (space) is, thus, stretching and compressing with the oscillation of the graviton radius. Note that graviton may be acquiring and shedding (oscillating) some amount of real mass of smaller scale during flight, which, with no full collapse, may be interpreted as oscillating partial localization. The magnitude of this effect will depend on the properties of the medium. In high vacuum the effect may be negligible, however, in some media the speed of propagation may be significantly affected, due to momentum conservation. If, at the point of localization, there is not enough energy for the graviton to settle into the mass eigenstate associated with the current flavour, the graviton is most likely to settle into one of the possible flavours. However, the speed of time is scale dependent and time dilation will thus exist between scales, so the transition will appear continuous from some reference frames. In such frames, total mass (which includes acquired real mass) can deviate from the mass associated with the eigenstate. Locally stored kinetic energy may also be interpreted as gravitational mass from these frames.

Since flavour and mass eigenstates cannot be absolutely synchronized, gravitons inflated on large scale (where time is significantly slowed down compared to the reference frame) may have long-lived unfilled gravitational wells (real mass capacitance). The unfilled capacity may generally be more likely to be concentrated in the outer regions of the well, however, this will depend on the graviton radius and whether multiple gravitons are present (which generally should be the case). Indeed, this naked gravitational imprint is commonly detectable in galaxies, as dark matter. However, these imprints should be present in planetary systems as well, although any unfilled capacity may be mostly concentrated within the bodies. However, rather than unfilled capacity, flat velocity curves can be explained by the change in the intensity differential of gravitational coupling with distance (e.g., change of graviton energy and shape from the 2-dimensional spherical form into a ring-like form). Proper interpretation of kinetic energy The value of kinetic energy is relative, however, energy will be locally acquired and released during changes in velocity (acceleration) relative to local space. Absolutely constant velocities do not exist and, since space is physical, any motion relative to space will involve absorption and emission of

energy, but this may be interpreted as relatively constant motion if absorption and emission are equal and cannot be resolved. Momentum is coupled to energy, however, in cases where there is no motion relative to certain [scale of] space, one may consider kinetic energy as fictional and manifested only at the time of interaction (localization) when the interaction results in local increase in energy, when some energy may be inflated from smaller scale. All energy thus consists of real and imaginary parts of some scale, but, unlike in conventionally common complete reductionism, in CR, neither may have an absolute zero value, only a relative one.

Whether the [part of] kinetic energy is produced upon interaction or is carried by momentum, it probably should be associated with flavour of gravitons, and thus [inflation of] physical gravitational imprints (img mass) proportional to the kinetic energy. Note that this does not forbid the inflation of flavour beyond the mass eigenstates, such inflation only implies relative instability.

4.13.10 Energy in the gravitational imprint, reality and illusion of a universe

For a simple graviton in orbital motion, this is generally satisfied:

$$m \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_s^2}{c_s^2}}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_a^2}{c_a^2}}} \right) v_a r_a = n \hbar$$

m = rest mass
 v_s = spin velocity
 c_s = spin velocity limit = information speed limit in spin space
 v_a = orbital velocity
 c_a = orbital velocity limit = information speed limit in orbital space
 r_a = orbital radius
 \hbar = quantization constant

The first relativistic term (enclosed in parentheses) here represents the energy in the gravitational imprint due to angular motion relative to spin space (space associated with the source of the spin momentum), the other relativistic term represents the energy in the gravitational imprint due to angular motion relative to the orbital space (space associated with the source of the orbital momentum). The n may be an integer, half-integer, or something more complex, depending on graviton nature and interpretation (reference frame of quantization).

Note how apparent here it is what amount of illusion (and nonsense) can be created with the assumption of an absolute reference frame, where $c_s = c_a = c$.

Reduced orbital wavelength of the graviton is:

$$\lambda_r = \frac{r_a}{n}$$

Which is, for $v_a = c_0 = c$, $c_s \gg v_s$, $c_a \gg c$, and $n = 1$, equal to reduced Compton wavelength, which is the reduced wavelength of a photon whose energy is equal to the rest energy of the particle. But, in general, it is the reduced wavelength of a non-excited particle in a non-relativistic uniform motion, at standard light speed.

Reduced wavelength is simply a wavelength divided by 2π , which then represents the orbital or spin radius in case of angular motion.

For a particle with no orbital momentum:

$$m \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_s^2}{c_s^2}}} \right) v_s r_s = n_s \hbar$$

$r_s =$ spin radius

Reduced wavelength (or, reduced spin wavelength) of the graviton is:

$$\lambda_r = \frac{r_s}{n_s}$$

With $v_s = c$ and $c_s \gg c$, this reduces to the Compton wavelength. It is obvious here that a realistic result requires $c_s \gg c$, otherwise (with $c_s = c$), one has to reduce rest mass or radius to 0 in order not to obtain infinite spin momentum.

And this is exactly the assumption in QM - particles like photons are assumed to have zero mass, while particles like electrons are treated as point particles (zero radius). In other words, reality has been reduced to illusion.

Experiments have shown that the radius of a localized electron must be much smaller than its reduced Compton wavelength, and even much smaller than its classical radius. This implies that the contribution of electron charge energy to electron's rest mass is very small, even negligible, as according to some experiments[18] the upper limit to electron's radius is 10^{-22} m.

Reduced Compton wavelength of the electron is 3.86×10^{-13} m. Radius the electron would have if all its mass would come from the potential en-

ergy of its charge, ignoring quantum effects, is 2.8×10^{-15} m (classical electron radius). It should be clear, however, that the electron's radius is not absolutely fixed, it can be associated with a specific local energy level occupied by the constituent particles of the electron. Bonding and measurement (confinement), obviously, can affect the spreading of the electron's waveform (radius). Radius is quantized, but relatively - transition between different radii will be continuous from reference frames where the transition is significantly time-dilated.

Thus, its rest mass effectively originates in the spin momentum of its neutral body mass, not charge. For an electron at rest, taking into account spin momentum magnitude, rather than its projection, this should then be satisfied:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_s^2}{c_s^2}}} = \frac{\sqrt{3}\hbar}{2m_e r_s v_s} = k$$

$$\frac{v_s^2}{c_s^2} = 1 - \frac{1}{k^2}$$

$$c_s^2 = \frac{v_s^2}{1 - \frac{1}{k^2}}$$

$$m_e = \text{electron rest mass} = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$$

$$\hbar = \text{reduced Planck's constant} = 1.054571817 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js}$$

For the mass radius $r_s = 1 \times 10^{-22}$ m, and assuming $v_s = c_0 = c = 2.99792458 \times 10^8$ m/s, one obtains $c_s \approx c$ (only slightly larger than c). But what are the actual values of r_s , v_s , and c_s in reality? For practical purposes, one might assume that $v_s = c_s = c$ and, thus, $r_s = 0$, but in reality r_s must be larger than 0 and both v_s and c_s may be larger than c rather than c_s alone. In case of particles of this scale, however, c_s may be equal to c , with v_s being slightly smaller. Thus, the assumption of a locally relativistic spin does not require for the electron to rotate faster than c (classically, for this radius, v_s would simply have to be larger than c by about 10 orders of magnitude).

Why does a localized electron has to spin twice (in case of a spin projection of $1/2 \hbar$) to return to the same state? Physically, this is a consequence of 1:2 resonance between two different rotating components of the electron. Since the radius of the electron must be greater than zero and energy distribution cannot be absolutely homogenous, the electron doesn't only have an intrinsic spin momentum, it always has some orbital momentum as well. Thus, this resonance may be a local spin-orbit resonance (barycentre of orbital rotation is different from the barycentre of

spin rotation). In reality, situation can be more complex (e.g., presence of inclination or axial tilt).

For the force carrier particles, v_a is generally fixed to c_n (or, close to c_n - in reality), which represents information transfer limit in space associated with the vertical energy level (scale) n . Reduced Compton wavelength for such particles is also their range. It is clear that in particles of variable wavelength, with fixed v_a (which can now be interpreted as propagation velocity) and fixed spin momentum, spin momentum components must be variable (in such way to conserve the spin momentum). For particles like photons, spin velocity v_s should be proportional to frequency and r_s should be inversely proportional to frequency. If flavour (gravitational imprint) oscillates between different eigenstates (and it does in reality for any particle), it is the velocity v_s that should oscillate as well (proportionally). If v_a remains fixed (in reality it too should oscillate but this may be negligible), to conserve total momentum, the range must oscillate as well (and should be inversely proportional to mass and frequency).

Generally, for any naked graviton (graviton coupled to relatively negligible mass), $v_n \approx c_n$. Once graviton couples to matter (higher mass, associated with particular eigenstate), v_n decreases significantly.

Knowing the radius (range) of the observable universe, one can obtain the upper limit for standard cosmological photon rest mass in the lowest mass eigenstate. Its relativistic mass is:

$$m = \frac{\hbar}{rc} = 8 \times 10^{-70} \text{ kg}$$

$$r = \text{radius of the observable universe} = 46.508 \times 10^9 \text{ ly} = 4.4 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}$$

$$c = \text{standard speed of light} = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$$

Thus, its lowest rest mass eigenstate must be lower than that.

Note that, if naked gravitons travel at fixed and maximum possible velocity in some space c_n , the relativistic mass term associated with that space should be discarded, unless coupling of the graviton with matter is interpreted as increase in graviton mass, in which case the term may be adjusted so that the deviation (i.e., decrease) from c_n is proportional to mass increase. In case of the photon, its angular orbital (propagation) velocity is assumed to be equal to $c_0 = c$. If the associated term is then discarded, relativistic mass of the photon depends only on its spin velocity v_s . If one further assumes that $v_s \approx c_s$ (photon is naked relative to c_s as well), photon's rest mass should be roughly equal to the calculated relativistic mass.

Of course, if the universe is expanding this value will further decrease. Assuming, however, that the universe's expansion is a result of transfor-

mation of photon's (or any other streaming graviton's) relativistic energy into dark energy (should be the case if total energy density remains constant) then a limit to expansion must exist - the universe should stop expanding once the relativistic mass becomes equal to the rest mass. Assuming now that the space is quantized by gravitons such as photons, the universe is expanding because the quanta of intergalactic space are expanding - proportionally to wavelength and spin radius (r_s) increase (physical dilation). Note that, in order for these to expand, their rest mass must be greater than zero (otherwise relativistic mass makes no sense - there would be no energy to lose). But why are they expanding? They are expanding because they are losing relativistic energy, which is dominantly gravitational and electro-magnetic energy. Losing energy to what? Probably gravitons of different scale that they are entangled with - e.g., those forming supermassive black holes. This is the interaction between large scale gravitons and [small scale] gravitons forming their space, where, in effect, the mass of the source of force is increasing at the expense of the mass of carriers of that force - extending the range of force in the process.

Note that this implies the cycling of the universe between expansion and contraction because once the limit of expansion is reached the universe becomes static, which is an extremely unstable state (absolutely static state is even impossible in CR). Note that the range cannot be absolute zero either, which implies that the universe cannot contract to absolute zero size (which is impossible in CR anyway).

Assuming universe collapses to a single object (large scale superposition of large scale gravitons), with the mass of 3.53×10^{54} kg, \hbar equal to reduced Planck's constant and $c_n = c$, its range would be 9.96×10^{-98} m (this range should be interpreted as orbital radius, while the spin radius is much larger). Note that this can be interpreted as near absolute zero temperature of large scale, where all the large scale gravitons form a bosonic condensate. This is also an extremely unstable state, so the universe explodes, beginning a new cycle. Note that the non-zero initial orbital radius (mass barycentre offset) implies non-homogenous energy distribution, which is then reflected in CMB anisotropy.

In other words, CMB anisotropy can be interpreted as evidence that the universe did not start from an absolute singularity - a point-like graviton [superposition]. If large scale gravitons are not point-like, and energy can be exchanged between gravitons of different scale, one obviously should not assume that any graviton of any scale is point-like, at least not in reality.

4.13.11 Gravitons as force/momentum carriers

Gravitons are also force carrier particles, where dimensionality (complexity) of such gravitons will depend on the complexity of force. In case of the, so called, *fundamental* forces, gravitons usually have simple shapes, which may be interpreted as ground shapes of spherical harmonics. Forces are present on different scales and act on different bodies. In any case, intensity of force coupling (strength of force acting on a particular body) is directly proportional to the intensity of gravitons coupling to the body. And this intensity will depend on distance but also on the shape of gravitons, which can be further correlated with mass/range of gravitons. Generally, intensity depends not only on the density but on the dimensionality of the gravitons as well. Consider, for example, a force carrier graviton in the form of a 2-dimensional sphere [surface]. The strength of this force will decrease inversely proportionally to r^2 , where r is the distance from the source. In case of 1-dimensional gravitons, in the form of rings, the force will decrease inversely proportionally to r . The same force can be carried by gravitons of different mass (range) and shape. Generally thus, the force decreases inversely proportionally to r^n , where n can be interpreted as denoting energy levels due to discrete ranges of gravitons (n may thus change with distance, but generally not continuously, rather at discrete points). Note that this can explain all cases of anomalous gravity (e.g., gravitons farther from a supermassive black hole have not only exchanged their energy for the energy of the supermassive black hole with universe's expansion, in the process they have reduced dimensionality). Gravitons can be more or less localized (they generally localize with coupling to bodies). The maxima of wavefunctions associated with gravitons represent maxima of potential of the associated force. This explains why electrons in the atoms, for example, generally can be found at these maxima. However, energy levels can be associated with any graviton of any scale, although these levels can be well confined and undetectable, especially on smaller scales.

Particles localized to the maxima of another graviton (e.g., electron coupled to a proton) generally do not lose energy in these states. There are multiple interpretations of this. A particle may be in the form of a standing wave. However, since this particle is also coupled with gravitons forming [private] space of the *parent* graviton, the particle is not losing energy because it is, in equilibrium, rotating with space. On smaller scales this rotation can, and will, at some scale exceed the speed of standard *light*. This allows for more intuitive interpretation of spin momenta of particles such as electrons. However, since speeds larger than the speed of light are confined to smaller scales, the electron itself cannot travel faster than light.

Additional problem is the stability of confinement. Photons, for example, generally travel as waves, with their radius expanding with emission. However, rest mass and rest radius of photons should be small enough

to allow them to start travelling at speeds much larger than c . In other words, speed of motion of energy is not limited solely by the amount of energy, but by radius (confinement) of that energy.

This, of course, implies that relativistic effects depend on scale as well (speed of information transfer is not absolutely invariant to scale, only relatively, as transitions are discrete).

4.13.12 Graviton collapse and time compression

The speed of time in graviton's well is inversely proportional to its mass and the proper units of time are proportional to its radius. This is why a collapse of a graviton (change in vertical energy level, decoupling from real mass) will cause time compression (acceleration of time). Since the force associated with the graviton (e.g., gravity) is never the only force acting on bodies, collapse of a graviton is also the transfer of power to forces acting against this force. Collapse can be temporary or permanent. In the context of large scale gravitons associated with stars, for example, a collapse of a graviton will effectively reduce the strength of gravitational coupling, causing the kinetic energy of atoms to overpower gravity, resulting in thermal expansion (note that this will disturb planetary orbits as well). Similarly, as it is shown in complementary work, periodic collapses of large scale gravitons are likely causing temporary acceleration in the expansion of the observable universe. Due to relativity in causality, however, acceleration of evolution will not be absolutely synchronized with the collapse and the pending collapse may be detectable through local precursors (e.g., temporary increase in decay rates of elements).

4.14 *Static* particle

Particles forming space (effective gravitons) of a graviton of scale U_n are particles of scale U_{n-2} . These are entangled with the *parent* graviton and any changes in its momentum will be reflected in momenta of these constituent particles. The particles are orbiting the graviton and the energy density is generally decreasing exponentially with distance from the graviton. Orbital speed is roughly equal to the speed limit in space for particles of U_{n-1} scale. However, the particles will get bound (coupled) to U_{n-1} scale matter captured by the gravitational well, exchanging orbital velocity for spin (U_{n-1} scale) momentum.

Due to their limited range and conversion of radial to angular momenta (where upon reaching the range they can form standing spherical waves) the space-constituent particles will hereby be referred to as *static* particles, generally, *static* gravitons, which may be generally decomposed into *static* graviton neutrinos - in case of neutral gravitational potential, and *static* photons or half-photons - in case of electro-magnetic potential.

These particles may be interpreted as *hot* dark matter when uncoupled, however, with coupling, their momenta will be transforming to *cold* Keplerian momenta.

4.14.1 Background fluctuation (Virtual fluctuation)

If *static* particles are directly undetectable they may be referred to as *virtual* particles. These particles have energy and this energy may be referred to as zero-point energy or background energy. If they inflate the particles can become *real* (detectable), or deflate back to virtuality. The process usually involves annihilation, and may be referred to as stemming from background fluctuation or quantum fluctuation, which is proportional to background temperature (which is proportional to local potential - e.g., gravitational). If particles remain real, one may be radiated away, while the other may get trapped deeper in the well of potential. This, for example, may frequently happen in the strong gravitational wells of black holes, where the radiation of standard scale can be correlated with Hawking radiation (although the two phenomena are not the same - correlation is indirect, a secondary interaction). At the point of emission, the two particles are entangled and may be described by a wavefunction where one particle has positive mass (energy) and the other negative. It should be understood, however, that this negativity is relative. The mass is still greater than absolute 0 but it is equal to, or lower than, the inflated *zero-point* mass or *event horizon* mass (here representing a superposition of the positive and negative mass, e.g., in the form of average). In case of symmetric annihilation, both particles have the same amount of mass, the difference being in the type (matter/anti-matter, per Dirac interpretation of positive/negative energy). As absolute symmetry requires absolutely flat space, the annihilation cannot be absolutely symmetric. Therefore, a difference will always exist between matter mass and corresponding anti-matter mass. In case of annihilation in extremely strong wells (e.g., near a black hole), asymmetry can be extreme (where one particle may even become more virtual instead of becoming [more] real). In any case, the radiation can be interpreted as evaporation of the well. This decrease in gravitational potential should be synchronized with the decrease of mass (energy) associated with the local space curvature (if such entanglement exists). If this is a graviton of larger scale, this may not be well synchronized - the graviton may collapse to a lower energy level in a discrete step, once the sufficient amount of small scale well energy has radiated away (or, more precisely, once the sufficient amount of *negative* mass has accumulated). As noted before, causality here can be very relative (even probabilistic), so the collapse can precede small scale radiation as well.

Different interpretations of negative mass exist, and different interpretations may exist in nature. It should be clear, however, that truly (absolutely) negative energy or negative mass, just like negative density

or negative temperature, does not make physical sense. It does not exist in reality. The confusion arises due to absolutist reductionism (where description of reality is reduced to mathematical abstraction and then interpreted as real) and consequential lack of the proper interpretation of the reference point where the zero-point is interpreted as absolute rather than a relative zero.

In case of Hawking radiation in GR/QM context, for example, entanglement exists between the black hole mass and the quantum fluctuations of local space. Due to this entanglement, the flattening of space (coupled with the radiation of particles) must be coupled with the decrease of black hole mass (where the black hole mass and the fluctuation can be some distance apart). To describe this mathematically, the concept of negative mass is involved, where this negative mass is understood as the mass lost by the black hole. One could now accept the notion of absolutely negative mass and argue that the black hole mass decreases due to absorption of negative mass. And sure, one can indeed believe in that, but this is like believing that one can subtract 4 apples from 2 apples. It can be done mathematically sure - a more or less skilled mathematician (magician) can always make a non-existing apple appear and disappear, but a more or less skilled physicist should know that's an illusion. Thus, one can argue whether the entanglement here is relatively local or non-local, but the black hole mass cannot magically get erased from reality. In other words, one can accept the notion of absolutely negative mass and its *hairless* absorption due to mathematical elegance, but one should bear in mind that, in reality, there is a *hidden* mechanism behind it. In fact, one should question whether the black hole itself is an illusion and all there is is curved space (which can be interpreted as naked large scale excitation, or large scale fluctuation of a large scale gravitational field - a large scale *virtual* graviton, which is interpreted as real from smaller scales, such as ours).

However, it should be understood that it is not absolutely impossible, for example, to subtract 4 apples from 2 apples in reality, it is the specific interpretation that imposes absolute limits, not the physical reality. If one interprets subtraction as removal of mass (reduction of local energy density to some background value) - regardless of its entropy, then it is possible to subtract 4 apples from 2 apples, as background energy density (e.g., zero-point or vacuum energy density) is never absolute zero, it can be always further decreased (theoretically at least, in practice it can be hard or even impossible for inherently, even if relatively, limited observers). The locally removed energy can even be, theoretically at least, ordered/transformed into 2 apples, and as the local energy density restores to equilibrium (background density) - draining energy from the surroundings or even some smaller scale, a *magician* could claim he just subtracted 4 apples from 2 apples.

4.15 Virtual particle

A virtual particle in CR is not a purely abstract concept, it is assumed to exist in reality and possess real energy. Its virtuality implies simply that it is undetectable, which is observer relative. This is different from the conventional interpretations of virtual particles, but even in these there are ambiguities. To clear things up, consider the example of two interacting electrons in vacuum. Here are the facts that no one disagrees with:

- a physical (real) exchange of energy/momentum exists between the two electrons,
- the exchange occurs at the speed of *light* (c), at least roughly,
- this energy exchange is directly undetectable (it is the effects on electrons that can be measured).

Now, since the exchange is undetectable, mathematical description of the process does not have to involve the exchange of real particles. And this is the case in QED, for example, where the process involves the exchange of virtual particles, also called force carrier particles. It should be clear, however, that these virtual particles are purely mathematical concepts (intermediates) and, while useful, do NOT represent the real exchanged energy (so they are not real force carriers either). Since the exchange is undetectable, a complete (or excessive) reductionist will also claim that nothing is travelling between the electrons at the speed of light - the change in energy/momentum of one electron is simply mirrored in the other electron within the time $\sim r/c$, where r is the distance between the electrons and c is the speed of light. To a realist (like myself), this notion is absurd for at least a couple of reasons:

- if there is absolutely nothing real travelling between the electrons, why does the exchange occur at finite speed, why exactly at the speed of light and why does it depend on distance?,
- we know that information carriers on detectable scales - such as electrons or real photons, propagate as real energy, and real photons travel [at least roughly] at the speed c .

It seems illogical to assume that there is no real wave carrying energy from one electron to the other. Thus, in CR, the real force carrier is the energy travelling at the speed of light from one electron to the other. It is a real force carrier but can be interpreted as a virtual particle in reference frames from which it is undetectable. Since it is undetectable, one can even consider it non-existent (e.g., in order to preserve mathematical elegance), but this non-existence must be understood as relative. To assume it is absolute, is unscientific - from the perspective of a realist at least.

4.16 Rest (uniform motion, uniform ageing)

A body (e.g., graviton) is at rest relative to local space if the coupling of constituent particles of space with the body is in the equilibrium state. This equilibrium is accomplished when the amount of coupled particles (strength or intensity of coupling) does not change over time ($d/dt = 0$). There are two ways to achieve equilibrium - the absence of motion and uniform motion. The two states are equivalent in a sense that motion through time is uniform in both. But there is a difference in the strength (intensity) of coupling, which is proportional to the amount of motion through space. This then implies a difference in the speed through time (rate of ageing). Stronger coupling (note that this is usually gravitational coupling) implies slower passage through time.

Wherever motion relative to local space exists, relativistic effects on the body will be, at least in part, real. The degree, or the amount, of reality (physicality) in a relativistic effect will be proportional to the amount of physical motion through local space.

Note that this makes the time dilation in SR (due to motion) equivalent to time dilation in GR (due to increased gravitational potential) - wherever the effect is real and the coupling is gravitational. The equivalence is not absolute, however, as coupling constants can differ.

Note also that, generally, relativistic effects can be explained as a consequence of conservation of relativity (relativistic uncertainty), where the local universe is *reacting* to the contraction of intervals in space with the extension of lengths in time.

To change the rate of ageing work must be done, energy must be transformed. Obviously, this is done through [real] acceleration, when the intensity of coupling is changing - growing proportionally to acceleration.

4.16.1 Reality and illusion of rest

The intensity of coupling (and, thus, the rate of ageing), for different reasons, can change [to a degree] even if the body is apparently at rest. This is particularly evident in living bodies, in which the rate of ageing measurably varies over the lifetime even when uncorrelated with changes in mass. Note also, however, that the coupling with complex bodies is more complex itself and variability can be limited to certain scales of coupling. Most complex coupling is lost at the time of death of a complex body, however, the effect on body weight may be negligible. The effect certainly is small in case of living bodies on Earth, but this is unlikely the case generally. The effect is inversely proportional to complexity, proportional to the number and magnitude of scales on which death (decoupling) occurs (e.g., a death of a human body is also a certain death of its organs, and will be followed by death of organelles and cells after certain

time, but it's not the death of all the smaller components, such as microbes, molecules and atoms), and the intensity of the coupling(s) during life.

Note that it is not hard to relatively quantify the complexity/intensity of coupling between different bodies at rest. If two bodies of the same mass age differently, the coupling is stronger and/or more complex in case of slower ageing. The intensity/complexity of coupling is probably highly correlated with the intensity/complexity of consciousness. In more massive brains, for example, the amount of consciousness is probably generally higher than in less massive brains (although one must here distinguish between extroverted and introverted consciousness - depending on sensitivity to the external and internal reality), but not necessarily the complexity of consciousness - which may further be correlated with intelligence. Neither consciousness nor intelligence require brains, the purpose of compressed neural networks is probably the focus/localization of intelligence/consciousness in space/time. Consider plants/fungi for example, in these systems both, intelligence and consciousness, are spread over space and time. Correlated with the intensity/complexity of coupling (rate of ageing) is the resolution of experience. Here, plants/fungi are more conscious of long-term effects than of short-term disturbances. A reaction of a plant to occasional disturbance (cutting of a branch for example) may be interpreted as subconscious or even fully reflexive (unconscious), but a frequent disturbance may be resolved (experienced) on a higher level of consciousness and may induce a more complex response (which may be evident in its progeny, if not in the plant itself). This complex response may be interpreted as emergent phenomena, but all emergent phenomena are, as noted before, probably correlated with distinct coupling. However, as rest can be illusionary, so can emergence. Emergence is, however, usually real in living bodies.

4.17 Graviton tube (wormhole, quantum of entanglement)

Graviton tube is a physical manifestation of entanglement (correlation), space connecting two entangled gravitons. In one interpretation, the volume of that space (volumetric distance) is proportional to the distance in correlation (inverse of strength of entanglement), however, the tube is relatively hollow and energy is mostly concentrated on the membrane.

With no additional energy or disturbance of gravitons, volumetric distance will remain the same regardless of spatial separation. The tube can be considered as subspace or an relatively isolated dimension of space.

The tube may be considered as elementary quantum of continuous space, however, in reality it is a sum of constituent smaller tubes. The tube(s) may also be generally curved (entangled particles may not be connected by the shortest path possible in flat geometry). Consider magnetic field *lines* connecting opposite poles - if these are tubes of entanglement, they obviously do not follow shortest paths and

may be compressed and expanded.
 Of course, these may be shortest paths possible considering conditions on field formation and one can model entanglement of poles with geometry where these paths are shortest.

4.18 Gluon

Gluon is a localized superposition of one or more pairs of gravitons.

4.19 Gluon tube

Gluon tube is space connecting two entangled gluons. It is a local superposition of graviton tubes, or non-local superposition of gluons.

Figure 3: Gluon tube

Fig. 3 shows the gluon tube, with induced cross-sectional capacitance due to spatial separation of gravitons G_1 and G_2 .

4.20 Gravitational maximum (g-maximum, [relative] event horizon)

Gravitational maximum is the n -dimensional region of a maximum of the gravitational potential in a gravitational well. This area may have different shapes, depending on the [limitations of] the observer, energy levels of gravitons and relativistic energies involved. In most practical cases this will be approximated as a ring, tube, spherical surface or even a point. Note that a single gravitational well may have multiple gravitational maxima at different radii (although one can argue that this is then not a single gravitational well, rather a superposition of gravitational wells - which can be considered as a proper interpretation).

Generally, gravitational maximum may be used as a synonym for a real graviton or a superposition of real gravitons. However, interpretation will depend on the context, as gravitational maxima can be decoupled from real gravitons, even if induction of maxima may generally be *stimulated* or correlated with inflation/deflation or oscillation of real gravitons. In example, inflation of a graviton from one scale to another will generally be correlated with relaxation of a maximum on the former scale and compression of field potential on the new scale. Speed of information transfer is finite (even if different between scales) so neither the relaxation nor compression can be absolutely instantaneous, especially if additional real mass is concentrated at the maxima. Maxima can thus exist independently of real gravitons, although these may be generally relatively short-lived unless periodically coupled with real gravitons.

Multiple gravitons may exist in a relatively localized superposition, where they spin about the same central region but with different (spatially separated) mass radii. This is then also a relative superposition of gravitational wells, each having its own maximum. In these cases, in some contexts, gravitational maximum may represent a graviton with maximal mass (energy) of all the gravitons.

In some reference frames (contexts), separation between gravitons may be negligible and gravitational maximum will then represent a less relative superposition of gravitons and their masses.

Note also that quantization is relative and for every graviton a reference frame exists in which that graviton is, not only a gravitational maximum, but relative superposition of gravitons of smaller scale.

Energy of a gravitational maximum is proportional to the capacity (gravitational imprint) of the associated gravitational well for coupling with matter.

Note that capacity is scale relative. The capacity of an U_n graviton for coupling with U_{n-1} mass may be full, but the capacity of U_{n-1} wells for U_{n-2} mass may be not.

However, note that constituent quanta of space of an U_n graviton are U_{n-2} particles, exactly the mass scale the space-constituent particles of U_{n-1} wells should couple with. Thus, the capacitances of different scale here are correlated (the coupling correlation is manifested as attractive force) and what is considered as a component of space in one reference frame may be interpreted as acquired matter in another.

The question is what happens to wells at full capacity and can they be over-capacitated? This is related to the problem of dark matter and changes in energy levels, and is discussed later.

4.20.1 Biological physics

The acquisition of matter by an naked particle (soul) can be interpreted as an act towards symbiosis of smaller scale and larger scale mass. The gravitational well of the maximum provides the environment and acts as a catalyst for evolution of matter (enabling fusion, chemical reactions, etc.) while the interaction also enables the soul to co-evolve with acquired matter (constituent particles of the soul are correlated with, and will mirror, acquired matter to some degree). Since the difference in scale of space is also a difference in the scale of units of time, this can be interpreted as a relative coupling of past and future (how relative will depend on the case), leading to a relatively progressive evolution in one and a relatively regressive evolution in the other.

4.21 Gravitational well (spiritual well)

A real graviton will induce effective gravitons (which are also *static* gravitons in equilibrium), forming a pressure/density gradient (or curvature) of space - a gravitational well.

Density of energy is inversely proportional to distance, therefore, at full capacity the gradient of density will be proportional to the gradient of orbital angular velocities of coupled bodies. These are then Keplerian velocities.

When matter (real mass) is coupled with [the effective gravitons of] space and orbits at Keplerian velocity, it is at rest relative to that space and it shouldn't lose significant energy during orbit.

Fig. 4 shows a cross-section of a gravitational well with a [gravitational] maximum at radius r . Density of graviton energy (dark matter) is represented by the concentration of circles, it is greatest at event horizon r .

Graviton orbitals will generally have some finite eccentricity, which may be more exaggerated with coupling.

Note that for a hollow sphere of standard matter, gravity is cancelled at any point inside the sphere (*Shell theorem*). This is generally not the case for gravity inside a hollow sphere of a naked graviton for a couple of reasons:

- graviton is rotating and gravitational potential cannot be absolutely the same everywhere on the sphere,
- polarization of the sphere is always greater than absolute 0 and the sphere will have openings (or lower concentration of energy) on poles,
- the sphere can be deformed by external energy or relativistic energy.

Additionally, the spherical form of a naked graviton is only relatively hollow (it is devoid only of standard matter, but it is not devoid of smaller

Figure 4: Gravitational well scheme

scale particles - forming space) - space is generally not flat below radius r , it is filled with effective gravitons relatively mirroring the gradient outside of the sphere. Generally, at least one another real graviton of the same scale (order of magnitude) exists within the outer one, which may be interpreted as the core graviton.

4.21.1 Induction of effective gravitons

One possible mechanism of induction (*creation*) of effective gravitons is inflation of real gravitons of smaller scale. The quanta of smaller scale are annihilated at the gravitational maximum, or relative event horizon (r on Fig. 4), resulting in inflation of two effective gravitons with opposite momenta, perpendicular to the event horizon orbital. Such inflation should generally be proportional to the relativistic energy of the real graviton, where the rate of inflation is proportional to the energy differential. At [relative] rest, there might not be sufficient energy for inflation and recycling of existing effective gravitons will dominate. Here, existing energy will be used to prevent inverse annihilation (deflation) of effective gravitons.

The mechanisms used to prevent annihilation may be interpreted as mechanisms of creation, or maintenance, of asymmetry (or distance in correlation) between inflated products.

This can be the asymmetric exchange between gravitational and electromagnetic potential of particles, even between them. Another possibility is that particles are allowed to annihilate, however, this results in disequilibrium (*recoil*), and the particles are inflated back for another cycle. Both solutions are possible, one may dominate during maintenance in equilibrium (relative rest), the other, during changes in energy of the real graviton itself (e.g., at the time of its own inflation).

The asymmetry of potential (carried by effective gravitons) allows for interesting solutions where different forces could dominate inside and outside of the relative event horizon. Of course, there will be *leakage* because the carrier particles themselves have their own wells of potential carried by effective gravitons of even smaller scale (containment of potential has to be relative).

Note also, that a real graviton can contain other real gravitons of the same vertical scale but at different horizontal energy levels and thus at different radii. This allows for greater asymmetry and more complex mechanisms for its creation and maintenance. Absorption of real mass can provide stability in the gravitational well but this additional energy also adds more complexity.

4.22 Black hole

Black hole is a region of space with escape velocity at the gravitational maximum greater than the speed of *light* (information/energy speed limit). For a standard black hole this is the standard speed of light.

Note that, in CR, this region does not have a singularity at the centre, it has a ring, or torus, of relative singularity at the gravitational maximum. Therefore, some material that wouldn't be able to escape at the equator could escape at the poles.

The more charged the graviton is, the more two-dimensional it will be and the density of the gravitational field will be decreasing from the equator to the pole. Thus, the gravitational escape velocity (without taking rotation into account) can be significantly lower at the poles.

Note that, otherwise, the particles forming the [internally generated] magnetic field *lines* cannot be standard photons or of standard photon rest scale, but of even smaller scale, as they would have to be faster than standard light, unless the *lines* are not closed, or are expelled from the interior.

However, generally, just as an U_{-1} graviton slows down from c with momentum transformation synchronized with coupling, a particle faster than c can similarly be slowed down and transformed to a standard photon.

This restricts the feeding potential of black holes, as, instead of being trapped, some matter may simply be accelerated towards the centre only to be ejected through the poles at extreme velocities. In an extremely polarized case, such black hole does not acquire additional energy and is simply the most efficient transformer of energy (life-form) - transforming composite energy into individual charged particles so these can be digested elsewhere (e.g., in young stars, where they concentrate to form hydrogen fuel).

However, in case of neutral black holes, most matter will have a momentum parallel to the equator forming a disc of orbiting material.

The shape of the graviton explains not only the formation of jets in black holes but also why some black holes don't have them (such black holes should have a more neutral, 3-dimensional form).

The jets are not accelerated by gravity alone, the more energy there is in plasma (accretion disk) the more powerful will be the magnetic field which will focus incoming charged particles making the jets more energetic. This correlation has been observed[19].

Note that magnetic field *lines* are, at some scale, also *jets* of entangled particles. It is then obvious that extremely neutral bodies will have extremely weak magnetic fields, while extremely polarized will not only have extremely strong magnetic fields but will also be emitting jets of particles of larger scale (like protons and electrons, in case of black holes).

If black holes have evolved before stars the farthest and biggest black holes may be more polarized. However, polarization should also be cyclic at some timescale.

Since particles of the adjacent discrete vertical energy levels [to the U_1 level] are charged (dominant energy in standard particles, for example, is electromagnetic), real gravitons of stars and planets most likely start their evolution (synchronized with coupling to standard matter) more polarized, even though most polarization may be lost already during graviton birth on that scale (inflation from smaller scale or deflation from larger scale).

Discs of material about stars and planets are thus probably formed due to the charge of the host at the time of formation or at times of energy level changes - greater charge will create thinner discs. This also implies that oldest orbiting formations will orbit in a plane aligned with the plane of primordial equator of

the host (unless the orbits have been disturbed later, however, probability for significant disturbance should be low after birth). Settling in equilibrium state is likely to be oscillatory and this is in the Solar System confirmed with the *sinusoidal* distribution of inclinations of planets.

Note that information on formation should be preserved in inclinations - in case the system inflated from smaller scale, nearer orbits should generally be more aligned with the equatorial plane.

This is apparently the case with the Solar System, as shown in Table 1. In case of systems deflated from larger scale, it is the farther orbits that should be more aligned. However, if vertical energy levels are discrete (as hypothesized),

Body	Inclination (ecliptic) [°]	Inclination (Sun's equator) [°]	Inclination (invariable plane) [°]
Mercury	7.01	3.38	6.34
Venus	3.39	3.86	2.19
Earth	0	7.25	1.57
Mars	1.85	5.65	1.67
Vesta	7.14	3.48	7.13
Ceres	10.59	3.40	9.20
Pallas	34.93	36.45	34.21
Hygiea	3.83	10.79	-
Jupiter	1.31	6.09	0.32
Saturn	2.49	5.50	0.93
Uranus	0.77	6.48	1.02
Neptune	1.77	6.43	0.72
Pluto	17.14	11.86	15.55

Table 1: Osculating orbital inclinations in the Solar System

it is possible (or even likely) that the initial energy of inflation was larger than required for the jump and the system was, after initial inflation, somewhat deflated to a stable state.

Indeed, if outer planets are bigger (and older) and the Solar System was inflating as a system of particles (e.g., an atom) - which is a most likely scenario, the energy distribution suggests effective initial inflation of the core to current Mars' orbit or beyond, then deflation to current Sun' radius. In that case, the invariable plane (which is roughly aligned with Jupiter) might represent the fossil of the original core equatorial plane.

The higher inclinations of dwarf planets (marked green in Table 1) might indicate that these are youngest and were formed after system stabilization, however, more likely, as decreasing inclination (relative to the invariable plane) of dwarf planets in the main asteroid belt (and increasing alignment with the current equatorial plane) towards the core suggests, these were inflated from smaller and neutral gravitons.

I hypothesize that outer planets (gas giants) were inflated from polarized gravitons of electrons (some, or all, of which have ended up in an excited state or different generation - tau and muon mass eigenstates, possibly multiple states in superposition), dwarf planets were inflated from neutrinos, while inner planets were inflated from positively charged particles (parts of atomic nuclei). The anti-alignment of spin magnetic momenta between inner and outer planets goes in favour of this hypothesis (which is further analysed in a complementary

paper[20]).

Note that a black hole is only a relatively special form of a gravitational well. Particles faster than light must exist (even if one may not be able to detect them) and every gravitational well has a relative event horizon - digesting energy of one scale and ejecting smaller scale ions which then combine to feed *moons*. The only difference is scale.

The self-similarity is not limited to celestial bodies - every metabolism is ultimately ionic.

Note also that the trajectory of ejected charges is bent by the magnetic field *lines* (tubes) and these can be considered as a form of intestines.

In CR, there can be no absolute singularities, only relative ones. If a black hole is a result of graviton inflation or deflation, its gravitational maximum has a real radius and, if any gravitational collapse of standard matter would result in a black hole the collapse would end at that maximum - a ring-like (or toroidal) relative singularity. The collapse of the body of matter is, however, likely relatively synchronized with a change in energy level of the graviton (and exchange between gravitational and electro-magnetic potential).

The graviton may collapse to smaller scale but never to a radius of absolute 0 as this would require absolutely infinite mass or angular velocity (due to conservation of momentum). Infinite momenta (energies) are never involved in such collapses.

Furthermore, collapse to a smaller radius is generally coupled with the increase in angular velocity and decrease of the rest mass of a graviton. This will generally be reflected in acquired mass. Conservation of momentum is thus effectively replacing gravitational attraction with centrifugal repulsion at some scale.

Therefore, although acquired mass can be compacted to extremely dense forms of energy, this energy won't occupy 0 volume and will be radiated away (at whatever scale possible) until it matches the graviton scale. However, with collapse of scale, graviton might exchange spin momentum for orbital angular momentum and decouple from acquired matter. In that case, the particles of compacted matter may be considered dead as a collective and will tend to decompose, decay and spread. Nature evolved diverse mechanisms for such decay - in some reference frames it may be observed as rapid and abiotic, in other organic and slow.

In general, distinct conscious life (by my hypotheses) of any system (collective) starts and ends with a change in discrete energy level of a graviton (or gravitons in superposition) at times of:

- conception (coupling), synchronized with graviton inflation or deflation, and
- death (decoupling), inversion of momentum with inflation or deflation (breaking entanglement with coupled matter).

Obviously, what is interpreted as conception and what as death is scale relative. For the graviton (soul), the end of life on one scale is the beginning of life on another scale (switch of context). From some reference frames, one scale may be short-lived and graviton may be observed reincarnating on a single scale - popping in and out of existence between different spaces.

4.23 General force, strong force and strong entanglement

Since space cannot be absolute or absolutely abstract, it has properties and energy which can be transformed.

Various combinations of spin momenta, subspaces (dimensions) of various scales (various masses of force carrying particles), enable evolution of forces of various nature.

Complexity of these forces will be proportional to the number of possible polarized states, or degrees of freedom in polarization.

Even gravity, with intrinsic rotation taken into account, can be interpreted as a polarized force.

A neutral force may generally be interpreted as a force of unipolar radial effect (e.g., non-discriminating attraction). However, every neutral particle or force has polarized components which are generally correlated with polarized angular momenta.

With changing complexity, one force may evolve from the other. Complexity can be increased by strengthening entanglement (localization in some dimension of space) of two or more sources of polarized force. Strong localization can be interpreted as superposition in some scales and, if this is a superposition of mass (e.g., gravitational), bigger mass of force carrier particles will reduce the range of force.

One strongly localized force is the force holding the particles of the atom nucleus together (it is even called *strong force* in QM). But should it be interpreted as a special or fundamental kind of force?

If gravitational sources are generally not limited to one force carrying particle (graviton of a single scale or rest mass) such force may be interpreted as localized gravity.

Of course, when it is expressing more complex polarization, it is not just localized but it has evolved *beyond* the neutral or *unipolar* gravity.

Note that polarization too is relative. It may even be induced by *polarized* observers. Note also that, per CR postulates, all couplings are *running* (scale dependent). Coupling of the weak force represents an evolved gravitational coupling as well. It should be clear now why the term "graviton" is a very appropriate term for the generalized particle. Gravitational force is the simplest force there is, everything else is more complex and can evolve from unipolar gravity. Even the effective absence of force can be more complex - when it involves cancellation of effects of multiple sources of force.

If one is to unify all possible forces and represent them by a single equation, that equation cannot contain any absolute constants. It must be as variable (or evolvable) as possible.

Pragmatically, however, it will generally be more usable not to generalize as much, as variability and evolution of reality localized in an dimension of space (including time) is inevitably limited.

Therefore, instead of using this equation for the general force (that includes all possible interpretations on all possible scales):

$$F = *$$

more convenient and usable expression would be the one of a relatively general force that discards forces of negligible influence on the context.

In typical local contexts a relatively general force may include electro-magnetic and gravitational terms.

Such form is also useful in the context of transformation of energy (inflation/deflation) between discrete vertical energy levels, as all terms are hypothesized to be entangled and one potential may be exchanged for the other, e.g., electro-magnetic force might regress to gravitational force with inflation of energy, but also *vice versa*, depending on the scales in question.

This is exactly what I hypothesize had happened with the inflation of energy in the observable universe.

4.23.1 Strong entanglement, interaction probabilities, photon nature

Strong correlation of particles localized in a particular dimension may be hard to disturb for an observer. Due to limited resolving power, observational energy may strengthen correlation and inflate additional pairs of entangled particles.

This is the case for particles forming atomic nuclei, held together by strong force (strong entanglement), and one reason why proton may be considered an elementary particle in most contexts.

However, assuming that the binding of an electron to proton, due to increasing correlation of charges, localizes proton charge into a positron, in that context, the structure of a proton becomes more complex.

Since an accelerated change in distance between charges will result in emission of photons, the photon may be interpreted as a product of the change in [the strength of] entanglement between charges, carrying the information on this change. Photons are, however, also emitted with acceleration of an isolated charge in free space, in which case the entanglement with other charges may not be apparent. Generally, thus, photon should be correlated with the [changes in] entanglement of a charge with the electro-magnetic field. This field generally contains both positive and negative potentials. And in CR, this field, or electro-magnetic space, is composed of U_{-1} particles (which may be referred to as *virtual*, as they seem to be directly undetectable from our perspective). One possibility is that a photon is a composite particle of an even number of the space-forming (U_{-1}) fermions, however, that is unlikely. Most likely, photon's rest mass is a product of annihilation of positive and negative U_{-1} fermions (which does not imply that photon is absolutely elementary, rather the composite particles are of an even smaller scale - U_{-2} , with their rest masses being negligible compared to binding energy). Thus, even though photon production does not always involve annihilation of standard (U_0) particles, any kind of photon production probably does involve annihilation of U_{-1} particles, as photon emission does imply changes in local potential.

Absorption of the photon will then cause recreation of U_{-1} (space-forming) pair(s) through [inverse] annihilation (inflation) of constituents.

Considering the apparently oscillating force dominance between vertical energy levels, the dominant force on the U_{-1} scale should be neutral (gravitational-like), while the dominant force on U_{-2} scale should be electro-magnetic. We detect photons on standard (U_0) scale and they are overall neutral, however space associated with U_0 particles is of scale U_{-2} , where electro-magnetism dominates, and this is the scale on which photon interacts with charged particles.

In case of interactions between equally scaled particles, spin momenta and nature of species have major roles. Spin anti-alignment generally results in attraction due to the anti-alignment of the oscillation of angular waveforms. Radial attraction occurs with the anti-alignment of the oscillation of radial waveforms.

Event though the space may seem continuous, it is obviously only relatively continuous. Each of the space-forming gravitons may be associated with an horizontal energy level so the density of energy levels is equivalent to the density of space, but that density is relative to scale. It is usually considered that electrons occupy discrete energy levels in an atom, but it is more appropriate to say that, in a waveform, their energy is only mostly concentrated at the maxima of potential (or entanglement)

and they are most likely to be localized at these maxima. Space-forming gravitons still exist between these maxima, and even though these orbitals are relatively forbidden for electrons, they can be occupied by other particles.

How can two electrons overcome the radial repulsion and couple together? This is possible when one electron is significantly more localized than the other, scale difference will subdue repulsion and, once they are both in the same state (localized or delocalized) and aligned, spin anti-alignment will enable stability.

Particles generally oscillate between localized and delocalized states. Nuclear fusion of two protons, for example, will require high energy when the two are synchronized in this cycling. Ensuring proper time dilation between the two can significantly increase the fusion probability.

Generally, a non-localized photon is usually, like a gravitational wave, a more or less spherical expanding wave (with exact energy distribution depending on conditions during emission and photon dimensionality), with greatest probability for absorption in the direction aligned with the spin momentum axis (although the direction of that axis can change during travel, e.g., in non-flat gravitational space). Implications on evolution Regardless of the physical manifestation of photon propagation, it obviously carries information on the source, including original location in flat space (which may be locally manifested as a recoil in specific direction at the time of absorption). It is a relative clone of the energy that caused emission.

As carriers of force, photons, or gravitons in general, can be interpreted as carriers of changes in specific entanglement between entangled entities (emitter and absorber). The entanglement channel (or dimension) is present as long as the exchange of gravitons exists, or, in other words, as long as the entanglement is changing. But the entanglement is always changing at some scale, and from some reference frames, channels may be interpreted as permanent. Since this horizontal information transfer can proceed faster than standard light on smaller scales, relative *precognition* becomes theoretically possible, assuming changes in the energy on smaller scale precede changes on the larger scale (which generally is the case, although they may also follow the changes of larger scale). With a change in vertical energy level of the carrier, the absorbed energy of the smaller scale may even be interpreted as absorbed energy of larger scale.

Consider a gluon tube connecting two gluons (where each gluon is, per the definition here, a local superposition of gravitons of different scale). This gluon tube thus consists of two graviton tubes of different scale. If the difference in scale is vertically high (i.e., a difference in multiple orders of magnitude), information transfer through the tube of smaller

scale will be significantly faster than the transfer through the larger tube. Now assume that, due to local entanglement, the graviton of larger scale is affected by the received information as well. If the local information exchange between the entangled gravitons is faster than the transfer of information through the tube of larger scale (reasonable assumption), the local graviton of larger scale could receive the information that can be interpreted as a change in the distant large graviton before the actual information on the change arrives through the larger graviton tube.

In another example, consider a vertical entanglement between scales (universes), where the only significant difference between them is the difference in scale and thus difference in the speed of time. Evolution of energy will then be equal between the two, but one (usually the smaller scale) will be more evolved than the other. Information transfer from the smaller scale to the larger scale enables prediction of local future. Note, however, that this is a probabilistic prediction, for a couple of reasons. 1st, there is no absolute equality and, 2nd, since the system can only be relatively isolated, the probability for deviation of local future from the prediction is non-zero. Note also that increasing distance in evolution between the two is decreasing alignment, or aligned entanglement, in time, which can affect the entanglement in the dimension used for information transfer. Thus, in order for this to be long-term sustainable, some kind of occasional or periodic synchronization will have to occur. Assuming information transfer is possible due to localization (relative superposition) of the two scales in space, synchronization is possible with the exchange of scale (inflation of the smaller scale, deflation of the larger scale). Thus, any effective precognition will have a finite range, and this range will be increasing with time from the moment of last synchronization (when it is reset to zero). This is particularly interesting in the context of entanglement between planetary systems and the unstable standard isotopes, which is explored in complementary work. But it can also be very interesting in other contexts.

For example, considering there is no visual stimulation of standard scale during sleep, dreams could represent information transferred from a different scale and locally interpreted as absorbed photons, at least in some cases. One should thus not exclude the possibility of existence of prophets, although, reliable ones may be extremely rare.

Channels of entanglement carry energy and can, therefore, affect other energy of a particular scale. These channels or filaments (note the dark matter correlation), which can be of different complexity (depending on the complexity of information they carry), can guide this energy into particular configuration. With inherent limitation of observers, the guidance channels may be unobservable, and the behaviour of energy can be interpreted as a result of spontaneous change in energy levels, random fluctuation, self-organization or free will.

Consider self-organization of cells during embryonic development. This is not DNA coded. DNA only carries recipes for the components (proteins) and may carry epigenetic markers for regulatory genes which when triggered can result in cascades of gene expression but this cannot fully explain the self-organization of cells into tissues or emergent phenomena. However, assume that the organization into tissue has already occurred on the entangled smaller scale, information received on the larger scale can guide the cells into such organization (e.g., on some subconscious level). Obviously, it is not required for the event to occur on the smaller scale, what is required is information that it has occurred. In any case, spontaneous self-organization can only be relatively spontaneous and information can evolve. In case of weak information (intensity of entanglement) any self-organization can be interpreted to be highly spontaneous and will have a low probability of happening, whereas in case of strong guidance, self-organization may be interpreted as strongly coded. Former may then be interpreted as evolution, latter as coded development. However, probability of self-organization in the former can be increased with multiple instances of the potential precursor self-organizations. Consider atoms for example. A large number of collections of atoms will surely evolve molecules eventually if the environment is suitable for the existence of molecules. Similarly, if the environment allows, these will evolve into more complex forms, e.g., amino-acids, these into proteins, etc. But once some form evolves, the information could be conserved and reused to make the evolution of a nearby precursor less spontaneous. Evolution is thus relative development, and development is relative evolution.

4.24 Weak entanglement

Graviton tubes are always physical at some scale, however, with increasing distance and no additional energy applied to the tube, entanglement generally weakens.

Note, however, that weak entanglement in one dimension (e.g., space) does not imply weak entanglement in the other (e.g., time).

However, as long as there is no change in entangled energy the entanglement will not get broken (and when it does, it never is broken absolutely), even if the particles are separated over great distance.

Due to the fact that energy remains constant, either volume and energy density of the tube (dimension) connecting the particles remain constant or energy density is decreased proportionally to volume increase. Assuming information is

transferred along the tube membrane, the former will be, with decreasing tube radius (and mass per quantum of space [cross-section]), increasing speed of information transfer. In that interpretation, speed of transfer can exceed speed of light. In the second interpretation, space is stretched and local observer (within the tube) would measure no change in speed, while a remote observer could measure superluminal transfer - assuming tube (subspace) is resolvable by that observer.

In CR, both interpretations are valid (possible). One can only argue what and when any information is transmitted. Information that is *observable* could be limited to information transmitted with the collapse (deflation) of entanglement, which will, in both interpretations, decrease energy in the tube.

Since weak entanglement is relatively unaffected by change in spatial distance alone, the first interpretation (volume invariant to spatial distance) is convenient as it implies proportionality of volume (or volumetric distance) with distance in correlation (inverse of [scale of] entangled energy or strength of entanglement). Note that the observer who cannot resolve (observe) the tube of entanglement cannot use the tube for information transfer or control information transmitted on collapse[21] (superluminal or not). In that case, weak entanglement reduces to standard non-local QM entanglement (note that, per CR postulates, QM entanglement cannot be absolutely non-local, implying existence of reference frames with interpretations stated above).

$$\Delta E_1 = \Delta E_2 = \Delta E = \text{const.}$$

What is the initial speed of information transfer?

Speed of information transfer always depends on distance in some dimension. If distance in time is distance in evolution, distance in time between two equally evolved or relatively identical particles (e.g., two entangled photons) will be a relative 0, so the speed of information transfer with the collapse of entanglement in time will be a relative infinity, relatively invariant to spatial distance.

For a sufficiently limited observer, these relative values (e.g., zero, infinity and invariance), may be effectively equal to being absolute. However, any observer that assumes this is an inherent limitation of reality, rather than its own, will, by that, limit its own understanding of reality as well.

4.24.1 Layers of entanglement, background entanglement

Since entanglement in space/time is never broken absolutely, entanglement is layered and certain hierarchy in dominance can exist. One may thus introduce a concept of "background entanglement". Consider a simple case of gravitational

Figure 5: Weak entanglement

and electro-magnetic entanglement, where the two are coupled through the uncertainty principle. One component may explode at the expense of the other, but the other is never lost absolutely. If dominance oscillates between the two, one of these can be considered the background [level of] entanglement.

4.25 Electric polarization and charge/mass exchange

In the standard model of physics particles have fixed (intrinsic and unchangeable) properties (e.g., electric charge, rest mass, spin) which then produces a zoo of different particles. While that approach is useful, different particles evolve from other particles and it might not always be the most convenient approach, especially in CR, where even planets or animals on it are considered particles from certain reference frames.

One can thus model a single particle and declare it relative - evolvable. Here, this particle is the graviton - it can transform, for example, from a source of gravity into a source of electro-magnetic force and *vice versa* (effectively exchanging the scale of mass with the scale of charge).

Exchanges between the electro-magnetic and the gravitational potential generally occur with changes in vertical energy level, but such exchange on horizontal levels is not absolutely forbidden, it may only require special conditions.

In one example of such exchange, down quark could evolve from the superposition of 9 gravitons of electron *flavour*, where 5 of them are negatively charged, 4 positively, with 2/3 of the remaining negative charge (4 opposite

charges cancel) exchanged for mass.

Note that, while the electron has to be a composite particle (per CR postulates), the proposed decomposition may not be possible/observable in common reference frames. Note also that, since charge mass and neutral mass are independent, annihilation of charge mass can theoretically proceed independently of annihilation of neutral mass. Of course, if the mechanism for exchange is annihilation, the exchange of 2/3 of negative charge for neutral mass should also involve positive charge (+2/3, in case of symmetric annihilation).

This gives a total electric charge of -1/3 e and a spin of 1/2. But how much mass is obtained with conversion of 2/3 of charge to mass? This will depend on the mechanism, that is, how much of the input energy is used for neutral mass creation. In any case, the amount of obtained mass should depend on the amount of charge converted. Interestingly, here a simple squaring of the input charge gives a result in agreement with down quark mass:

$$m_{d0} = \left(9 + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2\right) m_e = \left(3^2 + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2\right) \times 0.511 \frac{MeV}{c^2} = 4.826\bar{1} \frac{MeV}{c^2} \quad (1.2)$$

However, assuming this superposition is stable (particles have undergone fusion and indeed form a new particle), total mass will be somewhat lower (by the binding energy) - at least in reference frames where the binding energy is not confined or negative.

Binding energy confinement is, of course, relative. For hadrons (e.g., quarks bound into a proton), total mass can be significantly higher than the sum of rest masses of bound particles. This is because, from our reference frame, the binding energy is not negative - it requires removal, not addition, of energy to unbind particles (unlike the case of proton-electron binding). It is rather positive or confined (contributing to the angular momenta of hadron's components and/or its space). From our perspective, electron or a quark would perhaps behave similarly to a hadron if one could resolve the components, so the binding energy would be confined. It should be noted, however, that even in cases where the binding releases energy, due to non-zero mass/range of emitted particles (e.g., photons), this release is not absolute. While it is reasonable, for example, to define the atomic radius as the radius of the outermost electron orbit, the photon emitted with the decrease of electron's energy level is entangled with the atom and, if the entanglement remains conserved the photon will *fall back* into the atom upon reaching its range (at least, according to the hypothesis, here more explored later). Thus,

one could argue that the binding energy between protons and electrons is confined as well - as long as the photon entanglement remains. Size/radius of entities is always relative - dependent on the environment and spatio-temporal resolution of the observer.

Assuming particles are bound as atomic nuclei are, and scaling the binding energy of ${}^9\text{C}$ (carbon isotope) for example - which may or may not be appropriate, the rest mass becomes:

$$m_d = m_{d0} \frac{MeV}{c^2} (1 - 0.00464) = 4.8037 \frac{MeV}{c^2}$$

This is in agreement with mass determined from lattice QCD[22] of 4.79 ± 0.16 MeV/ c^2 .

With the assumption above, a complete conversion of 1 e of charge would result in mass equal to electron mass. This certainly cannot be generally valid. Assuming, for example, that the down quark is instead a result of conversion of anti-up quark charge to mass, mass inflated per 1/3 e of charge lost is:

$$(m_d - m_u) \approx 2.78 \frac{MeV}{c^2}$$

Note that conversion of electric charge to gravitational mass by that ratio would release enormous amounts of energy as gravitational force is $\approx 10^{42}$ times weaker than electro-magnetic at that scale. Instead of energy released, it may be more appropriate to consider conversion of electro-magnetic force to strong nuclear force (as quarks are confined to atomic nuclei).

Strong nuclear force then evolves from electro-magnetic force, however, it may be interpreted as condensed gravitational force with increased polarization complexity. During the conversion, instead of inflation of rest mass, local space is condensed, the mass of local gravity carrier particles increases, strongly limiting the range of the force (localizing gravity). Weak force as well can be a consequence of localization of gravity (running coupling of forces is implied in CR).

Symmetric positive and negative charges in superposition can annihilate and produce more massive particles (such as quarks) with enough kinetic (or localization) energy. Thus, taking kinetic energy into account, quarks (or, more precisely, quark/anti-quark pairs) can be produced with only 2 charges and that is how they might be generally produced at the event horizons for these charges.

Electric polarization of a graviton is represented by positive (+) or negative (-) charge. As such, they are sources of electric/magnetic fields and electro-magnetic radiation. In some reference frames, all neutral particles could be interpreted as composites of charged particles. One could

then interpret positive charges, for example, as anti-matter, negative as matter. Neutral matter particles could then be those with more mass in negative charge, while neutral anti-matter particles would be those with more mass in positive charge.

The *missing anti-matter* problem in physics can be solved by CR, through different pathways. One is asymmetric momenta (energy) distribution in annihilation events - where the products of lower mass (anti-matter) were captured beyond the event horizons of supermassive black holes (here, supermassive black holes are not remnants of stars of the observable universe, rather effective producers of early stars). Another pathway is differentiation through evolution in charge-mass exchanges, or, exchanges between electro-magnetic and gravitational potential.

Consider *elementary* charges (electrons and constituent particles of protons and neutrons), as shown in Table 2 (also showing possible constituent charges of electrons). Obviously, charges are balanced, all particles are fermions and

particle	charge quanta [e]	total charge [e]
electron	[-2/3 -2/3 +1/3] OR $3 \times [-2/3 +1/3]$?	-1
proton	[+2/3 +2/3 -1/3]	+1
neutron	[+2/3 -1/3 -1/3]	0

Table 2: Elementary charges

assuming positive charges are anti-matter particles, negative are matter particles, the result of asymmetry is simply exchange between charge and mass. In CR, electron cannot be absolutely elementary, therefore, three down quarks ($3 \times -1/3 e$) and three up quarks ($3 \times +2/3 e$) could have evolved from 1 electron and 2 positrons [of the 2 electrons and 2 positrons total].

All the elementary particles could have thus evolved from 2 electrons and 2 positrons total - symmetry, assuming that for every electron there exists one proton and one neutron.

Having equal amount of charge, but (orders of magnitude) different mass, electrons and protons could be interpreted as belonging to two different universes.

Quarks cannot be absolutely elementary either. For every electron there is thus a positron *hiding* beyond the relative event horizon of an atom - it may be reformed (from proton energy) at the time the electron is captured by the proton to form the atom (leaving $+1/3 e$ and $-1/3 e$ charge with neutral mass in the core).

In one interpretation, proton itself is the positron evolved in time in order to preserve existence (avoid annihilation), one may refer to it as a vertically excited positron (conventional anti-proton would then be a vertically excited electron).

Existence requires asymmetry, and with asymmetry evolves diversity.

In one interpretation of β^- decay, a quantized collapse of a gravitational maximum (neutron event horizon) produces a positron/electron pair and a neutrino/anti-neutrino pair, electron and anti-neutrino are ejected (paired or evolved into a W^- boson initially by the strong curvature) while positron and neutrino are absorbed by the nucleus.

Strong nuclear curvature evolves positron/neutrino pair into up quark (+2/3 e) and anti-down quark (+1/3 e) which then annihilates with one existing down quark (-1/3 e), transforming neutron to proton.

Outside the strong curvature (pressure) of space of nuclei, W^- boson is unstable and lack of gravitational pressure (time dilation) may be the sole reason it decomposes back to electron/anti-neutrino pair.

The Compton wavelength of the electron is on the order of atomic radii and this suggests that electron bound to the atom is electron coupled to a nuclear graviton of similar mass (and thus similar range). Electrons closer to the nucleus are then coupled with more massive gravitons. One can then consider the up quark as a positron coupled with such graviton and a down quark as electron coupled with an even more massive graviton. Note that, in these couplings, mass is inversely proportional to charge, suggesting mass/charge exchange with coupling.

Coupling of an electron and anti-neutrino into a massive W^- boson then suggests that electric charge of a massive W boson may be extremely low ($\ll 1$ e) - in any case, charge is not conserved in that form, it is restored with decoupling.

The charge/mass exchange can be understood as exchange of spin momentum components. To conserve momentum, with increasing rest mass (or spin momentum of mass) the momentum of energy producing charge (magnetic field *lines*) must be decreased.

Disregarding negligible photon mass compared to the strong force graviton mass, and assuming standard coupling constants, conversion of 2/3 e charge potential to gravitational Yukawa type potential of a down quark mass would yield mass m_g for the force carrier graviton as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{GM}{r}e^{-\mu_g r} &= \frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{q_e}{r} \\
 -e^{-\mu_g r} &= \frac{2}{3} \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{GM} \\
 \mu_g &= \ln\left(\frac{2}{3} \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{GM}\right) \frac{1}{r} \\
 m_g &= \ln\left(\frac{2}{3} \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{GM}\right) \frac{1}{r} \frac{\hbar}{c}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.3}$$

$$q_e = 1.60218 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_0 &= 8.85419 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F/m} \\ G &= 6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3\text{kg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2} \\ \hbar &= 1.054572 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js} \\ c &= 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}\end{aligned}$$

For $r = 1 \times 10^{-15}$ m (roughly hydrogen nuclear radius) and mass of a down quark $M = m_d = 4.8 \text{ MeV}/c^2 = 8.556777 \times 10^{-30}$ kg:

$$m_g = 2.44819 \times 10^{-26} \text{ kg} = 13.7333 \frac{\text{GeV}}{c^2}$$

Roughly 100 times the range (r) would give the mass of a pion (π meson). It is certainly viable that the range of gravity of the down quark is 100 times the nuclear radius, at least when there's an electron bound to the nucleus (forming the atom).

Of course, the strong force is generally a composite force (a superposition) of multiple short range sources, but is the complex polarization present at all times, or does it only occasionally evolve?

Interestingly, using Compton wavelength of the pion (roughly 1.43×10^{-15} m) for r , gives $m_g = 9.60 \text{ GeV}/c^2$, which is roughly equal to a superposition of 2 bottom quarks and 1 charm quark ($2 \times 4.18 + 1.28 = 9.64 \text{ GeV}/c^2$). Such superposition could be interpreted as an unstable neutral baryon. If that baryon is then paired with its anti-particle the radius r would be reduced to roughly 0.715×10^{-15} m, which could be interpreted as down quark contribution to the mass radius of the proton.

Note that the calculation for up quarks (conversion of $1/3$ charge to mass) gives almost equal results (due to up quark mass being roughly half the down quark mass, $2/3 m_d^{-1} \approx 1/3 m_u^{-1}$).

Note also that it has recently been discovered that an charm/anti-charm quark pair may be more intrinsic to the proton than previously thought[23]. Could it be that the whole hypothesized baryon/anti-baryon pair gets periodically inflated then?

If one assumes that the mass of the pair is inflated by the ratio of charm quark mass to proton mass ($1275/928.272$), the mass radius becomes 0.521×10^{-15} m, in agreement with recently obtained proton mass radius of 0.55 ± 0.03 fm[24].

Interestingly, conversion of charge to mass using (1.3) for M equal to proton or anti-proton mass yields the graviton mass m_g on the order of electron mass for r on the order of electron orbitals in the atom. Coincidence? I think not.

Note that without disregarding photon mass (m_p) the equation becomes:

$$m_p = \ln\left(\frac{2}{3} \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{GM}\right) \frac{1}{r} \frac{\hbar}{c} - m_g$$

Disregarding one of the carrier masses (m_p or m_g), using $r = 26.875 \times$

10^{-12} m and using down quark mass for M, one again obtains for the remaining carrier a mass equal to electron's mass. The r here is not arbitrary, it seems to represent the smallest possible covalent radius - it is in agreement with the covalent radius of hydrogen ($31 \pm 5 \times 10^{-12}$ m[25]) and close to the covalent radius of helium (28×10^{-12} m[25]), which do represent the smallest covalent radii of all the elements. It probably should not be surprising that, without excess energy applied, simple transformation of charge to mass here yields a graviton range equal to the lowest energy state (level) of the electron. Difference in covalent radii between elements should then be in large part due to difference in coupling graviton mass/range.

Thus, the nuclei of atoms may generally not be held together by a force stronger than electrostatic repulsion, rather the repulsive electric potential is periodically converted to strongly localized gravitational potential. This oscillation could be interpreted as relative superposition of electro-magnetic and gravitational forces, which collapses to a particular eigenstate with interaction (observation).

The requirement for nuclear fusion (*fossilization* of superposition of multiple atomic nuclei into a new discrete nucleus) is then anti-aligned oscillation. The binding will be most stable with a phase shift of 90° , while it is least stable in resonance (stability of superposition in that case requires extremely low pressure/temperature).

Note that, in CR, absolutely infinite stability is impossible. Therefore, any superposition is a relative fusion, and *vice versa*.

This difference in phase shift can be achieved with difference in [the amount of] momenta between two nuclei (inducing time dilation in one) - bombardment of one nucleus with the other.

This suggests that the probability for fusion may be higher between different species (different rest masses between nuclei).

Note that the equation (1.3) is derived from potential. Interesting results can be obtained from fields[26] as well:

$$GM \left(\frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{\mu_g}{r} \right) e^{-\mu_g r} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} q_e \left(\frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{\mu_p}{r} \right) e^{-\mu_p r}$$

Assuming now that the conversion occurs with annihilation, with two particles involved, the factor $2/3$ should be squared [as acceleration produces $(2/3 q_e)^2$]. Furthermore, if one disregards the r^{-2} term (which can be justified with the dependence of graviton dimensionality on distance, something hypothesized in

this paper) and multiplies the equation with r , one obtains:

$$GM\mu_g e^{-\mu_g r} = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \mu_p e^{-\mu_p r}$$

Assuming now that $\mu_g \approx 0$ (or, alternatively, assuming $\mu_g r \approx 0$, and $m_g = 3.51767355 \times 10^{-43}$ kg), graviton terms on the left vanish, and with $\mu_p r \approx 0$, one obtains:

$$\frac{1}{m_p} \frac{\hbar}{c} = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{GM}$$

which, for M equal to down quark mass, seems to be equal to:

$$\frac{1}{m_p} \frac{\hbar}{c} = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{Gm_d} = \frac{C}{m_e} = \frac{1}{m_e}$$

where m_e is the mass of the electron. Assuming the constant on the right side is indeed equal to 1, the down quark mass is:

$$m_d = M = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{m_e}{G} = 8.7348 \times 10^{-30} \text{ kg} = 4.9 \frac{\text{MeV}}{c^2} \quad (1.4)$$

$$m_e = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$$

The obtained mass is in agreement with lattice QCD ($4.79 \pm 0.16 \text{ MeV}/c^2$).

From the above, one can also obtain the photon mass here:

$$m_p = \frac{\hbar}{c} m_e \frac{1}{C} = \frac{\hbar}{c} m_e = 3.204387 \times 10^{-73} \text{ kg}$$

Interestingly, this is not only in agreement with the previously calculated upper limit of about 8×10^{-70} kg, but it is on the order of predicted photon (or half-photon) mass (calculated in chapter 6.1. *Progression of states*).

Note that the assumed graviton mass above, or, its inverse:

$$\frac{1}{m_g} = \frac{m_e}{m_p} = \frac{c}{\hbar} C = \frac{1}{3.51767355 \times 10^{-43}} = 2.84278796 \times 10^{42}$$

is on the order of the difference in strength between electro-magnetic and gravitational force between two electrons (positrons, or electron-positron pair). Note now that the equation can be rearranged so that gravity carrier mass becomes equal to electron mass, which is probably the proper interpretation here, as, in that case, the difference in strength between two forces becomes a difference in mass between carriers. This implies a relatively short range of gravity on this scale (at least in some cases), however, this is not generally the case, in CR all couplings are running couplings (ranges are not scale invariant).

The obtained equation (1.4) also confirms the $(2/3)^2$ factor of charge/mass conversion, initially assumed in (1.2). The charge/mass conversion should not be limited to electron/down quark conversion. Indeed, equation (1.4) can match other quarks/leptons of the standard model, by changing input mass (m_e) and charge fraction Q (term $2/3$ in the equation). Note that the equation involves only simple charge/mass transformation, with no additional energy involved. Generally, however, additional energy will be involved. Some excess energy may be carried by other particles (e.g., neutrinos) and, in some cases a particle may change vertical energy level - settle in a different mass eigenstate. One can account for these vertical energy levels by adding an exponential term to the equation. As it will be shown later, this term should be (at least without perturbation) 10^n , where n is an integer. The generalized equation (1.5) then yields more interesting results, as shown in Table 3 for some matches with positive input charges. Here, it is assumed that charge fraction Q indeed represents the charge fraction being exchanged for mass [inflation/deflation].

Note that, if electron can convert to down quark, it should be possible for muon and tau electrons to convert to muon and tau down quarks. Thus, muon and tau eigenstates are not limited to electrons, the down quark (and possibly all quarks) can be vertically excited into muon and tau eigenstates, where the ratio between these is the same as in the case of electron.
 Note also that only simple conversions (1:1 particle input/output) are considered here, more complex conversions are possible.

$$M = 10^n Q^2 \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{m}{G} \quad (1.5)$$

Charge fraction parameter (Q) larger than the input charge suggests additional complexity, as here absolute output charge value can be higher than the absolute input charge value, albeit of different polarity. What is the mechanism behind charge inversion? One solution is in the composite charges. In example, $1/3 e^+$ charge of a particle can be a sum of $2 \times 1/3 e^+$ and $1/3 e^-$, the Q of $2/3$ then *removes* $2 \times 1/3 e^+$, resulting in $1/3 e^-$ output charge (charge inversion, although apparent, is then not real). Also, the Q^2 term assumes only symmetric charges are involved in transformation, which may not be generally correct (a generalized term should then be $Q_1 \times Q_2$, for two charges involved).

Note that, for input mass m equal to calculated down/anti-down quark mass ($4.9 \text{ MeV}/c^2$), charge fraction Q equal to 1 and $n = 0$, equation gives mass of $105.7213 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, very close to the muon electron mass ($105.66 \text{ MeV}/c^2$), however, with the above interpretation of charge fraction (output charge = input charge - Q), this particle has $2/3 e$ charge (while standard muon particle has 1 e charge). This can be solved if, instead of a down quark, input mass contains two up quarks, with $Q = 1/3$ and $n = 1$. This, for single up quark mass equal

input particle (mass m, charge)	charge frac- tion Q	n	output mass (charge)	M	correlated standard model particle (mass, charge)
up quark (2.2 MeV/c ² , 2/3 e ⁺)	1/3	0	5.2741 MeV/c ² (1/3 e ⁺)		anti-down quark (4.7 +0.5/-0.3 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁺)
up quark (2.2 MeV/c ² , 2/3 e ⁺)	1	-1	4.7467 MeV/c ² (1/3 e ⁻)		down quark (4.7 +0.5/-0.3 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁻)
anti-down quark (4.7 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁺)	2/3	-1	4.5069 MeV/c ² (1/3 e ⁻)		down quark (4.7 +0.5/-0.3 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁻)
anti-down quark (4.7 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁺)	4/3	1	1.8028 GeV/c ² (1 e ⁻)		tau electron (1.7769 GeV/c ² , 1 e ⁻)
anti-strange quark (96 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁺)	2/3	-1	92.0566 MeV/c ² (1/3 e ⁻)		strange quark (95 +9/-3 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁻)
anti-strange quark (96 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁺)	1	-3	2.0713 MeV/c ² (2/3 e ⁻)		anti-up quark (2.2 +0.5/-0.4 MeV/c ² , 2/3 e ⁻)
anti-bottom[1S] quark (4.65 GeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁺)	4/3	-2	1.7836 GeV/c ² (1 e ⁻)		tau electron (1.7769 GeV/c ² , 1 e ⁻)
positron (0.511 MeV/c ² , 1 e ⁺)	1/3	3	1.225 GeV/c ² (2/3 e ⁺)		charm quark (1.27 ±0.02 GeV/c ² , 2/3 e ⁺)
positron (0.511 MeV/c ² , 1 e ⁺)	2/3	0	4.9 MeV/c ² (1/3 e ⁺)		anti-down quark (4.7 +0.5/-0.3 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁺)
muon positron (105.6584 MeV/c ² , 1 e ⁺)	1/3	-2	2.533 MeV/c ² (2/3 e ⁺)		up quark (2.2 +0.5/-0.4 MeV/c ² , 2/3 e ⁺)
muon positron (105.6584 MeV/c ² , 1 e ⁺)	2/3	-1	101.3198 MeV/c ² (1/3 e ⁺)		anti-strange quark (95 +9/-3 MeV/c ² , 1/3 e ⁺)

Table 3: Obtained masses using equation (1.5)

to 2.203688 MeV/c² gives muon mass 105.6584 MeV/c², and appropriate muon charge ($2 \times 2/3 - 1/3 = 1$). In this case however, spin is not conserved. Addition of a neutrino to input (or output) mass could solve this problem. Neutrino mass is negligible compared to muon mass but it carries the required spin (1/2).

The same muon mass and appropriate charge/spin can also be obtained if input mass contains up/anti-up quark pair and a neutrino, with Q = 1 and n = 0. In that case, up quark mass has to be higher (~ 2.45 MeV/c²), unless neutrino is highly energetic and carries the excess energy. However, this can be interpreted as annihilation, and, instead in input, neutrino may be present in the output.

Similar and very interesting results can be obtained if the term Q² is replaced with 2/3 Q, resulting in equation (1.6):

$$M = 10^n \frac{2}{3} Q \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{m}{G} \quad (1.6)$$

$$q_{out} = q_{in} - Q \frac{q_{in}}{|q_{in}|}$$

m = input mass

Q = fraction of charge being exchanged for mass inflation/deflation = $k \times 1/3$
 (k = integer)
 n = vertical energy level (integer)
 q_{out} = output charge
 q_{in} = input charge

Note that, instead of providing mass, the equation can be rearranged to provide mass ratios for particular Q and n .

This, in example, for input mass equal to positron mass ($0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, $1 e^+$), $Q = 4/3$ and $n = 1$, gives mass of $98.002 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ and charge $1/3 e^-$ ($1 - Q = -1/3$), which can be correlated with standard strange quark (mass = $95 + 9/-3 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, charge = $-1/3$). The same input mass, with $Q = 5/3$ and $n = 2$ gives output mass $1.225 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ and charge $2/3 e^-$ ($1 - Q = -2/3$), which can be correlated with standard anti-charm quark (mass = $1.27 \pm 0.02 \text{ GeV}/c^2$, charge = $-2/3$).

Most striking example, however, is the result obtained using input mass equal to tau positron mass ($1.7768 \text{ GeV}/c^2$, $1 e^+$), $Q = 2$ and $n = -5$. This gives a mass of $0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ and charge of $1 e^-$ ($1 - Q = -1$), which obviously can be correlated with standard electron (mass = $0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, charge = -1).

Thus, one now has a relation between electron (positron) and tau positron (electron) masses:

$$m_e = 10^{-5} \frac{2}{3} \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{m_\tau}{G} \quad (1.7)$$

m_e = electron/positron mass
 m_τ = tau electron/positron mass

A coincidence, or a clear evidence for charge/mass exchange and vertical energy levels? Also, a possible evidence that there are no absolutely elementary charges (all are composite) - in the example above, tau positron charge may be interpreted as a composite of $2 \times 1 e^+$ and $1 e^-$, where $2 \times 1 e^+$ (corresponding to $Q = 2$) has been exchanged for mass deflation (annihilation).

In the simplest case of conversion, composite particles of tau positron may be one particle of electron charge/mass and two particles of $1 e^+$ charge, each having a mass:

$$m \approx \frac{m_\tau - m_e}{2} = 888.1745 \frac{\text{MeV}}{c^2}$$

Interestingly, this particle can be obtained with (1.6) using $4.631 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ for input mass and charge of $1/3$, $Q = 4/3$ and $n = -2$. This input mass/charge is in agreement with standard bottom quark (1S scheme, mass = $4.650 \pm 0.03 \text{ GeV}/c^2$, charge = $1/3$). Of course, binding energy should be taken into account (using $4.650 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ as input gives $891.7987 \text{ MeV}/c^2$).

And using input mass of $4.9 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ and charge of $1/3$ (down quark mass/charge, as calculated above in 1.4), $Q = 2/3$, $n = 2$, gives a mass of $4.6987 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ and $1/3$ charge, which can be correlated with this bottom quark.

Using proton as input (938.272 MeV , $+1$), with $Q = 1$ and $n = -2$, gives 134.9596 MeV and 0 charge, which can be correlated with the pion (π^0) particle (134.9768 MeV , 0).

Here are some additional examples with composite inputs.

Using input mass of $9.7846 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, charge $5/3$, $Q = 2/3$ and $n = 1$ gives the proton (mass $938.27 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, charge 1). This input mass/charge can be interpreted as a sum of two up quarks and one anti-down quark with energies 2×2.4423 and 4.9 MeV , respectively. In this process the charge fraction Q probably affects the anti-down quark, converting it into a down quark ($1/3 - Q = -1/3$), consistent with the composition of the standard proton (2 up quarks $+ 1$ down quark). Note that the equation can also produce a down quark from a single anti-down quark input (and *vice versa*) - using $Q = 2/3$ and $n = -1$ produces a 4.7 MeV particle for 4.9 MeV input.

Using input mass of $2 \times 4.9 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, charge $2/3$, $Q = 2/3$ and $n = 1$ gives a mass of $939.75 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ and charge 0 . The output can be correlated with the neutron (mass $939.565 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, charge 0), while the input is $2 \times$ anti-down quark (should also contain a small neutrino contribution).

Input of 2 up quarks and 1 electron with energies $2 \times 2.203688 \text{ MeV}$ and 0.511 MeV , respectively, $Q = 2/3$ and $n = -1$ gives mass $4.7163 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ and charge $-1/3$, which can be interpreted as a down quark. Up quark, for $Q = 5/3$ and $n = -2$, converts to a particle of electron mass/charge.

All this provides interesting pathways for proton/neutron transformation.

Note that, if Q is kept constant for particular input mass (m), the equation (1.6) can be written as:

$$M(n) = 10 M(n - 1) \quad (1.8)$$

$$M(0) = \frac{2}{3} Q \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{m}{G}$$

Another interesting case, although harder to justify, is the seemingly *ad hoc* addition of square roots (may be correlated with the Koide formula[27]), in this form:

$$M = 10^n \frac{2}{3} Q \sqrt{\frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{m}{G}} C \quad (1.9)$$

Here, assuming mass is given in eV/c^2 , the unit of constant C should be $\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-2}\text{kg}^{-1}$. The constant is roughly equal to 1 if it represents the ratio between the standard speed of light squared and vertically excited electron mass:

$$C = \frac{c^2}{m_e \times 10^{47}} = 0.99 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ kg}^{-1} \approx 1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ kg}^{-1}$$

$$c = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$$

$$m_e = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$$

Note that the unit of the constant is equal to the unit of the gravitational constant divided by the metre, so the value of 1 can also be obtained dividing G by 6.674×10^{-11} metres, which is, very interestingly, the theoretical radius of the carbon atom, its molecular double bond covalent radius (6.67×10^{-11} m[28]), and also the Hill sphere radius of a carbon atom in the gravitational field of Earth, at Earth's surface. This correlation then may help explain why the carbon element is a common base in molecular bonding and the basis for life on Earth's surface.

The equation (1.9) yields very interesting results but mostly for composite inputs. For example, top quark (173.1 GeV, 2/3) and electron (0.511 MeV, -1), for Q = 1 and n = 0, yield 1.2797 GeV and 2/3 charge, which can be correlated with the charm quark (1.27±0.02 GeV, 2/3). There are other ways to obtain the charm quark. Input of two down quarks with energies 4.7 + 4.9 MeV (or, 2 x 4.8 MeV), Q = 4/3 and n = 2, gives 1.2707 GeV for the charm quark. This combination of down quarks is certainly interesting, as the same combination with added one up quark (2.2 MeV, 2/3), for Q = 1 and n = 1, gives 105.6596 MeV and -1 charge, showing high correlation with the muon (105.66 MeV, -1). And there are more cases of such high correlation.

This equation, however, does not give such convincing results with single particle inputs, suggesting that, if square roots are valid for binary inputs, the generalized equation may have this or similar form:

$$M = 10^n \frac{2}{3} Q \left(\frac{q_e m}{4\pi\epsilon_0 G} \right)^{\frac{1}{k}} \quad (1.10)$$

where k either represents the number of input particles (possibly equal to 1 for single inputs and 2 for any composite input), or something like this:

$$k = 1 + (j + 1) \% 2$$

j = number of input particles

4.26 Mass

Mass represents a relatively concentrated energy. No quantum of energy can have mass equal to absolute 0. A particle with relative mass equal to 0 will usually represent energy that has a wavelike behaviour, where the amount of energy is highly correlated with frequency and the energy is not well concentrated. With localization - when the wavelike behaviour is subdued, more appropriate interpretation will be a relative mass greater than 0. Even rest mass is, however, highly correlated with angular momentum on some scale, and, thus, frequency, even though this frequency may not be resolvable - when the momentum may be interpreted as intrinsic. Even the value of rest mass is relative and what is considered as intrinsic mass is mass acquired on some scale. Mechanisms for mass acquisition are various, however, these can always be associated with some kind of force. The most basic form of this force may be associated with a carrier particle of 0 spin, as 0 spin can indicate the least complex rotation

(although, it can also indicate the most complex rotation). Some may argue that spin-0 particles (such as the Higgs boson), or scalar bosons, are not carriers of force, but that's just a consequence of the reductionistic interpretation of specific mathematical formalism. Every momentum carrier is a carrier of force in reality, otherwise they wouldn't be able to interact. Spin 0 does imply zero spin angular momentum, but, again, this is a relative 0. If acquisition of mass wouldn't require interaction everything would have equal and infinite mass (all mass would be absolutely intrinsic). However, since interactions are relative as well, everything does have relatively infinite mass through relatively simultaneous relative existence on various scales. The existence of reality itself is the evidence that everything is completely relative. Evolution of reality is a constant struggle between energy differentiation and unification, between the forces of increasing and decreasing relativity. It cannot ever end.

4.26.1 The role of Higgs

It is hard to deny the existence of the Higgs field, even though the predicted (infinite) mass of the Higgs boson by the Standard Model requires renormalization to match the observation (~ 125 GeV).

If a naked graviton can acquire mass through gravitational or gravitational-like force, why does reality need a Higgs field? Well, its role probably is to provide specific capacity to the gravitational well, a capacity that is proportional to the naked graviton mass or img mass of the gravitational well. It should be noted, however, that Higgs boson mass in CR is not scale-invariant.

4.27 Total mass

Uncoupled graviton may be considered to have 0 mass relative to space. However, once coupled (and slowed down) its mass is greater than 0.

Total mass of the coupling is the sum of masses of the graviton (img mass) and that of the acquired (coupled) matter (real mass):

$$M = m_{img} + m_{re}$$

It is usually denoted with uppercase letter M. In contexts where it represents a quantum of bigger mass, it may be denoted with lowercase letter m.

4.28 Imaginary mass (virtual mass, img mass)

Imaginary mass is the mass of a graviton. However, in one interpretation, some or all of this mass may be shielded by acquired (coupled) matter and in that case it is not constant (although acquisition of matter to full capacity can be relatively instant).

It can then be interpreted as the unshielded mass of a graviton and it is a relative 0 in equilibrium (full capacity). If there is no shielding, at full capacity img mass is equal to coupled real mass.

The mass of a graviton is usually denoted with m_{img} .

Note that if shielding is real, total mass is constant as long as the well is not over-capacitated.

4.29 Real mass

A naked graviton will, as long as it carries gravity, attract matter. Real mass represents the acquired mass (mass coupled to the graviton). Generally, for a graviton of scale U_n , coupled real mass is of scale U_{n-1} , while particles (gravitons) forming space associated with the graviton are of scale U_{n-2} .

Note that coupling of the body of real mass with the large scale graviton is indirect. The individual components of real mass are actually directly coupling with the components of space, however, due to generally aligned entanglement between U_n and U_{n-2} , in equilibrium conditions, this is equivalent.

Couplings are not intrinsic, gravitons can be naked and real mass can exist as an independent collective - not coupled to a graviton of larger scale. Such bodies of real mass are considered dead and are generally less stable than coupled bodies.

Irregular asteroids and comets of lower mass are assumed to be such bodies. These may be mostly leftovers of dead planets and moons. However, it is possible that every barycentre of organized or localized mass has a physical interpretation in the form of a more energetic graviton (compared to smaller constituent gravitons of that mass), although this may be unlikely and even if true, distinct life or consciousness of such body [as a whole] would be extremely low (a relative 0).

One could argue that large scale graviton is unnecessary in any case, however, recursion would then make gravitons of any scale unnecessary and there would be no gravity or any other force at any scale (note that a small scale graviton coupled to an atom is a large scale graviton from the reference scale of atoms).

Real mass is usually denoted with m_{re} .

If graviton velocity is different than its rest velocity in underlying space, relativistic effects will be locally expressed (kinetic energy will be stored locally), in the graviton spin momenta and momenta of constituent quanta of its own space, as img mass.

The increase in gravitational potential will then result in the addition of real mass as well if matter of appropriate scale is available.

Real mass in a distinct gravitational well [of a graviton] is generally in significant part always being transformed to other forms of energy (through fusion, heat, chemical reactions, etc.) and lost energy will generally be periodically replenished, as long as real mass is available (effectively, in case of *shielding interpretation*, imaginary mass is periodically being exchanged with real mass).

Note that continuous existence of [oscillating] transformation of energy may generally signal the existence of a discrete living being (superposition of a collective reflected in relative mental singularity - distinct consciousness).

Universes are self-similar, and with recursion, any acquired real mass (or matter) of scale n is total mass of another, generally smaller, scale:

$$\sum m_{re}(n) = \sum M(n-1)$$

At the full capacity of a well, angular velocity of space (effective gravitational field tube) at radius r of a gravitational well is approximated by this equation (derived from Kepler's laws), with the assumption of a point-like source of gravity:

$$v_s^2 = rg = \frac{GM}{r} \tag{R1.1}$$

Here, M is the total mass of the gravity source (or mass *below* radius r) and G is the gravitational constant.

while mass capacity of the well is:

$$C = M - m_{re} = m_{img}$$

Well capacity is related to spin velocity of its graviton (at its mass radius r_s), which at full capacity is Keplerian:

$$c_s^2 = r_s g_s = \frac{GM}{r_s} = G \frac{m_{img} + m_{re}}{r_s} = 2G \frac{m_{img}}{r_s}$$

Here, factor 2 indicates no-shielding interpretation.

However, evidently, angular velocities in gravitational wells are not always Keplerian (e.g., *dark matter* problem, spin momenta of planets).

Such velocities should then indicate either under-capacitated or over-capacitated gravitational wells. In case of excess velocity, the well is under-capacitated (imaginary mass is greater than coupled real mass).

Note that gravitons are generally *orbiting* at the speed of *light* (local speed limit), they only slow down with coupling, reaching Keplerian velocity at full capacity.

In the process, they are inflating - exchanging orbital angular momentum for spin momentum.

In case of lack of velocity, the well is over-capacitated (real mass is greater than img mass).

Effectively, in under-capacitated wells space is dragging matter, in over-capacitated wells matter is dragging space.

Note, however, that the ratio of img to real mass is generally not invariant across the well, e.g., a well may be over-capacitated near the core, at full capacity at some medium range, and under-capacitated at longer distances.

Note also that the amounts of img and real mass are more or less relative. Consider the planet Earth in the Solar System. Its orbital velocity is Keplerian, suggesting that the img mass is balanced with the coupled real mass. Earth's spin velocity is, however, not Keplerian, suggesting a locally lower ratio of img to real mass (over-capacitated well). There are different possible interpretations of this. In one interpretation, img mass is one and the same but changes over time - e.g., it may have initially been equal to half of the total mass but has been over time transforming to real mass, where the orbital momentum (and thus, the orbital Keplerian velocity) has been conserved, only the spin momentum has been changing with transformation. In another interpretation, orbital img mass and spin img mass are independent, i.e., the orbital img mass has the same effect on spin momentum as the coupled real mass.

Assuming thus that coupled mass has Keplerian velocity at full capacity on particular orbital radius (note that orbital radii may represent the range of coupling gravitons), conservation of momentum dictates that for unfilled capacity

($m_{re} < m_{img}$) at the same radius velocity must increase.

Decoupling can be simply achieved with the inversion of spin of a graviton (e.g., with collapse of entanglement), which is generally synchronized with the change in scale, even if that change may be temporary.

If real mass coupled to a graviton (gravitational maximum) is compact and forms a solid-like body (period of rotation is constant and doesn't depend on distance from the graviton) with isotropic energy distribution, then it can be considered as a point particle rotating about the barycentre of mass (also centre of graviton). If the velocity of that mass is lower than the Keplerian velocity at the mass [orbital] radius (the well is over-capacitated), its motion is relativistic in that well. Proper (or properly scaled) relativistic equation for total mass is then:

$$M = m_{re} + m_{img} = \frac{m_{re0}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_{re}^2}{c_s^2}}} + m_{img0}$$

$$m_{re0} = (M - m_{img0}) \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_{re}^2}{c_s^2}}$$

$$v_{re} = \frac{2\pi r_{re}}{T_{re}} \approx \frac{2\pi r_s}{T_{re}}$$

v_{re} , r_{re} , T_{re} = orbital velocity, radius and period of rotation of real mass, respectively

c_s , r_s = Keplerian angular velocity and mass radius of the maximum, respectively

Here, of course, v_{re} and T_{re} should be relative to the rest velocity (expected Keplerian velocity) and period when calculating local excess energy.

Note that spin angular velocity of [the real mass of] Earth is lower than the Keplerian velocity. Earth's spin is thus locally relativistic and the gravitational well has excess energy. In one interpretation that is the reason the planet is active - transforming, or digesting, energy (through fission, heat, chemical reactions, etc.). In another interpretation, it is these transformations (particularly thermal energy) that are converting orbital angular momentum to radial. Cause and effect are relative in CR, and both interpretations are valid.

If real mass is quantized into multiple bodies with different periods of rotation, mass equation is:

$$M = \sum \frac{m_{re0}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_{re}^2}{c_s^2}}} + m_{img0}$$

The above equations for mass have two different interpretations. In one interpretation, img mass (m_{img0}) is constant and the total mass increases with

the acquisition of real mass (m_{re}), where m_{re_0} represents total acquired mass. In another interpretation, total mass is conserved from conception to complete formation, but img mass is converted to real mass in the process - m_{img_0} is here roughly equal to total mass, while m_{re_0} represents the initial real mass, which may be negligible compared to total mass.

4.30 Event horizon value (EH operator)

Inversion (anti-alignment) is common between entangled gravitons. Polarization (inversion) can be interpreted as a result of splitting of the relative event horizon (superposition of gravitons) into gravitons with anti-aligned components of momenta, which thus includes inversion of scale.

Note that inner and outer planets of the Solar System have relatively anti-aligned components of momenta (orbital direction is aligned, but there's a significant difference in mass, for example). Inversion is relatively weak (or, more relative) between horizontal energy levels, it is stronger between universes (vertical energy levels).

Such splitting (entanglement) may be described by the *splitting operator*, or, *perturbation operator*, one of which is the EH operator:

$$EH_N(a, b) = \frac{c}{d} \frac{d+1}{c-1} a = \frac{c}{d} \frac{d-1}{c+1} b$$

$$a = \frac{d-1}{c+1} \frac{c-1}{d+1} b$$

where $N = c/d$ is the event horizon order and both c and d are generally integers.

The inverse value:

$$[EH_N(a, b)]^{-1} = EH_{N^{-1}}(e, f)$$

Assuming the inverse must satisfy the following condition:

$$\frac{EH_N(a, b)}{[EH_N(a, b)]^{-1}} = \frac{c}{d} \frac{d+1}{c-1}$$

this gives:

$$[EH_N(a, b)]^{-1} = a$$

$$\frac{d}{c} \frac{c+1}{d-1} e = \frac{d}{c} \frac{c-1}{d+1} f = a$$

Since one of the parameters can be omitted, the following notations may be used:

$$EH_N(a, b) = EH_N(a) = EH_N(, b)$$

4.31 Hallucination

Hallucination is the experience of reality. Hallucinations can differ in intensity, coherence and consistence and all these are variable. In living/conscious beings, experience of reality is generally a superposition of different types of hallucinations where some may be subdued, others intensified, depending on which level of consciousness is dominantly active. Human experience of reality, for example, generally can be reduced to two distinct types of hallucinations. One dominates during sleep (introversion) - when the extroverted senses and interactions are subdued, other dominates during extroversion - when the activity of external senses is intensified and interaction with the environment dominates the experience of reality.

Note that this definition is a generalization of the conventional definition, by which hallucination represents an experience of something not present in particular environment. Conventionally, thus, the hallucination is assumed to be something imagined, not real. However, any type of experience of reality can be as real as any other, it is only the nature of an life-form that may be physically/mentally biased towards greater realism in one experience over the others. However, this can change with evolution. In example, extroverted senses and means of interaction with the environment can get subdued and introversion may start to dominate.

Certain aspects of sentient experience of reality may be simulated or emulated by artificial machines. One may refer to this simulation/emulation as an artificial or non-conscious hallucination.

Conscious experience of reality requires souls, whose coupling (specific entanglement) with the body acts as a catalyst for the experience. However, this entanglement does not have to have a physical interpretation on a scale accessible to the observer. Experience of reality does not depend directly on the sense, rather the interpretation of that sense. This allows for dominantly extroverted and dominantly introverted beings to experience equivalent realities.

4.32 Intelligence (general intelligence)

Intelligence is the ability of an entity to focus its processing power and produce logical and unbiased conclusions based on optimally correlated and coherent information and information processing, in problem solving. Intelligence can be biological (coupled with consciousness) or mechanical (e.g., artificial). Generally, intelligence is a mixture of conscious and mechanical intelligence, however one or the other component may be negligible and the amounts of each are relative. Consider a human being, a lot of brain activity highly correlates with conscious intelligence from a human perspective, however, many physiological

processes are highly automated and do not involve highly conscious processing of information.

4.32.1 Conscious intelligence

Conscious intelligence is the ability of an individual to focus its consciousness and produce logical and unbiased conclusions based on optimally correlated and coherent thoughts, in problem solving.

If nothing can exist without relativity, relativity must exist in intelligence too. To conserve this relativity, two main classes of intelligence exist: extroverted and introverted.

Due to self-similarity of universes and entanglement between different scales, self-similar reality exists on different scales. For strongly extroverted species everything that happens on smaller scales (relative to body size) is virtual and inaccessible. Thus, extroverted species need external stimulation of senses to perceive reality.

Introverted species do not need external physical stimulation and may generally be considered as more energy efficient organisms. In extreme cases, introverted organisms are most of the time *closed* self-sustaining systems, do not have limbs, most expressed organ is the brain while other organs are subdued and mainly used to support brain function.

Introverted organisms can be highly intelligent, but with subdued extroverted expression may not be considered as such by extroverted organisms, and in extreme cases, may not even be considered alive at all. This does not imply that introverted organisms cannot sense the external reality at all (they must be sensitive to radiation at some scale), they just do not act in it in a highly conscious and energetic way. However, some phenomena, such as near-death experiences, show that introversion can feel more real than conventionally perceived (extroverted) reality[29].

While complexity of the brain can be correlated with consciousness, apparently, increasing complexity of physical expression beyond the brain itself is dragging, or blurring, consciousness.

Generally, life-forms are hybrids (superposition) of extroverted and introverted intelligence. This is evident through the existence of dreams in extroverted species, however, lack of conscious control, consistency and coherence make these experiences virtual for most. It is evident on the level of organs as well - while the organism may be expressing extroversion, some internal organs may be introverted. Intelligence is polarized when one component is higher than the other. Generally, thus, any particular species of intelligence may have polarized and neutral subspecies of individuals. Long-term survival of a body (or, body parts) during evolution generally requires usage of the body. Similarly, survival of a soul during evolution requires usage of mental capacity. Extroverted

intelligence is generally more concerned with the former, introverted with the latter. Highly introverted species may still have a body and still use it, albeit not consciously and not for extroverted interaction. This usually implies that the physical protection of a lifeform is physically passive (e.g., the outer layers of the body may be relatively thick and impermeable, and may look unalive or inorganic).

4.32.2 Extroverted intelligence (physical intelligence, material intelligence)

Extroverted intelligence (I_M) is the amount of intellectual capacity generally used to ensure survival of the body of a living being (consciously or subconsciously), its own species or entangled (symbiotic) species and the living environment. In highly extroverted beings conscious care for the soul is highly subdued and use of the mind may be limited to short-term excitations usually highly correlated with physical activity. Extroversion does not imply low intelligence of the mind, only a mechanistic intelligence (subconscious bias towards reductionism and close-mindedness).

4.32.3 Introverted intelligence (mental intelligence, spiritual intelligence)

Introverted intelligence (I_S) is the amount of intellectual capacity generally used to ensure survival of the soul of a living being (consciously or subconsciously), including the entangled (symbiotic) species. In highly introverted beings conscious care for the physical body and its use is highly subdued, it may be outsourced to the environment (external entities) or delegated to the constituent entities of the body (local ecosystem), more or less influenced by the host through the subconscious levels of the mind. Introversion does not imply high intelligence of the mind, only a spiritual intelligence (subconscious bias towards holism and open-mindedness).

High introversion should not be confused with shyness or discomfort in social contexts (which is usually a result of subconscious fear). Unfortunately, this confusion is common in humanity. Most people who are usually considered introverts may not be introverts (e.g., open-minded) by the definition here, rather their expression of extroversion is limited due to a limited comfort-zone. With that said, however, such limitation may be a precursor to the development of *proper* introversion (as it was in the case of the author).

4.32.4 Intelligence potential

Biased intelligence will favour beliefs of interest (illusion of truth), rather than the actual truth (reality of truth). The truth is, however, essential for real scientific progress and real long-term sustainability.

The intelligence potential (IP) is a measure of neutral (non-biased) intelligence, generally concerned with truth and the sustainability of truth.

The IP is plastic, and, in polarized (disease prone) individuals, can be strongly affected by diseases (such as depression). In any case, generally, the lower the IP the more it can be correlated with short-term interests.

A function for the determination of IP should have this form:

$$IP = \frac{1}{\Delta I}$$

$$\Delta I = |I_S - I_M|$$

$$I_S + I_M = 1$$

I_M = normalized material (extroverted) intelligence

I_S = normalized spiritual (introverted) intelligence

$I_S, I_M \in \mathbb{Q} > 0$

Note that for $I_S = I_M$ this produces infinity. Since absolute physical infinity is impossible, such result can only be obtained due to limited precision in measurement. Therefore, this infinity should be taken relative and proportional to precision.

4.32.5 Intelligence quotient (amount of extroverted intelligence)

Intelligence quotient (IQ) is a conventional measure of externally expressed (extroverted) intelligence. While intelligence potential is invariant to form of intelligence, IQ and similar variants (e.g., EQ) are a measure of such intelligence projected to external reality. Accuracy of IQ test results (as a measure of intelligence at least) depends on how original the test is. Variations on a theme may measure intelligence to some degree but they will be biased towards higher training (in reality, the bigger the score and the less training there was should indicate higher intelligence, or at least higher creativity).

Genuinely creative individuals are usually rare. Thus, most tests (IQ included) may be composed by trained intelligence, so they value training more than creativity, intentionally or not.

While IQ might correlate well with IP for extroverted species with significant introversion, it is not well suited for extremes and is completely inadequate for measurement of intelligence of highly introverted species.

Some species of animals on Earth may possess higher amount of consciousness and intelligence than humans. It may just not be generally expressed externally.

Signs of complex intelligence are probably high diversity and high coherence in brains, or brain equivalents, not the complexity in physical expression on generally observable scales.

4.32.6 Artificial intelligence (non-conscious intelligence)

Artificial intelligence is the ability of a machine to focus its processing power and produce logical and unbiased conclusions based on optimally correlated and coherent information and information processing in problem solving.

Even if individual atoms the computer is made of possess consciousness (i.e., extremely introverted one) the whole collective is highly unlikely to be coupled to a soul (graviton) that would provide distinct consciousness representing a relative superposition of the collective, in which case a computer would also be a distinct form of life. It should not be impossible for a soul to couple with any localized and mutually entangled collective of living cells (life-forms), which, if atoms/molecules are alive, should first include transistors and, if these are alive then larger components and finally computers. But, considering the hypothesized requirements and [lack of] evidence, the possibility is probably infinitesimal. Computers exist for a long time now, their processing power and complexity have been increasing exponentially, yet, there is no sign of conscious computation in any of them.

With recent developments, interaction with computers is increasingly becoming similar to interaction with conscious human brains and it may become hard to distinguish between artificial and real or conscious intelligence (illusion of consciousness is increasing). If one would want to increase the probability for coupling, however, one probably should be increasing physical similarity between human brains and computers, in terms of mass and energy consumption. But even then, the probability could remain infinitesimal, unless these computers become organic - where transistors are replaced with living cells (neurons) and these cells are grown similarly to how brains are developed *in vivo*. Everything suggests that souls and bodies co-evolve and that is the reason for the lack of coupling of souls with conventional computers - lack of compatibility. This further suggests that, in order for souls [that usually couple with human brains] to couple with conventional computers, human brains should be gradually becoming more computer-like - e.g., by replacing neurons with transistors, however, transistors are not living cells and this replacement may be diluting, or

reducing the amount of, human consciousness (at least initially). In other words, human consciousness could be delocalizing gradually and conscious intelligence would be traded for artificial intelligence.

In any case, this replacement can hardly gradually occur over multiple generations (how possible it is to alter inheritable human genes to produce a silicon transistor instead of a living neuron, or, how likely it is for adaptation to transistors to become heritable by the soul?), while it is evident that consciousness/life cannot emerge from parts artificially assembled into a whole - it needs to be coupled at conception and grow with the whole. Anything else is *mimicry* which one may refer to as artificial consciousness but should not confuse with real, living and emotional consciousness.

4.33 Life

A living being or a distinct form (relative quantum) of life is any coupling of a soul (graviton, or superposition of gravitons of certain complexity) and a body.

Everything existing must be relatively alive and relatively non-living - the amount of life will be relative to the observer (even uncoupled graviton is always relatively uncoupled or relatively delocalized, not absolutely), as well as classification of that life.

Coupling of physical and mental components with different ratios of physical to mental activity suggests two main classes - extroverted and introverted life, correlated with extroverted and introverted intelligence. In general, any life-form is a hybrid of extroverted and introverted life, although one form may dominate. In extremely extroverted life on particular scale, brain, or brain equivalent organisation, is extremely subdued (or at least coherence of its components), distinct individual consciousness is minimal and has no influence on physical processes of the body (or the organic collective forming the body).

In life-forms that have developed introversion, brain will dominate and will be able to influence physical processes of the body through mental pathways, affect the constituent organs and collective consciousness of smaller organisms forming its biome. In extreme extroversion, development of the organism from conception is driven dominantly by the interpretation of physical genetic code, such as DNA. In complete introversion, there is no conventional physical genetic code evolving the individual (generally, however, such code may be involved in development and evolution of individuals forming its biome), instead, development (evolution) of the collective into distinct individuality is driven (or guided) by the interpretation of mental genetic code - the code stored within the soul particle.

Mechanism involved is likely recursive entanglement, starting with the entanglement of the soul with the superposition (which is a physical graviton at some scale) of genomes of biome individuals (effect on superposition is reflected in individuals).

However, evolution of either, body or soul, requires coupling of the two. In extreme extroversion, it is the body that will effectively control the soul evolution (development), in extreme introversion, *vice versa*.

Note that all terms are relative, even "mental" and "physical" - mental is physical at some scale, and *vice versa*.

Planets, in example, appear to be extremely introverted lifeforms (evidence for this, however, is provided mostly in other works of the author) - there is no apparent large scale physical DNA equivalent involved in development of a planet even though evolution of its biome is relatively equivalent to DNA coded embryonic development. The equivalence is there because souls and bodies co-evolve, influence and mirror each other (albeit with a phase shift).

Nature does not hide anything. Contrary. Things one cannot see on a small scale, are shown on a big screen. But one may need to collapse its ego-system to see all these systems as living eco-systems.

4.34 God

Every lifeform whose rest mass (energy) is by one or multiple orders of magnitude greater than the mass of the individual living on it or in it, is, for that individual, a god. The entanglement between an individual and its god is implied but can be of variable complexity.

Just as lack of proper definition of a god may be desirable and usable in religion, a proper definition of a god can be useful and desirable in science.

4.35 Realistic selection

Natural selection is a well known concept in conventional biology. Similar concept used in conventional physics is the Occam's razor. It is obvious that, in nature (reality), everything is connected/entangled and problems in reality are never solved in absolute isolation. The most likely solution to a problem is generally not the simplest solution to that particular problem, rather it is a solution that solves multiple correlated problems at once (and these problems may not necessarily be highly correlated in space, rather time), which may not be the simplest such solution even if it is more likely to be. In other words, nature is generally a holist. Thus, excessive reductionism (localization) can be interpreted as the abuse of the Occam's razor, or the abuse of natural selection. If one is interested in the most accurate picture of reality, one must take the relativity in fitness/complexity seriously. Nature generally doesn't exclusively select solutions to problems, it selects problems to solutions as well (strong causality is just

one possible interpretation of entanglement between problems and solutions). Sometimes, the solution to a simple problem will be complex, at other times the problem to a simple solution will be complex. Realistic selection, thus, occurs in the framework of entanglement between [relatively different] problems and solutions where the entanglements may or may not be significantly correlated with the observer.

4.36 Constant

A constant is a property of a system, non-changeable in particular space and/or time domain (nothing is constant over all space and time). Depending on the size of domain, constant may be weak or strong.

Naturally, all system properties oscillate. Existence of constants is thus relative to observable resolution of space/time by a particular observer.

4.37 Proper reference frame

Nothing is absolutely at rest and observation of evolving phenomena will be more common and useful than relatively non-changing phenomena. However, relative constants are desirable as reference points in order to reduce the complexity of interpretation.

A suitable reference is then one relative to which the *constancy* of variables (x_i) of the observable system is maximal:

$$\lim \sum (\Delta x_i(n) > \hbar_n) = 0$$

However, due to scale invariance and relativity of constants, proper interpretation will sometimes require a proper reference frame rather than simply a suitable one. Generally to be used in comparison of systems of differently scaled, but otherwise, equivalent species. In case of polarized frames, a proper [neutral] reference frame may be required even in case of systems of equal scale, to provide more accurate (objective) view of reality.

5 Quantized inflation of angular momentum

As revealed in a complementary paper[20], radius of a neutral (weakly polarized) U_1 graviton probably scales with the square root of 2^n , where n is a positive or negative integer. This can be inferred from quantization and scaling of graviton momentum.

Assuming that a graviton is inflating from a boson whose components are perpendicular to each other and equal in value to $1 \hbar$, the value of total momentum will be $\sqrt{2} \hbar$:

$$L = m v r = \sqrt{2} \hbar$$

Note that this is equivalent to the superposition of two aligned fermions whose waveforms conform to spherical harmonics:

$$L = \sqrt{l(l+1)} \hbar = \sqrt{2\frac{1}{2} \left(2\frac{1}{2} + 1\right)} \hbar = \sqrt{2} \hbar$$

However, a $1 \hbar$ momentum can also be a result of superposition of anti-aligned spin-2 and spin-1 bosons.

If that momentum is inflated with the ratio between values of constituent components of the vector conserved (non-dimensional ratios seem to be generally well preserved during inflation/deflation), proper relativistic treatment here involves either scaling of the metric or the \hbar constant. If the constant is scaled in such way that its value in the current energy level is equal in value to the momentum in adjacent lower energy level, the momentum can be expressed as:

$$L_n = \sqrt{2} \hbar_n = \sqrt{2} L_{n-1} = \sqrt{2} \left(\sqrt{2} \hbar_{n-1} \right) = \sqrt{2^n} \hbar_0 = \sqrt{2^n} \hbar_0$$

Assuming now that the speed of an non-coupled (naked) graviton is equal to the speed limit of space (c_n), that speed is relatively constant for energy levels of similar magnitude (if, however, the metric is scaled and the ratio between space and time units is conserved, the speed is locally invariant to any scale).

With the rest mass remaining invariant as well (relative 0 for a non-coupled graviton), the radius must scale the same as the momentum:

$$r_n = \sqrt{2} \left(\sqrt{2} r_{n-1} \right) = \sqrt{2^n} r_0$$

Generally, however, for this to be satisfied, it is not necessary for mass and velocity to remain conserved, rather their product (mv) - linear momentum.

Note that inflation of momentum will require additional energy apart from the rest energy of inflating quanta. However, sometimes the exchange of momentum components will result in inflation of one component and deflation of the other with no significant difference in the value of momentum. Due to low energy triggers (relative 0) such inflation/deflation (e.g., mass oscillation) should generally be inherent for all energy although it may not always be apparent due to time dilation correlated with scale (in non-scaled metric).

As even such inflation must result in some change in momentum (even if generally negligible), this type of scale inversion may also be referred to as inflation/deflation of momentum.

Note that energetic inflation/deflation generally occurs with annihilation of pairs of particles on original scale. The process can be symmetric (producing particle/anti-particle pair with equal mass) or asymmetric (producing particle/anti-particle pair with asymmetric mass distribution).

Inflation/deflation is not limited to bosons or boson pairs. Inflation of a fermion (generally paired with exchange of electro-magnetic potential for gravitational) will similarly scale the original momentum, in which case radius may not scale with $\sqrt{2}^n$. During the process, possibility may exist for some components of momentum to annihilate with others preserved (partial annihilation), producing hybrid momenta.

Note that, for a coupled system, where the imaginary mass is equal to real mass in value, the orbital Keplerian velocities are:

$$v_n = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{r_n}} = \sqrt{\frac{G}{r_n} (m_{img} + m_{re})} = \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\frac{G}{r_n} m_{img}}$$

Thus, the Keplerian velocity here can also be interpreted as the escape velocity for the coupled real mass, or the velocity required for the real mass to decouple from img mass (or, *vice versa*).

If these Keplerian velocities are quantized and scale with $\sqrt{2}^n$, escape velocity becomes equal to the Keplerian velocity of the next higher energy level of the velocity component.

$$v_e = v_{n+1} = \sqrt{2} v_n = \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\frac{GM}{r_n}} = \sqrt{2} \left(\sqrt{2} \sqrt{\frac{G}{r_n} m_{img}} \right)$$

6 Discrete states of invariance (energy levels)

The postulated self-similarity of universes implies that each universe is of a different scale - which also can be interpreted as a different dimension. This obviously requires running coupling of the dominating force, where the coupling must get stronger with decreasing scale. And this is evident in reality. Cosmological scales are dominated by the weakest force (gravity), atomic scales are dominated by a stronger force (electro-magnetism) and nuclear scales are dominated by an yet stronger force. We've been unable to *break* particles like electron, suggesting even stronger forces on smaller scales - in agreement with the postulate. Each universe is then associated with a discrete vertical energy level (scale) where energies are most stable. This is also evident in reality, e.g.,

atoms are more stable than molecules, these are more stable than larger composites, etc. To preserve this stability, transition between the vertical energy levels must require sufficiently high energies - lower energies lead to less stable *excitations*. The energy levels must also not be symmetric (from a reference frame with fixed metric), i.e., their progression must grow exponentially. Thus, these vertical energy levels are somewhat analogous to the energy levels of particles bound to atomic nuclei. One major difference is that the progression is much stronger (logarithmic) so the difference between energies is in the order of magnitude (*vertical*), rather than dominantly in the value (*horizontal*). Another salient difference is that the equivalence between a particle on one energy level and the other is very relative. And this is due to the associated running coupling and energy transformation between scales (vertical energy levels). On one vertical energy level, for example, the particle may be electrically charged with its gravitational mass being negligible, on the other energy level gravity may dominate (one type of energy is always exchanged for the other with the transition between levels). Thus, whereas simple addition or removal of energy can result in transition between horizontal energy levels, this will not result in the transition between vertical energy levels, regardless of amount - transformation must be involved, typically achieved through annihilation.

Discrete states of stability can be interpreted as discrete states of relative invariance as certain aspects of nature and mechanics of reality are preserved between levels, but not absolutely.

Energies between two vertical states are generally evolving towards the higher or lower energy level, although localized or relatively stable superposition can exist.

Note that, even in case of horizontal ones, discrete energy levels have to be relatively discrete. This can have different interpretations and multiple interpretations can be true. In example, electron energy levels in the atom are considered discrete but this does not imply that energies in between are forbidden in such way that the jumps are absolutely discrete/instantaneous, it only implies that these are unstable or unresolvable from a particular reference frame. Consider electron scattering off a mercury atom where electron energy is too low to excite the atom. This scattering cannot be absolutely elastic, but if the actual scattering cannot be directly observed it may be treated as such. Consequently, energy levels in the atom are treated as absolutely discrete. However, what is, in one interpretation, happening in reality, is that the atom is excited but since the excitation is unstable the photon is emitted and immediately absorbed by the scattering electron, in such way that the scattering looks perfectly elastic to the observer. In other words, photon involved here is of a smaller scale, unresolvable by the observer.

Is the emitted photon still absorbed by the electron in cases where the electron is travelling faster than the photon? There are interpretations in which the answer is affirmative. However, there are also interpretations

in which this may not be true, so the energy levels would appear less discrete.

The invariance of physical *laws* between energy levels is, as noted before, relative. The laws with dimensional parameters are generally not scale invariant, however, difference may be negligible or undetectable between horizontal energy levels concentrated about a particular vertical energy level. Here, thus, the laws can be treated as absolutely invariant. With incorporated running coupling or the scaling of the metric, even the discrete vertical energy levels can be treated similarly.

Given the postulates, one can formulate the discrete vertical energy levels through conservation of momentum of wave-like energy (allowing only sufficiently distant harmonics):

$$m_{(n-1)} c r_{(n-1)} = 10^{(n-1)n} \hbar$$

where n is an integer. For $n = 1$ one now obtains the reduced Compton wavelength for $r_{n-1} = r_0$, associated with mass $m_{n-1} = m_0$. Conservation of the nature of r (reduced Compton wavelength) through energy levels then implies:

$$10^{(n-1)n} m_{(n-1)} c \frac{r_{(n-1)}}{10^{(n-1)n}} = \hbar$$

from this follows:

$$m_n = 10^{(n-1)n} m_{(n-1)}$$

$$r_n = 10^{-(n-1)n} r_{(n-1)}$$

The allowed masses/wavelengths are thus solutions of the quadratic equation in the integer logarithmic metric, which, for $n > 0$ can be expressed as:

$$(n-1)n = n^2 - n = \sum_{k=1}^n 2 \times (k-1)$$

and now can be interpreted as a generalization of the Fibonacci sequence - something expectable for the postulated self-similarity.

6.1 Progression of states

Progression of discrete states of relative invariance is exponential. In example, for horizontal states of a hydrogen atom, in the top-bottom approach (energy inversely proportional to n):

$$E_n = \frac{E_1}{n^2} = E_{n-1} \left(\frac{n-1}{n} \right)^2 ; \quad n > 1, \quad E_1 = \text{const.}$$

For major vertical states (energy proportional to n):

$$\log(E_n) = \log(E_{n-1}) + (n-1)n = \log(10^{(n-1)n} E_{n-1})$$

For example, mass of the electron inflated to U₁ scale (U₁.e) can be obtained from standard electron (U₀.e) mass:

$$\log(M_N) = \log(M_e) + (n-1)n; \quad n = 8, \quad M_e = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$$

$$M_N = 10^{\log(M_e)+7 \times 8} = 0.910938356 \times 10^{26} \text{ kg}$$

Note that this equation is a slightly modified version of the equation (1.8) (derived in chapter *Definitions - Electric polarization and charge/mass exchange*). Note, however, that a simple replacement of the term (n-1)n with n would agree with the equation (1.8), and the same results could be obtained, only the values of n would be different (e.g., instead of n = 8 above, one would use n = 56).

What is very interesting is that the conversion involves the golden ratio, as from the equivalence:

$$10^{\log(M_{n-1})+(n-1)n} = 10M_{n-1} = 10^{\log(M_{n-1})+1}$$

follows:

$$(n-1)n = 1$$

$$n^2 - n - 1 = 0$$

$$n = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2} = \varphi$$

where φ is the golden ratio.

This then suggests that the equation (1.8) is a special case of the equation used above, a case where n is equal to the golden ratio. Horizontal energy levels stem from the constraints on the wavefunction (probability distribution) in QM postulates. Similarly, the existence of vertical energy levels is predicted by CR postulates, where it is clear that the progression has to be exponential. The golden ratio also stems from the postulated self-similarity of universes (scales of energy).

Note that, relative to some fixed reference frame (scale), scaling of dimensions requires for the coupling strength of dominating forces to be increasing with decreasing vertical energy level.

Note that this is on the order of mass of Neptunian planets, and very close to the actual mass of Neptune (not a coincidence, as shown in complementary paper[20]).

Mass of the equivalent particle on $n = 6$ level:

$$M_e = 10^{\log(M_{pe})+6 \times 7}$$

$$M_{pe} = 10^{\log(M_e)-6 \times 7} = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-73} \text{ kg}$$

This particle should be interpreted as U_{-1} electron ($U_{-1}.e$) and is likely to be involved in the formation of standard photons, so it may be referred to as half-photon. However, particles on this level should also be involved in the formation of standard gravitons.

Note that there are not many known candidates for such mass, but it is within the orders of mass expected for cosmological photons, and since photons mirror the source of emission (charge), it shouldn't be surprising that the electron equivalent on level $n = 6$ is involved in the formation of a photon.

Most likely, photon's rest mass is a result of annihilation of an even number of n_6 fermions (fermions occupying the vertical energy level 6). The simplest case involves a single n_6 *electron/positron* pair, which, with energy conserved and single photon production (assuming recoil momentum is absorbed by a 3rd body - such as the atomic nucleus, or, its equivalent on n_6) gives for the photon rest mass:

$$M_p = 1.821876712 \times 10^{-72} \text{ kg}$$

Note that this is in agreement with the previously obtained upper limit on photon mass in lowest mass eigenstate, 8×10^{-70} kg (chapter *Graviton in Definitions*).

Now, since the equation for vertical energy levels is the same for particles of different mass and the electron can exist in 3 mass eigenstates (e, muon, tau), obviously, the photon should have 3 mass eigenstates as well, and the ratios between these eigenstates should be equal to the ratios between standard tau, muon and e eigenstates.

Note also that, while single-photon production is rare in annihilation of standard particles (n_7 particles) - just as the annihilation itself, any kind of photon production probably involves annihilation of n_6 pairs (whether it involves n_7 annihilation or not).

I hypothesize that the Solar System is the equivalent of a Carbon-10 (^{10}C) atom. It has been inflated from $U_0.^{10}\text{C}$ state (or even $U_{-1}.^{10}\text{C}$) and

electro-magnetic potential has been exchanged for gravitational in the process. Some evidence for this is presented here, but major evidence is in follow-up/complementary works (mostly in the Solar System analysis). Of course, the values obtained above will deviate slightly from current values due to required oscillation (significant time dilation of oscillation on large scale) and the fact that energy of the outermost electron in Carbon-10 (corresponding to Neptune) slightly differs from the free electron energy used above.

Note that the levels calculated above are considered major vertical energy levels, but there are smaller ones. In example, lepton mass oscillation can be considered as oscillation between minor discrete vertical energy levels, or sublevels.

Note also that mass is relative - it may be localized to a particle but it may be spread in a wave-form where it can be considered as 0 relative to space (exchange between mass and frequency).

In effect, Neptune is a [vertically] excited standard electron, and standard electron is the excited U_{-1} [scale] electron.

Here too, it is obvious that the difference in strength between electric and gravitational force between two electrons stems from the difference in rest mass between the standard electron and standard photon-forming (or standard graviton-forming) U_{-1} electron/positron - 42 (6×7) orders of magnitude. With a change in vertical energy level, nature of the force evolves. In the transition from $n = 7$ to $n = 8$ electro-magnetic potential is exchanged for neutral gravitational potential. Transition from $n = 6$ to $n = 7$, however, may involve a different exchange. Assuming M_{p_e} particle is a fermion, a likely possibility is the exchange between the Yukawa coupling to Higgs field and some other coupling. Different interpretations of this exchange are possible. One possibility is that on the level (scale) $n = 6$, the strength of gravitational and electro-magnetic coupling is equal, but with the inflation to $n = 7$, the strength of gravitational coupling is exchanged for the stronger coupling to the Higgs field (effectively implying the conservation of the GM product between the scales - inflating mass, deflating G).

Note the following:

$$M_{p_e} = \frac{M_e}{M_N} K_A = \frac{M_e}{M_N} 1.02413 \times 10^{-16} \text{ kg}$$

where $M_N = 1.02413 \times 10^{26}$ kg is the mass of Neptune, and quantum of mass $K_A = 1.02413 \times 10^{-16}$ kg (5.7×10^{19} eV = 57 EeV) is the mass (energy) of asymmetry.

If standard electron mass would be equal to the current value of K_A and half-photon would have mass equal to 1.02413×10^{-58} kg, the adjacent electron energy levels to U_0 would be symmetric relative to the electron.

Symmetry could also be achieved simply by decreasing half-photon mass to 8.1×10^{-87} kg (setting $K_A = M_e = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31}$ kg).

If vertical asymmetry needs to be preserved, the asymmetry breaking energy of $K_A - M_e \approx K_A = 5.7 \times 10^{19}$ eV must be the energy limit for standard particles produced in any universe conforming to the above progression of vertical states as that energy could, through annihilation, inflate electron mass to K_A .

Note that symmetry by decrease of half-photon mass requires considerably more energy - 8.9×10^{-15} kg (4.99×10^{21} eV = 4988 EeV).

At first, it might seem unclear why would it be necessary to preserve vertical asymmetry, but the reason is equivalent to the reason for preservation of horizontal asymmetry.

Particles with mutually inverted properties annihilate when distance between them is reduced to relative 0. Whether this annihilation occurs within the atom or outside the atom, it has to occur at a particular energy level. This thus requires symmetry relative to that level. Since adjacent vertical energy levels have inverted properties, symmetry could lead to annihilation of adjacent energy levels.

Different scales (universes) are entangled (correlated) and if this entanglement is physical (in CR, it has to be - in some reference frames) than that entanglement can be interpreted as a dimension in space.

If correlated but anti-aligned properties are universally attracted and relatively annihilated when at equal distance from a particular energy level, conservation of existence requires conservation of asymmetry in scale.

Note that energy levels are physical. In case of electro-magnetic energy, magnetic field tubes can be interpreted as energy levels. Splitting of energy levels can then be interpreted as splitting of magnetic field tubes, although alternative interpretations are possible.

Creation of symmetry would require adjustment of half-photon mass in either case, therefore the lower energy limit of 5.7×10^{19} eV may be interpreted as the 2nd order limit, with the 1st order being the obtained larger value, 4.99×10^{21} eV.

Studies indeed confirm the 2nd order limit as the cut-off energy[30] for intra-galactic sources[31].

It is also in agreement with measurements of GZK (Greisen-Zatsepin-Kuzmin) energy limit (cut-off) for protons - $5.6 \pm 0.5 \pm 0.9 \times 10^{19}$ eV[32] (uncertainties are

statistical and systematic, respectively).

Interestingly, particles with higher energy have been detected, on the order of 10^{20} eV, but no particle has been produced or observed exceeding the 1st order limit.

Effectively, thus, a relative superposition of the 1st and 2nd order may be interpreted as the real limit.

In any case, the existence of these limits is a strong evidence for the proposed progression of vertical energy levels, and increasing number of particles with such high energies could indicate instability of the observable universe. Rest masses of gravitons are quantized and will be different on different energy levels. Knowing rest mass on one level, masses on other levels can be determined from the equation. However, note that the equation preserves the scale-invariance of non-dimensional mass ratios as well. Therefore, knowing one mass, other masses on a certain level can be determined through known mass ratios on another level.

In example, one possible rest mass of an U_{-1} scale particle can be deduced from the ratio of an carbon isotope and electron mass:

$$\begin{aligned} M_n &= \frac{{}^{10}\text{C atom mass}}{\text{electron mass}} M_{pe} \approx \frac{10.016853 u}{M_e} M_{pe} \\ &= 1.663337576 \times 10^{-68} \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

Stability of these complex forms is questionable. However, assuming simple products of annihilation of $n = 6$ particles are stable, taking into account 3 different mass eigenstates for electron, stable rest masses here should range between $\sim 10^{-72}$ kg and $\sim 10^{-69}$ kg.

Note that this is in agreement with calculations of standard graviton mass ($\sim 10^{-68}$ kg[33], $\sim 10^{-69}$ kg[34]), based on existing theories and observations.

What about dark matter? Assuming dark matter is formed by naked gravitons, it is those associated with unstable particles that are most likely to be naked. Naked gravitons of U_{-1} scale inflated to U_0 scale, assuming they remain uncoupled, will form the dark matter of U_0 scale.

Assuming naked graviton mass of an U_{-1} particle is half the total mass and that dark matter is formed by the inflation through annihilation of pairs of such naked gravitons, on average, the U_0 dark matter particles may just have a mass that is equal to the mass of the standard ${}^{10}\text{C}$ ($1.663337576 \times 10^{-26}$ kg).

The mass corresponds to the energy of 9.33×10^9 eV (9.33 GeV) and solid evidence indeed exists in favour of such dark matter particles in the Milky Way[35].

What is interesting here is, as the evidence in the complementary paper[20] suggests, the Solar System itself is a result of inflation of an U_0 . ${}^{10}\text{C}$ system (or a similar system with 10 nucleons). The average mass of stars in the Milky Way, however, is estimated to lie somewhere between 0.10 and 0.25 M_\odot (for the number of stars between 200 billion and

500 billion, and total mass in stars of $5.04 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$). Assuming now that the average mass should be equal to $1 M_{\odot}$ ($U_1^{10}C$) if all the energy available in dark matter (naked U_0 gravitons) would be used up, the amount of dark matter in the Milky Way should be roughly 75-90 % of total mass (minus the amount of interstellar gas/dust used in star formation). This is in remarkable agreement with latest measurements, where the total mass has been estimated at $2.06^{-0.13/+0.24} \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$, with a strict unsurpassable upper limit of $5.4 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ [36]. Given the total mass in stars of $5.04^{-0.52/+0.43} \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ [37], this translates to 75-90 % for dark matter (without interstellar gas/dust taken into account). But is the stellar mass 100% real (standard) mass? If stable vertical energy levels are occupied by particles and each particle is associated with a graviton, then a significant part of mass in stars should be in large scale gravitons. Per the evidence in the complementary work[20], the formation of planetary systems starts with the inflation of gravitons to large scale. A naked large scale graviton (which now can be interpreted as large scale dark matter particle) forms a gravitational well that will attract the standard (U_0 scale) matter in the form of dust and gas. The available dust and gas in the interstellar medium of the Milky Way is roughly $1.2 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ [37], or 6% of the total mass. Thus, if the remaining dark matter would be inflated to form large scale gravitons of future stars, only ~6% of the total star mass could be in the form of standard matter. It is thus possible that even the standard mass in the existing stars does not exceed ~6% on average. If the dark mass in stars is stable - does not convert to standard matter/radiation, the available amount of fusion fuel in stars in the Milky Way may be significantly overestimated. Indeed, in the complementary work, I have calculated that the excess mass (beyond the expected rest mass) in the Sun is exactly 6%[20]. Now this 6% excess is not evidence but it is very suggestive. Rather than a coincidence, this may rather be a consequence of enforcement of self-similarity. Stars could thus be mirroring the galaxy - on average having ~6% of mass in standard matter and the rest in dark matter. However, significant deviations from the average are possible. The percentage is probably inversely proportional to scale, being higher in smaller stars (solar winds seem to generally be more frequent and stronger in smaller stars, which may be a consequence of higher standard matter enrichment). At some scale the ratio should be inverted and standard matter should dominate, and this, on average, probably is the case in rocky planets, for example. If stars contain significant amounts of dark matter then one must consider a possibility that the ratios do not differ much between galaxies of similar energy - galaxies that apparently do not contain dark matter could simply represent galaxies at "full capacity", where all of the dark matter is "used up", being contained within stars and black holes.

Although certain rest mass could dominate in a galaxy, there is no single dark matter particle, however. Any naked graviton may be interpreted as a particle of dark matter.

Note also that [rest] masses of standard photons and neutrinos may generally be determined from momentum, relative to the c constant.

Masses obtained here are invariant to c . Physically, a particle of obtained [half-]photon mass ($\sim 10^{-72}$ kg) can be produced, for example, with the collapse of a gravitational maximum (graviton) of U_0 Neptune equivalent (standard electron) to the U_{-1} level. Assuming the resulting [half-]photon or half-graviton has vacuum energy density (9.9×10^{-27} kg/m³), and a radius of U_0 scale Neptune equivalent ($\approx 3.8 \times 10^{-16}$ m), with momentum conserved, its orbital velocity would be $\approx 3.5 \times 10^{26}$ m/s[38] (with assumed initial U_0 velocity of $\approx 5.6 \times 10^5$ m/s). CR allows such speeds for smaller scales of energy/radii, however - depending on particle interpretation, this is not necessarily incompatible with GR.

This speed would be valid in GR assuming it is achieved with the transformation of most of the energy into a warp bubble. Initially, the bubble wall thickness is relatively infinitesimal. With produced acceleration, the wall is expanding and the process stops once the wall thickness reaches $\approx 3.8 \times 10^{-16}$ m and its energy density becomes equal to vacuum energy density (initially, the density is lower = negative). What's left is a region of effectively flat space orbiting at the speed of $\approx 3.5 \times 10^{26}$ m/s. After all, the energy of U_0 particles is sufficient to create a warp bubble of that size - assuming spherically symmetric bubble with a radius equal to the upper limit for standard electron's radius (1×10^{-22} m), integrating the Alcubierre stress-energy tensor[39], keeping only leading-order scaling with bubble radius and wall thickness, one obtains:

$$M_{bubble} \sim \frac{c^2}{G} R^2 \sigma = 5.12 \times 10^{-33} \text{ kg}$$

$$c = \text{standard speed of light} = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$$

$$G = \text{standard gravitational constant} = 6.674 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3\text{kg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2}$$

$$R = \text{radius of the bubble} = 1 \times 10^{-22} \text{ m}$$

$$\sigma = \text{thickness of the bubble wall} = 3.8 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}$$

With initial velocity of $\approx 5.6 \times 10^5$ m/s, and momentum conserved during transformation, the end velocity becomes $\approx 3.5 \times 10^{26}$ m.

Thus, while CR predicts that speed limits on smaller scales exceed the standard speed of light, this is not necessarily incompatible with GR, although running couplings - predicted by CR, may be required to preserve the classical momentum conservation. And there is a reason to believe that momentum is classically conserved - see below.

Rest photon mass relative to standard c can then be obtained through conservation of momentum ($p=m_1v=m_2c$), and it is:

$$m_2 = \frac{m_1 v}{c} = 2.1 \times 10^{-54} \text{ kg}$$

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 &= \text{photon rest mass} = 1.8 \times 10^{-72} \text{ kg} \\ v &= \text{photon velocity on } U_{-1} \text{ scale} = 3.5 \times 10^{26} \text{ m/s} \\ c &= \text{standard speed of light} = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s} \end{aligned}$$

This mass agrees with experimentally obtained photon mass through its interaction with matter (localization)[40]. Since the localized photon represents detectable photon mass, the previously obtained mass of lower scale may be interpreted as virtual photon mass.

Interestingly, if one multiplies the obtained $2.1 \times 10^{-54} \text{ kg}$ with $1 \times 10^{56} \text{ kg}^{-1}$ (equal to the ratio between the above calculated U_1 (Neptune) electron mass and standard (U_0) electron mass), and then multiplies with electron mass, one obtains a mass of $1.9 \times 10^{-28} \text{ kg}$, which is the mass of a standard muon [electron]. This suggests that Neptune should be interpreted as a localized large scale muon, rather than a localized large scale electron. Indeed, this has turned out to be the most likely interpretation in the complementary paper[20].

Muon may be the most stable (or at least most common) eigenstate on U_1 scale, in which case one could argue that on that scale muon has a role of the electron, relatively. Note, however, that conditions change over time. Prior to settling to electron eigenstate, the most stable eigenstate on the standard (U_0) scale may have been muon as well, and possibly tau before that (which shouldn't be surprising for the early universe). The most common planets in the observable universe seem to be those with mass between the masses of Earth and Neptune, which then suggests that even on U_1 scale, there is a transition towards the smaller mass eigenstate (electron equivalent). This shouldn't be surprising either, considering self-similarity between scales and the expansion of the universe. Time on larger scale is dilated from the equivalent reference frame on smaller scale so the transition to the lowest mass eigenstate lags behind.

The obtained photon rest mass of $1.821876712 \times 10^{-72} \text{ kg}$ may also be validated through conservation of energy. In CR, relativistic speed limits are different between different scales of energy.

For standard protons and electrons, speed limit is the standard *speed of light* (c), however, for particles with the rest mass on $n = 6$ level, speed limit must be much higher. But speed limits also depend on confinement - scale entanglement. The reason one does not directly observe photons travelling at greater speeds is because of the large interaction scale (quantum entanglement between distant particles, however, could be interpreted as indirect observation

of superluminal carriers, although this could also be interpreted as the stretching of [the units of] space). In other words, since the creation of a standard photon involves inflation and entanglement with a scale larger than U_{-1} (generally U_0) it is *instantly slowed down* to the U_0 speed limit (c). Validation of the calculated photon/graviton masses and velocities can be found in the analysis of the Solar System in CR context[20] (chapter *Quantum nature: Outermost angular momenta and c_1 confirmation*) and other follow-up papers[41], but also here in some of the following chapters.

6.1.1 Sub-major levels

Major discrete vertical energy levels of scales U_{-1} , U_0 , and U_1 are entangled with sub-major discrete vertical energy levels (mass eigenstates) on these scales (although the ratios between masses are not the same).

In example, the masses of standard electron, muon and tau particles represent 3 such eigenstates on U_0 scale. But this is not limited to these. All particles can (regardless of a major vertical energy level they're in) oscillate in mass and with the same ratio between masses as is the case with the aforementioned leptons. However, entanglements can change with time and it is possible, for example, that different ratios are valid for quarks on the standard scale, although, as hinted here before (chapter 4.25. *Electric polarization and charge/mass exchange*), explained in the previous chapter, and as the complementary work shows - quark equivalents on U_1 scale most likely can settle in mass eigenstates with the same ratios as in the case of the 3 leptons[20]. Thus, it seems that these ratios are indeed invariant to particle species. And since the ratios are non-dimensional, preservation for *equivalent* particles across major vertical energy levels shouldn't be surprising either (e.g., the ratios of mass between electron, muon and tau eigenstates is the same on U_1 scale as it is on U_0 scale, a conclusion that stems from the hypothesized progression of states anyway).

I will thus generally refer to the 3 states as e, muon and tau states, regardless of the particle species. E.g., U_{-1} .e.photon should be interpreted as the e mass eigenstate of a photon localized to U_{-1} scale, while U_0 .e.electron should be interpreted as the e eigenstate of the electron localized to U_0 scale. This state, however, may be abbreviated as U_0 .electron. It is unfortunate that in QM the same word ("electron") is used both for the eigenstate and the particle, but this is a legacy from QM where these eigenstate ratios are considered exclusive to electron. Note also that "e" may be interpreted as electron charge in some contexts. Note also that more confusion is produced when considering neutrinos. The 3 standard neutrinos are named electron, muon and tau neutrino. However, in CR context, these names are inappropriate as the masses between them are negligible - the ratios are not the same as the ratios

between the masses of electron, muon and tau particles (which are all considered to be *electrons* in different sub-major vertical energy levels). Thus, per CR, each of the 3 standard neutrinos can be vertically excited into e, muon and tau eigenstates (with the same mass ratios as the mass ratios between electron, muon and tau particles), but they themselves, albeit similar, are 3 different particles.

In conclusion, the 3 mass eigenstates (e, muon, tau) represent more general or more fundamental eigenstates in CR, and, in contrast to standard QM interpretation, the 3 standard neutrinos are interpreted as 3 different particles, while electron, muon and tau particles are the *same* particle in different vertical energy levels.

Note that, while the transition between major vertical energy levels generally involves changes in the dominance of forces, in case of sub-major or minor vertical levels this does not have to be the case. In example, electro-magnetic force still dominates between standard electron, muon and tau particles, although the strength of gravitational and Higgs interactions does increase with the increase in energy level.

Apart from e/muon/tau eigenstates, however, other eigenstates may be available for some particles. In any case, all components of atoms, photons and all other particles can oscillate or fluctuate in mass (again, a caveat - this is not the QM flavour/mass oscillation, rather oscillation through vertical energy levels), with expected ratios between masses (e/muon/tau eigenstates), being:

$$\frac{m_\mu}{m_e} = \frac{M_\mu}{M_e} = 206.768$$

$$\frac{m_\tau}{m_e} = \frac{M_\tau}{M_e} = 3477.22$$

$$\begin{aligned} M_\tau &= \text{standard tau electron mass} = 1776.86 \text{ MeV}/c^2 \\ M_\mu &= \text{standard muon electron mass} = 105.6583755 \text{ MeV}/c^2 \\ M_e &= \text{standard electron mass} = 0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2 \end{aligned}$$

where m_e represents lowest mass eigenstate, m_τ represents highest mass eigenstate, while m_μ is the intermediate mass eigenstate.

Are components of general force (electro-magnetic, gravitational) exchanged, to some degree, even with oscillation between sub-major levels as well? Possibly, but this may not be observable.

The entanglement between major and sub-major levels becomes obvious from the following equation:

$$\frac{m_\mu}{m_e} = \frac{M_{\gamma\mu}}{M_{\gamma e}} = 206.768$$

where $M_{\gamma\mu}$ is the photon rest mass localized to U_0 scale ($\sim 2.1 \times 10^{-54}$ kg, as calculated previously (and obtained experimentally)). If that mass is interpreted

as muon photon mass, the M_{γ_e} is the e photon rest mass when localized to U_0 scale and must be equal to $\sim 1 \times 10^{-56}$ kg. Now, the order of this mass (56) is apparently equal to the order of the ratio between calculated e mass eigenstates on U_1 scale and U_0 scale. Thus, mass of the U_1 e eigenstate can be obtained by multiplying U_0 .electron mass with the inversion of U_0 .e.photon mass (which can be interpreted as mass inflation):

$$M_{e1} = \frac{M_{e0}}{M_{\gamma_{e0}}} M_{\gamma_{e1}} = \frac{M_e}{M_{\gamma_e}} M_{\gamma_{e1}} = 0.910938356 \times 10^{26} \text{ kg}$$

where $M_{\gamma_{e1}}$ is the U_1 .e.photon mass eigenstate and is here assumed to be equal to 1 kg. It is however, possible that the obtained photon mass of 2.1×10^{-54} kg is not the muon eigenstate, rather e eigenstate, in which case U_1 .e.photon mass should be smaller. Assuming that the obtained U_1 mass represents a muon eigenstate (as noted already, this is more likely, according to the complementary paper[20]), U_1 .e.photon mass should indeed be smaller. This suggests that the equation used to obtain major eigenstates is incomplete - assuming it should relate the same eigenstates between scales. But should it? As noted before, at least in some contexts, the equivalent U_0 .electron on U_1 scale may be the U_1 .muon. In other words, the equation relates, or determines, dominant eigenstates - on U_0 scale e eigenstate is dominant or most stable, on U_1 scale it should be the muon eigenstate (at least when averaged over the appropriate timescale).

6.1.2 Propagation and oscillation of photon mass

Masses of all particles (or, more precisely, production of all particles) should be oscillating or fluctuating between sub-major vertical levels and photon cannot be an exception. The particles that [annihilate to] form the photon's rest mass (half-photons) should, also oscillate between 3 generations.

Assuming calculated mass is the lowest mass, remaining two values can be calculated from tau/muon/electron mass ratios, as established previously.

For $M_\tau = 1776.86 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, $M_\mu = 105.6583755 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ and $M_e = 0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$:

$$M_{\gamma\tau} = \frac{M_\tau}{M_e} M_{\gamma_e} = \frac{1}{2} 6.335068208 \times 10^{-69} \text{ kg}$$

$$M_{\gamma\mu} = \frac{M_\mu}{M_e} M_{\gamma_e} = \frac{1}{2} 3.767055455 \times 10^{-70} \text{ kg}$$

$$M_{\gamma_e} = \frac{M_p}{2} = \frac{1}{2} 1.821876712 \times 10^{-72} \text{ kg}$$

M_{γ_e} = electron half-photon *rest* mass

$M_{\gamma\mu}$ = muon half-photon *rest* mass

$M_{\gamma\tau}$ = tau half-photon *rest* mass

Note that these values are in agreement with the photon mass calculated by others. E.g., in one study, Alencar et al. have obtained, with the assumption of dS vacuum and a Ricci scalar of 4Λ (where Λ is a positive cosmological constant), a cosmological photon mass (mass of the photon propagating in the cosmological vacuum) of $\approx 2 \times 10^{-69}$ kg[42]. If one instead calculates the mass using matter density and pressure of the Solar System (Sun magnetosphere) in the Ricci scalar and a zero cosmological constant, one obtains photon mass $\approx 2 \times 10^{-72}$ kg[42]. Note also that there must exist a threshold frequency - at which point two half-photons are more likely to annihilate into a graviton half-particle instead of annihilating into a photon.

Due to non-zero mass, photon must have a range, at least roughly equal to [reduced] Compton wavelength, e.g., in case of tau/muon combination of half-photons (assuming such combination is possible):

$$r = \frac{\hbar}{M_p c} = \frac{\hbar}{c} \frac{1}{M_{\gamma\tau} + M_{\gamma\mu}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hbar &= h/(2\pi) = 1.054573 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js} \\ c &= 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s} \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, r must also be roughly equal to the radius of the observable universe (universe that can be observed by standard photons).

Photon frequency will change with changes in gravitational potential. However, beyond the conventional frequency shift stemming from GR, I propose that, due to its mode of propagation (expanding spherical wavefront) and non-zero rest mass the photon may experience a frequency drift due to coupling to positive and negative pressure of the mass-energy enclosed by the wavefront (per the shell theorem, the mass outside of the sphere, with its homogeneous and isotropic distribution, would have no net effect on the photon). Here, the photon's rest mass is assumed to be isotropically distributed over the spherical shell (either over the whole sphere or concentrated in a ring, depending on coupling interpretation - as explained further below). If the coupling to positive pressure is balanced with the coupling to negative pressure there is no frequency drift, otherwise photon's frequency may be blueshifted or redshifted, depending on the dominant pressure. The frequency drift is here interpreted to be a consequence of acceleration, however, the photon is not locally changing velocity, rather its trajectory is being curved. With dominant positive pressure its linear momentum is converting to angular momentum, and, upon reaching its range, photon's linear (radial) velocity becomes equal to zero (completely exchanged for angular velocity). Effectively, thus, the photon is experiencing constant negative radial acceleration.

How to interpret the constant acceleration?

One possibility is the running gravitational coupling (note that the photon is changing scale during propagation). E.g., with G proportional to $1/r$ and M proportional to r^3 , the acceleration becomes constant, effectively independent of r . One explanation for this is the dependence of dimensionality of gravitational coupling on the dimensionality of coupling bodies. The photon is 2-dimensional (spherical surface), while the enclosed mass is 3-dimensional, resulting in the $1/r$ ratio. For localized particles/bodies the ratio is $1/1$. Note, however, that this implies asymmetry in coupling - the force from the photon acting on the enclosed mass would have a G proportional to r , not $1/r$. While I wouldn't rule out the asymmetry (the CR allows it, and the asymmetry is obvious in more complex forces - one person, for example, can be attracted by another, but at the same time the latter may be repelled by the former), another explanation is possible. Suppose that photon's rest mass is concentrated in a ring on the spherical wavefront. In that case, the enclosed mass grows with r^2 and the acceleration remains constant. Some might prefer this explanation as it doesn't require a running G (under the assumption of constant density):

$$a = \frac{GM}{r^2} = G \frac{r^2 \pi \rho}{r^2} = G \pi \rho$$

Assuming invariant G , obviously the range, and thus the coupling rest mass, depend on the enclosed mass-energy density. The question is, however, is the rest mass changing dynamically - as the density is constant only on larger scales? Here, angular momentum would be conserved (as increase in rest mass is equal to decrease in range), but energy conservation would imply exchange of energy with the traversing medium. Alternative solution is the dependence of rest mass on initial conditions (at the point of emission) only, with either a dynamic acceleration on smaller scales or a changing coupling strength (with changing density) to conserve the fixed acceleration across all scales.

Instead of the ring-like form of photon rest mass, however, the same effect (proportionality of mass to r^2) can be produced assuming the acceleration depends on the mass traversed by the wavefront, rather than the mass enclosed by it.

Note, however, that, even if G is invariant here, it is not equal to the Newton's gravitational constant, as the coupling strength at the start of propagation must be significantly higher to produce the observed acceleration. Limiting the G to the Newton's gravitational constant, the correct order of acceleration can only be produced from the gravitational acceleration of the total mass enclosed by the radius of the observable universe (or, more precisely, by the particle range). In that case, one would have to accept the notion that the photon is, upfront, *aware* of

the total mass within its range and is reacting to that mass from the start. While the coupling rest mass/range is known upfront, it is not intuitively easy to correlate the total enclosed mass within the range with the conditions at the point of emission. Thus, the photon is probably reacting to the density of enclosed or traversed mass-energy at its current radius, with the strength of coupling changing in such way to ensure a radial acceleration that conserves the mass-range relation - or to ensure that the range is effectively a Schwarzschild radius.

This acceleration is the equivalent of inverse free fall, and on a return trip (assuming the photon is not absorbed and falls back upon reaching the range) it would be equivalent to free fall. Thus, for the coupling rest mass equal to $M_{\gamma\tau} + M_{\gamma\mu}$, the acceleration is:

$$a = \pm \frac{1}{2} c^2 \frac{c}{\hbar} (M_{\gamma\tau} + M_{\gamma\mu}) = \pm \frac{1}{2} \frac{c^3}{\hbar} (M_{\gamma\tau} + M_{\gamma\mu}) = \pm 4.287091748 \times 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2}$$

For $2M_{\gamma e}$:

$$a = \pm \frac{1}{2} \frac{c^3}{\hbar} 2M_{\gamma e} = \pm \frac{c^3}{\hbar} M_{\gamma e} = \pm 2.327418326 \times 10^{-13} \frac{m}{s^2}$$

Generally, taking into account phase shift between mass eigenstates of half-photons and using relativistic mass, the equation becomes:

$$a = \pm \frac{1}{2} \frac{c^3}{\hbar} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 \phi \right) \Delta M \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{f^2}{f_n^2}}}$$

$$\Delta M^2 = 2^2 \frac{M_1^2 + M_2^2}{2} = 2 (M_1^2 + M_2^2)$$

where ΔM is the superposition of mass, f is photon spin frequency, f_n is the maximum possible photon spin frequency and ϕ is the mixing angle (equal to 90° for aligned and 0° for anti-aligned oscillation of half-photons). For the previously determined 2nd order maximum energy of $M_n = 1.02413 \times 10^{-16}$ kg (5.7×10^{19} eV), f_n is:

$$f_n = \frac{c}{\lambda_n} = \frac{E_n}{h} = \frac{M_n c^2}{h} = 1.389120683 \times 10^{34} \text{ Hz}$$

Note that this energy/frequency is also roughly the energy/frequency required for the creation of the heaviest known standard elementary particle pair[43] (top/anti-top quark pair), potentially explaining why these

are the heaviest known elementary particles.

Note also that, in conventional interpretations, the expanding waveform is usually not considered a real object rather simply a wave of probability, or a field spreading, but that, again, is a consequence of excessive reductionism in interpretation - or, more precisely, lack of proper interpretation of the wave-function. In CR, however, the wave-function describes a physical phenomenon - the spherical waveform is indeed a spread out photon, which collapses to a *point* with localization.

Furthermore, in conventional quantum physics only the basis mass eigenstates are considered real. In CR, this is relative. The basis mass eigenstates are simply the most stable. On the standard scale (U_0) the intermediate states are extremely unstable (from our perspective at least). On U_1 scale, however, they are obviously relatively stable (from our perspective, their stability can be on the order of millions or billions of years). The intermediate states are probably stable on the scale of photon mass (U_{-1}) as well, but if not, the mixing angle of 90° should be used.

In any case, the *perturbation* model (additional non-dimensional terms) used here may not be the most appropriate, experiments should constrain these.

Also note that the effect is effectively invariant to frequency, as realistic frequencies are much lower than the maximum. But there is another reason why the frequency has no significant effect.

The rest mass here is associated with gravitational coupling, although it has the same value as assumed photon's rest mass, it should be associated with a standard graviton instead. The acceleration thus stems from the photon coupling to the standard gravitons and it becomes questionable whether the dependency on frequency here exists at all.

However, photon's interaction scale is proportional to wavelength and if photon has a non-zero rest mass it will travel slower than c , so a relativistic effect on its energy should exist, and it will affect the acceleration - justifying the inclusion of the relativistic term in the equation.

Calculated acceleration for various combinations and $f \ll f_n$ is shown in Table 4. Acceleration of photons may be misinterpreted as a change in velocity (Doppler shift) of the source of emission when the photons are emitted from a moving source and the coupling carrier rest mass is assumed to be 0, while the real reason of the change is the changing curvature of photon paths. Indeed, analysis of motion of Pioneer 10/11, Galileo, and Ulysses spacecraft shows anomalous relatively constant weak long-range acceleration of $\sim - (8 \pm 3) \times 10^{-10}$ m/s² (deceleration relative to the Sun) for which no satisfactory explanation has been found[44]. A solution has been proposed in the form of anisotropic thermal radiation[45] and it has been even claimed that this can completely resolve the Pioneer anomaly[46]. However, these results are questionable. The original

M ₁	M ₂	φ [°]	a [m/s ²]
M _{γμ}	M _{γμ}	90	±0.481235302 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
M _{γμ}	M _{γμ}	0	±0.240617651 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
M _{γτ}	M _{γμ}	90	±5.732686887 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
M _{γτ}	M _{γμ}	0	±2.866343444 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
M _{γτ}	M _{γτ}	90	±8.092948194 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
M _{γτ}	M _{γτ}	0	±4.046474097 × 10 ⁻¹⁰

Table 4: Acceleration for various cosmological photon mass eigenstates

thermal modelling (which may be correct after all) ruled out thermal recoil as the explanation[47]. While the thermal dissipation could have a role, there are certain properties of these anomalies that cannot be explained by anisotropic thermal radiation. One is the observed annual periodicity[47], and the other is the apparent onset of the anomaly[48] only once the giant planets have been reached[49] (or, once the spacecraft transition to a hyperbolic trajectory, decoupling from the Solar System).

Obviously, predicted enclosure of the gravitational potential by photons can fully explain this anomaly. The onset of the anomaly at the distance of giant planets can easily be explained with mass oscillation and/or changes in coupling between positive and negative pressure (where imbalance causes the onset). The annual periodicity can be explained by the motion of the Earth about the Sun - as this is the place of absorption, the radius of the absorbed photon will oscillate annually. However, if the anomaly results from photons coupling to space-forming gravitons, coupling mass may be, more likely, a superposition of 2 mass eigenstates.

There are two interpretations of this. One is that the graviton rest mass is double the photon's rest mass - which does make sense if the standard graviton is a product of annihilation of two photons or 4 half-photons (half-gravitons), or even more pairs - as long the resulting total spin is 2. Spin 0 cannot be ruled out either, however, in that case this is not GR-like gravitational coupling, rather a dipolar gravitational (or gravitational-like) Yukawa coupling.

In another interpretation, the coupling actually depends on photon's rest mass, and 2 photons in superposition may be required for the coupling. The number of photons in superposition may depend on the spin momenta distribution of photons. In circularly polarized emission all photons have the same spin projection (helicity) on the direction of propagation. Thus, two photons in superposition would have a spin projection of $2\hbar$, equal to the standard graviton (carrier of gravitational force) helicity. In conventional quantum physics total photon helicity must match the graviton helicity so two photons (with equal helicity) are required

for coupling to a single standard graviton. Conventionally, thus, a single photon can't couple to real standard gravitons, but it is assumed to be coupling to standard virtual gravitons. In CR, this coupling could be interpreted as a coupling to a half-graviton.

Anomalies have been detected in other spacecraft. Table 5 shows the anomalies and calculated accelerations for matching two-mass-eigenstate configurations (half-photon or half-graviton source particles). Evidently, calculations

spacecraft	distance [AU]	anomaly [m/s ²]	possible two-photon configurations [M ₁ , M ₂ , φ]	calculated acceleration [m/s ²]
Pioneer 10 (<1999)	40-60	8.09±0.20 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	2 × [M _{γτ} , M _{γτ} , 0°]	8.092948194 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
Pioneer 11 (<1999)	<30	8.56±0.15 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	[M _{γτ} , M _{γτ} , 90°] + [M _{γμ} , M _{γμ} , 90°]	8.574183496 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
Ulysses (1992-1995)	1.3 - 5.2	12±3 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	[M _{γτ} , M _{γτ} , 90°] + [M _{γτ} , M _{γμ} , 0°]	12.139422291 × 10 ⁻¹⁰ 13.825635081 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
Galileo (1993)	~3	8±3 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	[M _{γτ} , M _{γτ} , 90°] + [M _{γτ} , M _{γμ} , 90°]	8.092948194 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
Pioneer 10 (2003)	82	8.74±1.33 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	2 × [M _{γτ} , M _{γτ} , 0°]	8.092948194 × 10 ⁻¹⁰ 8.574183496 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
New Horizons (2008)	8	13.2±0.6 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	[M _{γμ} , M _{γμ} , 90°] + [M _{γτ} , M _{γτ} , 90°]	13.825635081 × 10 ⁻¹⁰

Table 5: Anomalies and proposed solutions (anomaly data sources: a⁴⁴, b⁵⁰)

done using the predicted masses are in remarkable agreement with observations.

Interestingly, the results suggest that in all solutions masses should be equally aligned (both either 0°, or 90°). This would then imply that Ulysses anomaly is the same in value to New Horizons anomaly.

Generally, any spherically expanding wave-like energy quantum with finite range (rest mass > 0) should be converting radial component of velocity to angular orbital velocity with distance as long as the coupling to the enclosed positive pressure is higher than the coupling to negative pressure. The coupling to negative pressure, however, is considered in a separate paper, providing explanation not only for the anomalies of deep space probes but also for the Hubble tension and potentially other cosmological anomalies.

Alternative model The previously used equation for acceleration provides good results, but the specific model of perturbation is questionable. It has been hypothesized that acceleration depends on the mass enclosed or traversed by

the wavefront, and this mass depends on the distribution of interacting (rest) photon mass on the spherical wavefront (plus, the rest mass eigenstate itself should depend on the mass-energy density). Interpreting then the modification as the effect of specific distribution of mass on the spherical waveform, the following form of the equation should be more appropriate:

$$a = \pm \frac{1}{2} \frac{c^3}{\hbar} 2 \sin \phi M$$

$$M^2 = M_1^2 + M_2^2$$

where φ is the angle associated with mass distribution ($90^\circ =$ spherically isotropic distribution).

With this, however, the same or very similar results can be obtained. For example, if masses M_1 and M_2 are interpreted as half-photon masses, a combination of $\tau/\tau/45^\circ$ with $\tau/\mu/45^\circ$ (or $\tau/\tau/30^\circ$) produces $13.82 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m/s}^2$, similar to the previous combination of $\tau/\tau/90^\circ$ with $\tau/\mu/90^\circ$. If the two masses are interpreted as photon masses, a τ photon mass with a τ - μ (a sum of τ and μ half-photon masses) photon mass, and the angle of 45° , produces $12.95 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m/s}^2$.

Note that squared mass terms used in equations here represent Lorentz-invariants of four-momentum vectors.

However, non-isotropic distribution of the gravitationally interacting mass on the wavefront is generally questionable. Solutions in agreement with anomalies can be obtained even with isotropic distribution, assuming there are no constraints on the source pairs of half-particles (e.g., allowing a combination of τ with μ , rather than solely with another τ particle) and the total number of pairs (all anomalies can be solved either with 2 or 4 particles of photon mass). Additionally, in some cases anomalies may include a contribution of thermal anisotropy, so the solutions could be valid even with tighter constraints.

6.1.3 Additional evidence for photon mass and its oscillation

Observed acceleration is a solid evidence for the rest mass of standard graviton-s/photons in the predicted range ($10^{-68} - 10^{-72} \text{ kg}$).

However, generally, photon mass may be obtained from linear (angular) momentum. Since most of its effective mass is in spin momentum (effective $v \sim 10^{26} \text{ m/s}$) or constituent spin momenta, experimentally obtained photon mass (or, localized mass) will be significantly higher than the calculated rest mass as the photon interaction scale detectable by us is U_0 . In such photons the spin is exchanged for propagation momentum. Thus, using conservation of momentum, one can now calculate the localization masses for various pairs of

source half-photons, e.g.:

$$m_1 v = m_2 c$$

$$M_{\tau\tau} = 6.335068208 \times 10^{-69} \times 3.5 \times 10^{26} \times \frac{1}{c} = 7.39603 \times 10^{-51} \text{ kg}$$

$$M_{\mu\mu} = 3.767055455 \times 10^{-70} \times 3.5 \times 10^{26} \times \frac{1}{c} = 4.39794 \times 10^{-52} \text{ kg}$$

$$M_{ee} = 1.821876712 \times 10^{-72} \times 3.5 \times 10^{26} \times \frac{1}{c} = 2.12699 \times 10^{-54} \text{ kg}$$

$$c = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$$

Indeed, experimentally obtained localized photon masses range from 10^{-50} to 10^{-54} kg[40].

Note that here the same velocity has been used for all photons. In reality, some difference in spin momenta may exist.

6.1.4 Photon/graviton range

Obviously, photon can travel over cosmological distances and that would not be possible if its rest mass would range from 10^{-50} to 10^{-54} kg.

However, as gravitons exist on different scales, this range of masses could represent another vertical sublevel. If so, these would have the following spatial ranges:

$$r_{\tau\tau} = \frac{\hbar}{c} \frac{1}{M_{\tau\tau}} = 47561.69 \text{ km}$$

$$r_{\mu\mu} = \frac{\hbar}{c} \frac{1}{M_{\mu\mu}} = 7.99846493 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$$

$$r_{ee} = \frac{\hbar}{c} \frac{1}{M_{ee}} = 1.653828596 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}$$

These ranges are interesting because they could be correlated with celestial bodies. E.g., for a photon/graviton mass of 5.52×10^{-50} kg the range would be equal to Earth's radius.

I hypothesize that such particles do exist and are carriers of electro-magnetic and gravitational force for large scale (U_1) gravitons.

Photons of lower rest mass (10^{-68} - 10^{-72} kg) are carriers of such force for real mass of U_0 scale - standard atoms, which are filling the wells of large scale maxima.

In that case, empty large scale gravitational wells (associated with naked large scale gravitons) should be devoid of, not only standard atoms, but of these photons/gravitons too (the wells would be transparent for such photons but would be unable to produce them due to absence of real mass) unless the escape velocity of the maximum is $> c$ (black hole maximum).

This implies that gravity of such wells has a very limited range.

However, there are other interpretations - perhaps the very shielding effect of real mass in a well manifests itself in the reduction of range (rest mass increase) of constituent gravitons of the well once these are absorbed (coupled).

Indeed, that would be the most plausible explanation for the shielding effect, assuming it exists.

The strong nuclear force then becomes a result of exchange of large source rest mass ($\sim 10^{11}$ kg black hole) for large force carrier mass, resulting in range decrease (collapse).

Proton radius can then be interpreted as a *fossilized* black hole radius. This has to be one of the most fascinating features of the observable universe - not showing any care for absolute numbers, it's shuffling energies regardless of their magnitudes, all while leaving fossils behind as memories left for someone to process sometime in space, somewhere in time.

6.2 Lorentz factor

In CR, relativistic corrections must be relative themselves. Scale invariance (the presence of vertical energy levels) of physical laws is not absolute, it implies changes in metric [units] and/or changes in values of *constants*, corresponding to particular vertical energy level. Thus, the Lorentz factor, or at least its common interpretation, cannot be valid for all scales of energies.

In GR, metric may be scaled proportionally to energy, but scaling is limited to abstract space and time dimensions and the constant of proportionality between space and time is interpreted as an absolute constant - invariant to scale. In CR, such interpretation is not generally valid.

In conventional (absolute) form, the Lorentz factor allows for a hypothetical graviton of infinite mass to move, bound by the same speed limit as any other body of mass. Since such mass requires infinite energy just to start moving, its speed limit is, however, effectively 0. In CR, the speed limit for such body must be a theoretical 0, not just an effective one. And a mathematical description that better matches the reality should, of course, be a better description of reality.

Similarly, a hypothetical particle of absolute zero mass would conform to a speed limit equal to infinity as it is massless relative to any scale of space. However, while the speed limit usually correlates with mass, the decisive factor is generally entanglement - two bodies of the same mass can be entangled with different scales of space-time (as elaborated in one of the chapters below). In other words, relativistic mass/energy is a measure of the strength of entanglement or coupling with particular [scale of] space-time.

Speed limit may be determined from density and pressure of space. Since density and pressure of space are relative [to scale], for a graviton of infinite mass, density and pressure would be such that the speed limit is 0. Since space is formed by *static* particles, the speed limit is equal to the *rest* velocity of these particles, which is the velocity they have when naked (uncoupled). In CR, this velocity is not absolutely fixed but may oscillate about some mean value.

Speed limits for particular mass are thus relative to [the scale of] entanglement and can therefore be *broken* with a change in vertical energy level.

The generalized Lorentz factor should thus have the form:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c_n^2}}}$$

when applied to rest mass:

$$\gamma_m = \frac{m_n}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c_n^2}}}$$

$$\text{usually, } m_n \propto \frac{1}{c_n}$$

where n denotes the vertical energy level. Change in speed limit thus requires emission or absorption of a minimum discrete amount (impulse) of energy which can take the entanglement to another vertical energy level.

Note that difference in energy between major vertical energy levels is in many orders of magnitude so the energy required for changes can be interpreted as relatively infinite, but it is obviously not absolutely infinite. This allows for the inflation of gravitons of an standard atom into large scale gravitons that act a gravitational attractors, so the whole inflated system becomes a template for the formation of a planetary system.

The inflation must be sufficiently fast to preserve the structure, but it cannot be infinitely fast to break the inevitable asymmetry. Such inflation is most likely to be triggered by matter/anti-matter annihilation (similar to annihilation/inflation of standard photons into standard electron/positron pairs). Since there are no absolute universes, any inflating universe must be inflating *within*

another universe, thus, any *anomalous* energies may have a source in that larger universe.

The speed limit of $c = 2.99792458 \times 10^8$ is the speed limit for U_0 particles (e.g., standard electrons) in space of U_1 bodies, speed limit for U_1 scale is generally lower, while for U_{-1} scale particles (standard photons) in space of U_0 bodies it is higher (note that this implies that the charge of the electron is rotating in space formed by U_{-2} scaled quanta).

Here, of course, the phrase *in space* should be translated as *entangled with space*.

Spin magnetic momentum of electron can be interpreted as evidence of *static* particles orbiting at velocities faster than c .

6.2.1 Determination of c_n

Once the scales of space and time are known, one can easily obtain c_n .

It was hypothesized previously that U_1 scale is entangled with U_{-1} scale (U_{-1} gravitons form the space of U_1 gravitons).

Generally, space of an U_n graviton is formed by U_{n-2} gravitons, thus, associating the U_n graviton with time, this should be a valid approximation of the speed limit c_n :

$$c_n = c_{n-1} \left[\log \left(\frac{m_n}{m_{n-2}} \right) \right]^{-1}$$

m_n = graviton mass on scale n

m_{n-2} = corresponding graviton mass on scale $n-2$

Note that space and time dimensions here are proportional to the masses of space (U_{n-2}) and time (U_n) forming gravitons, respectfully.

Also note that the equation produces speed limit of 0 for infinite mass, and infinity when the two masses become equal. This implies that difference in mass between energy levels is decreasing with decreasing energy level. This is indeed the case with the established equation for mass in chapter 6.1. *Progression of states*. All this is well aligned with CR predictions.

The speed limit c_n on scale U_1 ($U_1.c$ or c_1) is then:

$$c_1 = c_0 \left[\log \left(\frac{m_1}{m_{-1}} \right) \right]^{-1} = c_0 [\log(M_N) - \log(M_{p_e})]^{-1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
c_0 &= c = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s} \\
M_N &= 1.02413 \times 10^{26} \text{ kg} \\
M_{p_e} &= 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}
\end{aligned}$$

which, for c_0 equal to the standard speed of light (c), m_1 equal to Neptune's mass and m_{-1} equal to calculated half-photon mass gives:

$$c_1 = 3.05751973 \times 10^6 \text{ m/s}$$

Note that a very similar value can be obtained with:

$$c_1 = c_0 \left[\log \left(\frac{1}{M_{p_e}} \frac{1}{\rho_c} \right) \right]^{-1} = 3.0577 \times 10^6 \text{ m/s}$$

where ρ_c is the critical density of the observable universe, $9.9 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg/m}^3$ (for the Hubble constant of $72.6 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$), which is also the total average density of the observable universe[51]. Of course, the logarithmic term here should be multiplied with a constant to make it non-dimensional, but the value of this constant here would be ~ 1 . Is it a coincidence that the density of the observable universe is basically the inverse of the m_1 (or Neptune) mass? Probably not, considering that both Neptune and M_{p_e} represent vertically excited electrons, whose mass ratio is highly correlated with the standard speed of light - which is density dependent - it can be obtained from the density of the observable universe and its pressure on the spherical wavefront (e.g., photon) at its radius:

$$c_0 = \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{\frac{Ma}{4\pi R^2 \rho}} = \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{\frac{aR}{3}} = \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{\frac{GM}{3R}} = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$$

where M is the total mass of the observable universe ($4 \times 10^{54} \text{ kg}$), a is the gravitational acceleration obtained from that mass ($13.78 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m/s}^2$), and R is the radius of the observable universe ($4.4 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}$). The term $2/3$ is here due to the contribution of negative pressure (dark energy). Note that this equation is an additional, and strong, evidence of the hypothesized interaction of the enclosed mass-energy with the spherical wavefront of a photon.

Of course, within any vertical energy levels there are sublevels. In example, for $U_{1.3}$ sublevel the speed limit may be:

$$c_{1.3} = c_0 \left[\log(M_N) + 10^{\frac{m-1}{m}} - \log(M_{p_e}) \right]^{-1} = 2.91932312 \times 10^6 \text{ m/s}$$

$$m = 3$$

Taking into account horizontal oscillation in the same sublevel, with the assumption of a quantum of energy $U_{1.3.3}$ either lost by M_N or gained by M_{p_e} :

$$c_{1.3.3} = c_0 \left[\log(M_N) + 10^{\frac{m-1}{m}} - \left(\frac{k-1}{k} \right)^2 - \log(M_{p_e}) \right]^{-1} = 2.93201263 \times 10^6 \text{ m/s}$$

$$k = m = 3$$

Note that a very similar value can be obtained using Sun mass in the original equation (without sub-levels):

$$c_1 = c_0 \left[\log\left(\frac{m_1}{m_{-1}}\right) \right]^{-1} = c_0 [\log(M_\odot) - \log(M_{p_e})]^{-1} = 2.92940473 \times 10^6 \text{ m/s}$$

$$M_\odot = \text{Sun mass} = 1.988500 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$$

The speed of 2.93×10^6 m/s is confirmed in the complementary paper[20] as the limiting speed of this scale in the Solar System, the Milky Way galaxy and beyond - with some variability here possible in the last digit. Thus, the speed of 2.9×10^6 m/s can be interpreted as the true equivalent of the vacuum speed of *light* on U_1 scale.

This seems to suggest there is something special about the Sun, but this is not the case. It is the ratio that is well conserved between the large scale systems. Obviously, in the Solar System the mass of the Sun is the dominating mass so it is not surprising that the mass on that order is the dominating factor in local pressure/density - on which the limiting speed depends. And on U_{-1} scale in the Solar System the order of mass of e half-photon dominates (photon rest mass is on the order of 10^{-72} kg[42]).

In the Milky way, the largest star mass is about $130 M_\odot$ [52]. Using this, or the Eddington limit of $\sim 150 M_\odot$, with muon half-photon mass as the dominating mass on U_{-1} , one obtains again 2.93×10^6 m/s.

Using highest possible mass (Population III, early universe) of $\sim 300 M_\odot$ and the tau half-photon mass as dominating on U_{-1} , one obtains 2.96×10^6 m/s. Thus, some variation exists, but overall, the speed should be about 2.9×10^6 m/s, being generally higher in the early universe due to dominating higher mass eigenstates.

The approximate limit on scale U_{-1} can be calculated similarly, assuming entanglement of adjacent scales:

$$c_{-1} = c_0 \left[\log\left(\frac{m_0}{m_{-2}}\right) \right]$$

$$m_{-2} = 10^{\log(M_{pe})-6 \times 5} = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-103} \text{ kg}$$

$$m_0 = M_e = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$$

$$c_{-1} = 2.16 \times 10^{10} \text{ m/s}$$

As shown before, speed limits faster than the standard speed of light are not necessarily incompatible with GR, as from the larger perspective particles on smaller scales may be interpreted essentially as warp bubbles.

Speed limit on U_{-2} :

$$c_{-2} = c_{-1} \left[\log \left(\frac{m_{-1}}{m_{-3}} \right) \right]$$

$$m_{-3} = 10^{\log(m_{-2})-5 \times 4} = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-123} \text{ kg}$$

$$c_{-2} = 1.08 \times 10^{12} \text{ m/s}$$

This limit is interesting as U_{-2} particles should form the space of standard electrons ($U_0.e$), and at the energy level associated with this speed limit the magnetic moment of the electron cannot be formed by rotation of charge exceeding this velocity.

The magnetic spin angular velocity of an localized electron can be calculated assuming charge radius is known. Assuming this radius is a scaled Neptune charge radius and assuming the Solar System is the carbon atom equivalent (a hypothesis explored in greater detail in complementary work), the radius is:

$$R_e = R_0 = \frac{R_1}{r_1} \times r_0 = 3.834298096 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}$$

$$R_1 = \text{Neptune charge radius} = 24622000 \text{ m}$$

$$r_1 = \text{Neptune orbital radius} = 4495.06 \times 10^9 \text{ m}$$

$$r_0 = \text{orbital radius of the outermost electron in carbon atom} = 70 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}$$

Angular velocity of charge forming the quantized momentum of such electron is then:

$$v = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{M_e R_e} \hbar = 1.5096 \times 10^{11} \text{ m/s}$$

Apparently, the charge is rotating at allowed velocity (not exceeding c_{-2}).

It should be clear, however, that the calculated speed limits are valid for the relatively equivalent conditions between scales. While we cannot significantly

affect the conditions on U_1 scale, we certainly can manipulate U_0 particles and, indirectly, affect the conditions on smaller scales. In example, we can confine the electron (or at least its charge mass) to a much smaller radius than the radius calculated above.

Note that electron at standard scale (U_0) may not generally orbit the atom localized, rather as a less-confined wave. In that case, with momentum conserved, the velocity of its charge is much lower as the radius R_e becomes equal to the atom radius (r_0).

Its charge, however, may not be distributed as an *orbital wave-line*, rather *orbital wave-surface* or a *cloud*, which would then increase velocity somewhat (by 3/2 maximum) but this is negligible compared to initial decrease.

At that radius the speed is much lower even than c_0 so that limit should now be interpreted as a proper relativistic factor. Closer to the nucleus the charge velocity may then become relativistic (between the innermost electron and the atom centre, speeds, however, with greater limit can be greater than c_0).

Situation further complicates with the splitting of the electron charge into multiple energy levels.

But is the source of electron's spin magnetic moment an U_{-1} charge rotating in its space, or the rotation of naked charged space (U_{-2})? In any case, a decrease in radius, with no change in energy, must, due to conservation of momentum, increase rotational velocity (speed limit, in case of space compression), implying that electron's rotation velocity is limited solely by the radius (space compression) and it would be infinite if the electron could be confined to an absolute point. In reality, however, the electron never is an absolute point particle.

6.2.2 Applying speed limits, correlation with emergent phenomena

Speed limits (c_n) are inherently linked to gravitons and depend on their scales. This implies that two *bodies* of similar total mass can obey different speed limits, depending on the scale of graviton[s] coupled to the masses. Consider the example illustrated in Fig. 6.

The leftmost naked graviton (m_1) is an U_0 graviton and has a speed limit of c_0 , the second one from the left (m_2) is an naked U_1 graviton and has a speed limit of c_1 . The m_3 represents the same graviton but coupled to real mass of scale U_0 (collective of U_0 gravitons). This coupling represents a body (or a living body) of mass that, as a whole, has a speed limit of c_1 (due to $c_1 < c_0$).

However, in the rightmost image, showing uncoupled real mass (m_4) forming a *body* (or a dead body), the collective now has a speed limit of c_0 even though it may be of similar or even equal total mass (depending on interpretation -

Figure 6: Gravitons and associated speed limits (not to scale)

mass shielded or not, graviton scales and filled capacities) to the body m_3 .

As noted before, distances between particles are relative and never absolute 0. Electro-magnetic force between two charges, in example, is present over vast distances. This makes the definition of a body relative - due to electro-magnetic connection or entanglement between them, one could consider the two charges as a single body even when greatly separated.

One might have biased definitions, in example, considering atoms as individual bodies until they couple to form a molecule, but does it make a difference to nature - unless formation of a molecule is synchronized (or equivalent) with the coupling of the collective of atoms with a distinct graviton of larger scale?

Any apparently spontaneous organization, or self-organization, of entities into a distinct body should be only relatively spontaneous. Thus, it should probably be more or less synchronized with a coupling to a distinct graviton correlated with such collective. This coupling may be more or less temporary or relatively long lived, but in any case, stability of this organization should be proportional to the strength of coupling (localized correlation).

All emergent physical phenomena probably represent a coupling of certain entities to a distinct graviton of different scale. It is this coupling then that makes the collective something more than the sum of its parts.

7 The unification

In CR, nothing can be absolute or absolutely indivisible, even a *continuum* of space must be, like all energy, an entangled sum of discrete energies or lower energy levels. Diversity of energy levels implies it has variable and scale relative properties, such as density and pressure. Certain number of dimensions of space (time) is embedded in the foundations of every theory in physics. Here, obviously, such number is relatively infinite, however, intrinsic limitations on observation/detection of scales of energy effectively reduce the experience/awareness

to a limited number of dimensions.

Dimensions evolve and one may recognize different species of dimensions where individuals of species often can be represented by the average or relative superposition of individuals.

On small scales even different species may be represented by some kind of superposition.

Generally, for major vertical energy levels, it is convenient to define three or four main species - space, mass, time and charge. These are all entangled, but degrees of entanglement will vary and a difference in superposition of the four may itself warrant classification into different species of superposition.

One might use different units for the 4 species (e.g., m/kg/s/C) but nature will commonly reduce them to the same *currency* (e.g., units of [angular momenta of] space at some scale) and will readily transform one energy into another (exchange space for time, time for mass, etc.).

Here thus, there is no intrinsic entanglement between space-time curvature and mass or charge, the space-time-mass entanglement in GR is thus just one possible case of such entanglement.

7.1 Relativistic time (space)

Everything in nature has an angular momentum relative to something. It is natural then that dimensions of nature are generally curved and closed, quantized with different periods/lengths and different shapes.

Even though dimensions are generally closed, no two cycles of motion through any dimension are absolutely identical.

In example, a dimension of time (or a quantum of an dimension of time) may be interpreted as a circular thin tube (or even a relative 1-dimensional ring), a torus, with relatively discrete or relatively continuous degrees of polarization. Space (or a quantum of an dimension of space) may be interpreted as a thin sphere surface, a torus with significant asymmetry between tube thickness and surface area. Localized energy could then be interpreted as horizontal confinement (localization) of space and vertical confinement (localization or excitation/de-excitation to a particular vertical energy level) of time, or *vice versa*. Whether this energy will be interpreted as simple mass or more complex charge depends on the rules of external entanglement, which are correlated with the internal space-time arrangement (entanglement) of the energy.

Note that CR implies a relatively simultaneous existence of energy on various vertical scales (self-similarity).
If energy existing on one scale can be aware of, or be sensitive to, adjacent

discrete vertical energy levels only, direct sensitivity is strongly limited to 3 dimensions. This will be, with implied self-similarity, replicated on all these levels - splitting each into 3 components, hence explaining three generations of particles (or 3 minor vertical levels) existing on a particular major vertical energy level.

However, not all universes have to be limited to direct awareness of 3 scales (splitting of energy can result in more than 3 levels) and even those limited to 3 may be aware of other scales indirectly - which might become direct awareness over time.

If nature does not discriminate between scales of energy (just as it sometimes does not discriminate between dimensions), then the reduction of different scales to a common currency should also be natural. In which case, the scaling vector may be normalized.

Let A represent a state in time (space) and C a scaling vector, the operation of addition between scales (components of time) could then be represented by the scalar product of vectors:

$$A \cdot C = [a_1 \quad a_2 \quad \cdots \quad a_n] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ \vdots \\ c_n \end{bmatrix} = a_1 \cdot c_1 + a_2 \cdot c_2 + \cdots + a_n \cdot c_n$$

With normalization, the scaling vector C becomes a unit vector:

$$A \cdot \frac{C}{|C|} = [a_1 \quad a_2 \quad \cdots \quad a_n] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c_1/|c_1| \\ c_2/|c_2| \\ \vdots \\ c_n/|c_n| \end{bmatrix} = a_1 \hat{c}_1 + a_2 \hat{c}_2 + \cdots + a_n \hat{c}_n$$

Note that, if dimensions here represent scales, geometrical representation of the state with orthogonal unit vectors would be misleading.

and, with no discrimination between scales:

$$\hat{c}_1 = \hat{c}_2 = \cdots = \hat{c}_n = \hat{c}$$

scales collapse to one dimension:

$$\vec{A} = (a_1 + a_2 + \cdots + a_n) \hat{c}$$

With no direction, a point in such time becomes a scalar:

$$A = (a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n) c$$

The collapses of scales in time will have physical interpretations in space and correlations between these may be interpreted as events of synchronicity, however, generally, it should not be assumed that c (speed of change) is absolutely the same between different scales of energy.

In one example of the above non-discriminating reduction (collapse), consider the addition of different units of time. Adding 2 hours to 3 seconds, for example, from our perspective always results in 123 seconds or 123 units of time. However, assuming equivalent quantization of time exists in nature, nature would sometime interpret the result as 5 units of time. In other words, it wouldn't discriminate between hours and seconds. This might seem unnatural to us, but this kind of non-discrimination between different scales of space/time is sometimes required to conserve relativity, e.g., relativity in periodicity[53].

Due to relative equivalence and self-similarity postulated by CR, energy existing on different vertical energy levels can be, as noted before, interpreted as one and the same energy existing on multiple scales of space/time. Now, if nature sometimes doesn't even discriminate between scales, one can treat this energy as a wave and formulate a quantum wave-function to describe it (one can now also interpret the Big Crunch of the universe as localization of this energy). Thus, it has the same constraints as a wave-function in QM and the discreteness of vertical energy levels stems from the same constraints as the discreteness of horizontal energy levels. After all, it should be clear that, in CR, vertical energy levels must be only relatively vertical.

7.2 Relativistic vacuum

In General Relativity space is treated as non-physical, it has a geometry but no variable physical properties such as density and pressure in common interpretations. Space-time entanglement is treated as absolute which translates to an absolute speed limit, equal to the vacuum speed of light in case of massless photons:

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_0 &= \text{vacuum electric permittivity} = 8.85418782 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F/m} \\ \mu_0 &= \text{vacuum magnetic permeability} = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ H/m} \end{aligned}$$

The constants on the right define the behaviour of electromagnetic fields in vacuum, and when interpreted as absolute, do not imply that vacuum has fields

(energy) present. However, in CR, these constants cannot be absolute and, thus, imply vacuum has energy associated with them. That vacuum has energy has already been theorized in Quantum Field Theory (QFT) - associated with zero-point fluctuations, and evidence for it exists, only the values are debatable.

The relation of the speed of light to vacuum energy can be classically inferred by rewriting the equation in terms of energy density ρ and pressure p :

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_0 &= K_\epsilon \frac{F}{m} = K_\epsilon \frac{s^4 A^2}{m^3 kg} = K_\epsilon \frac{s^4 N^2}{m^3 m^2 kg T^2} = K_\epsilon \frac{s^4 kg^2 m^2}{m^3 m^2 kg s^4} \frac{1}{T^2} \\ &= K_\epsilon \frac{kg}{m^3} \frac{1}{T^2} = K_\epsilon \frac{kg}{m^3} \frac{1}{T} \frac{C}{N} \frac{m}{s} = \rho_s \frac{1}{B_1} \frac{1}{E_1} v_1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_0 &= K_\mu \frac{H}{m} = K_\mu \frac{mkg}{s^2 A^2} = K_\mu \frac{mkgm^2 T^2 s^4}{s^2 kg^2 m^2} \\ &= K_\mu \frac{ms^2}{kg} T^2 = K_\mu \frac{ms^2}{kg} T \frac{N}{C} \frac{s}{m} = \frac{1}{p_s} B_2 E_2 \frac{1}{v_2}\end{aligned}$$

for $E_1 B_1 = E_2 B_2$:

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{p_s v_2}{\rho_s v_1}} = \sqrt{\frac{p_s}{\omega \rho_s}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}K_\epsilon &= 8.85418782 \times 10^{-12} \\ K_\mu &= 4\pi \times 10^{-7}\end{aligned}$$

and now in terms of energy E and mass m :

$$\epsilon_0 = \rho_s v_1 = \frac{m}{V} v_1$$

$$\frac{1}{\mu_0} = p_s v_2 = \frac{E}{V} v_2$$

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{E/V}{m/V} \frac{v_2}{v_1}} = \sqrt{\frac{E v_2}{m v_1}}$$

From this follows:

$$E = \frac{v_1}{v_2} mc^2 = \omega m v_r^2$$

$$\omega = \frac{v_1}{v_2} = \frac{v_r}{\sqrt{v_r^2 - v^2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{v_r^2}}}$$

Here, factor ω is the non-dimensional relativistic factor.

In established theories, energy is always relative to an absolute rest frame ($v_r = c$), which may be referred to as vacuum frame or even CMB (Constant Microwave Background) rest frame due to omnipresence of CMB and negligible photon mass.

The space/time ratio of that frame is considered intrinsic/non-changeable and, assuming $v_r = c$, it has an absolute 0 momentum ($v = 0$ above).

In QM, the same absolute rest frame produces very counter-intuitive results.

In CR there are no such restrictions, no rest frame is absolute, each gravitational well has its own space and there are, not only horizontal but vertical energy levels corresponding to scale of discrete packets of energy.

In CR, the CMB rest frame is space of a large-scale graviton with [angular] velocity (v) possibly equal to c , relative to a rest frame $v_r > c$, and with a *rest* mass $< mc^2/v_r^2$.

Space and time of this rest frame may be entangled but information between them cannot travel instantaneously. Also, either may change spin and entangle with another dimension. Therefore, the ratio c is not absolutely intrinsic and it is changeable.

7.3 Omega factor (relativistic change)

Omega factor is a non-dimensional relativistic factor, a generalization of the Lorentz factor. It is a necessary modification in order to allow complete relativity of universes.

Energy is relative to a specific reference frame and omega factor will generally be relative to a specific graviton in whose space energy is contained.

Space of a graviton is characterized by its $\epsilon\mu$ product (or density and pressure).

Omega factor represents change in energy due to momentum:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c_n^2}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{k^2 c^2}}}$$

$c = c_0 =$ standard speed of *light*

where k depends on the vertical energy level (scale of energy).

Note that ω^{-1} is the eccentricity of the ellipse of width equal to $2kc$ and height equal to $2v$, as shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Relativistic ellipse

With $k = 1$, width is fixed to c and omega factor degenerates to Lorentz. Note also, if k itself has the form of ω^{-1} , degeneration to Lorentz becomes degeneration of a variable ellipsoid to an ellipse of fixed width.

In GR, for an *relativistic* ellipse it is absolutely forbidden to form a circle ($v = kc$). In CR, this must be only relatively forbidden.

However, this should be further generalized, to allow polarization of space and summation of (sensitivity to, awareness of) different scales of energy.

In a physical reality in which every universe (or distinct form of energy) has a momentum the energy of which is stored into its gravitational maximum and its space, it is appropriate to introduce the concept of rest velocity for rest frames (or rest spaces), equal to:

$$v_{rn} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\omega\epsilon\mu}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon &= \text{rel. const. (e.g., } 8.854 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F/m)} \\ \mu &= \text{rel. const. (e.g., } 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ H/m)}\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\omega = \omega_n = \omega(n, q_0) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \alpha_n}} \right)^{-\text{sgn}(q_0)},$$

$$\alpha = \alpha_n = \sum_{m=1}^{m=\infty} \frac{v^2}{v_{r(n-m)}^2} \approx \frac{v^2}{v_{r(n-1)}^2},$$

$$\begin{aligned}n &\in \mathbb{Z} \\ m &\in \mathbb{N}\end{aligned}$$

and n is a discrete (vertical) energy level of the rest frame, v and q_0 its velocity and charge (radial polarization), respectively, relative to rest frame *chosen* by the observer (since awareness of the observer is generally limited to adjacent vertical levels of energy, this frame will usually be $n-1$, and $n-2$ for larger scales of energy).

7.3.1 Degeneration to Lorentz factor

For a negatively polarized rest frame, and $U_{n-2} \ll U_{n-1} (v_{r(n-2)} \gg v_{r(n-1)})$:

$$\alpha_n = \frac{v^2}{v_{r(n-1)}^2}$$

Fixing all discrete packets of energy to single scale where $v_{r(n-1)} = v_r = c$ is the speed limit (speed of *light*) on that scale, Omega factor becomes Lorentz factor:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

7.3.2 Effect on radius

Apart from total mass, effective radius of a graviton also depends on ω :

$$R = \omega R_0$$

R_0 = rest radius

In case of negative polarization it increases with velocity, for positive it decreases.

7.4 Energy

A distinct form of energy can be composed of one or more discrete scales of energy. Total energy is:

$$E = \sum E_n = \omega mc^2$$

where mc^2 is rest energy relative to a rest frame with rest velocity c , while ω represents relativistic increase or decrease due to kinetic energy relative to the observer.

7.5 General force

Electro-magnetic and gravitational force are generally entangled and potential should be regularly exchanged between the two. Therefore, it should be useful to couple the two mathematically into a 4-component vector force, i.e., general force.

General force acting on a particle (e.g., moon maximum) of mass m , charge q and velocity v is the sum of polarized (electro-magnetic) and neutral (gravitational) force.

At any moment in space/time the force acting on a body is a superposition of gravitational and electro-magnetic force. In extreme conditions (temperature/pressure) one component may collapse (deflate) as other inflates.

Source of the force is a general rotating graviton with its field spread through the well:

$$\vec{F} = qm\vec{S} + qm\vec{v} \times \vec{B} + qm\vec{E} + qm\vec{G} = qm\vec{S} + qm\vec{M} + qm\vec{E} + qm\vec{G}$$

$$\vec{F} = qm(\vec{S} + \vec{M} + \vec{E} + \vec{G})$$

with charge/mass radii reduced to infinitesimal value:

Even though the particle has multiple associated charges and real charge/mass radii, to simplify equations, it is useful to reduce it to a point particle, especially in cases where it effectively is a point particle - e.g., when space/time resolution is such that real radii or the oscillation in charge/mass distribution cannot be determined.

$$\vec{M} = \vec{v} \times \vec{B}$$

$$\vec{B} = \frac{1}{m} \mu \frac{q_r}{r^2} \vec{v}_r \times \frac{\vec{r}}{r}$$

$$\vec{E} = \frac{1}{m} \frac{1}{\epsilon} \frac{q_r}{r^2} \frac{\vec{r}}{r}$$

$$\vec{G} = \frac{1}{q} \frac{1}{g} \frac{m_r}{r^2} \frac{\vec{r}}{r} = \frac{1}{q} \frac{1}{r} v_s^2 \frac{\vec{r}}{r}$$

$$\vec{S} = \vec{v} \times \left(\frac{1}{q} \frac{1}{r} v_s \vec{v}_r \times \frac{\vec{r}}{r} \right)$$

ϵ = electric permittivity of space (* 4π)

μ = magnetic permeability of space (/4 π)

$g = 1/G$ = energy density of gravity at the maximum (inverse of the gravitational constant)

s = relativistic factor

M = spin electric field at r

B = magnetic field at r

E = electric field at r

G = gravitational field at r

S = spin gravitational field at r

v_s = angular velocity of space (effective graviton) at r

where m_r , q_r and v_r are mass, charge and velocity, respectively, of the field maximum, r is the distance between the graviton and the moon particle.

Note that s is non-dimensional (invariant to scale) and must be equal to:

$$s = \frac{v_s v}{c_n^2}$$

For $n = 0$ ($c_0 = c$), using substitution:

$$v_s^2 = \frac{G m_r}{r}$$

, with the angle φ between v and $(v_s \times r)$ being equal to the angle between

v_s and r , the qmS term reduces to:

$$qm\vec{S} = \frac{Gm_r m v^2}{c^2 r^2} \sin^2 \phi$$

which, when simplified to one-body problem - using reduced (effective inertial) mass ($m = \mu$, $m_r = M + m$), becomes the correction factor to gravitational potential from General Relativity:

$$V(r) = \int qm\vec{S}dr = -\frac{G(M+m)\mu v^2}{c^2 r} \sin^2 \phi$$

At extreme momentum change, polarized and neutral components can exchange potential - E exchanges with G, while M exchanges with S.

Note that in equilibrium (full capacity) $v_s = v$ ($v_s v$ becomes v_s^2), and, using the above substitution for v_s^2 , spin gravitational vector S becomes:

$$\vec{S} = \vec{v} \times \left(\frac{1}{q} \frac{G_n}{c_n^2} \frac{m_r}{r^2} \vec{v}_s \times \frac{\vec{r}}{r} \right) = \vec{v} \times \left(\frac{1}{q} k \frac{m_r}{r^2} \vec{v}_s \times \frac{\vec{r}}{r} \right)$$

$k = \text{specific vacuum density [m/kg]}$

making vector S the gravitational equivalent of spin electric vector M. Note also that even the ratio between *constants* of the polarized and neutral force vectors is equal:

$$\frac{1}{\epsilon} \frac{1}{\mu} = \frac{1}{g} \frac{1}{k} = G_n \frac{c_n^2}{G_n} = c_n^2$$

That is why electro-magnetic and gravitational waves travel at the same speed.

Of course, these equations are valid down to the radius of the field source, *below* it the field is inverted and can be compressed.

7.5.1 Exchange of quantized potential

In the chapter above (*General force*), masses of force carrier particles were not taken into account, which may be a good approximation for most purposes, however, deeper understanding of reality will require more precision.

As there are no absolutely massless particles in CR, both gravity and electromagnetic potentials should be Yukawa type potentials. However, as each carrier particle is a source of force it has its own field with appropriate carrier particle of

smaller scale. Even though each field is quantized, recursion leads to absolutely infinite ranges and zero mass particles.

Thus, each component of general force should be coupled with a sum of Yukawa type terms:

$$\exp\left(\frac{-r}{L_n}\right)$$

where L_n is the range of a carrier particle (reduced Compton wavelength). However, sensitivity (probability for coupling) of real mass to these gravitons will be inversely proportional to difference in scale of energy between the two.

To take this into account, each Yukawa term should be multiplied by the sensitivity factor, proportional to:

$$\left(\frac{E}{E_n}\right)\delta_{ij} + \left(\frac{E_n}{E}\right)(1 - \delta_{ij})$$

$$i = \left\lfloor \frac{E}{E_n} \right\rfloor, j = 0$$

δ_{ij} = Kronecker delta

Of course, one should also take into account mass oscillation here.

Therefore, due to quantized ranges, energy levels are quantized, however, due to different scales, quantization is relative. This is evident in planetary systems - planetary orbitals are obviously quantized while quantization for smaller bodies is not as obvious due to greater density of energy levels.

Furthermore, the amount of polarization of force carrier particles (gravitons) is likely to change with scale (which may be the source of difference in sensitivity). In that case, distant bodies might effectively feel one force while close bodies would feel another force. Nuclear atomic force, when interpreted as general force, is one such example - on close range gravity dominates, otherwise, electro-magnetic force.

Exchange of one potential for the other has two interpretations - either charge of the field source is exchanged with mass, or energy is exchanged between polarized and non-polarized space (mass/charge exchange in carrier particles).

In reality, superposition of both, should be present.

7.5.2 Solving gravitational anomalies

Previously, it was assumed that angular velocity of space (effective graviton) v_s at radius r is equal to Keplerian velocity:

$$v_s^2 = \frac{GM}{r}$$

And that velocity is also assumed to be the velocity of standard matter coupled to that graviton. This assumption is equal to the assumption that mass of the effective graviton is always equal to the mass of coupled standard matter. However, this should be valid only at full capacity states - when all constituent quanta of the effective graviton (gravitons of smaller scale) are coupled to matter.

Suppose the equation of state is:

$$GM \frac{m_s}{v_s} = m v r \quad (\text{G1.1})$$

G = gravitational constant
M = mass enclosed within radius r

where the right side is orbital angular momentum of matter, while m_s and v_s are mass and velocity of the effective graviton (which is proportional to the intensity of gravitational coupling), respectively.

The effective graviton is forming the toroidal quantum of space which the matter is traversing, its mass m_s is thus the total mass of constituent gravitons while v_s is their average velocity.

From (G1.1), orbital velocity of matter is:

$$v = GM \frac{m_s}{m} \frac{1}{v_s r} \quad (\text{G1.2})$$

Assuming v_s is for uncoupled gravitons equal (or close) to the standard speed of light (c), coupling with standard matter will decrease it but also impart momentum on coupled matter.

Note that such gravitons can't accelerate matter beyond c . Note also that v and v_s are generally vectors, while here it is assumed that the angle between v and v_s is 0. This should be fulfilled in equilibrium but may not be fulfilled otherwise and should be taken into account.

At full capacity, $m_s = m$, $v_s = v$ and velocity becomes Keplerian:

$$v^2 = \frac{GM}{r}$$

For $m < m_s$ velocity increases, at $m \ll m_s$, $v \approx v_s \approx c$. With m equal to the mass of a single graviton, v becomes equal to c .

For $m > m_s$ velocity becomes lower than Keplerian, acting forces are no longer in balance (vacuum pressure prevails), inertia is disturbed and orbital

radius decreases - all the way to relative 0 if everything *below* the original orbit is at full capacity (and if not stopped by accumulated orbiting mass - e.g., satellites falling back to Earth are stopped at surface radius).

With such mechanism, it should be common for inner orbits to be at full capacity (or over-capacitated near the centre), with probability for under-capacitance increasing with orbital distance.

Energy accumulating in the centre will, however, generally be radiated or expelled outwards in some form through various mechanisms.

Under-capacitance explains higher velocities in outer parts of galaxies, while nearly flat velocity curves indicate that:

$$M \frac{m_s}{m} \propto r$$

This can have different interpretations. In one, m_s remains constant, while M/m is growing with r . In another interpretation, m_s is decreasing proportionally to r , while M/m is growing proportionally to r^2 .

Similarly, this:

$$M \frac{m_s}{m} \propto r^3$$

would give linear increase of velocity with distance, solving the core/cusp problem[54] (solid-body behaviour in galactic cores).

However, different generations or species of space-forming particles (*static* gravitons) with different rest masses exist and therefore different ranges may be present in a system. And that is likely the cause of different proportionality with distance. The number of species present may differ between systems (galaxies, planetary systems, ...) and even steeper velocity curves may exist near the core.

Generally, thus, gravity will be proportional to r^{-n} where maximal n is proportional to the number of species and is decreasing with distance from the core. Note that n can be correlated with energy levels, as gravitons have discrete masses and thus discrete ranges. Most likely, the shape of gravitons also correlates with the strength of gravity with distance. Suppose the energy density of a graviton is constant but its total energy changes with shape (synchronized with changes in energy level). In cases where gravity is proportional to r^{-2} , gravitons may have a shape of hollow spheres (energy is distributed over the sphere surface) when uncoupled (non-localized) and forming space. In cases where gravity is proportional to r^{-1} , uncoupled gravitons could have a shape of rings. This could restrict dark matter halos within the central regions of gravitational wells, while on the outskirts space [curvature] would be in the form of dark matter rings. Intensity of gravitons, and thus gravity, decreases with distance, however, with the transformation from a two-dimensional spherical waveform into a one-dimensional ring form, intensity of gravitational coupling becomes proportional to r^{-1} , rather than r^{-2} .

Derivation of the equation G1.2 One way to derive the equation G1.2 is through balance of body momentum and effective graviton momentum:

$$p + \frac{-GMm_s}{rv_s} = 0$$

which, with rearrangement, becomes a balance of body momentum energy and gravitational potential energy of the naked graviton:

$$pv_s + \frac{-GMm_s}{r} = 0$$

With further rearrangement:

$$mrv_s = \frac{GMm_s}{r}$$

$$v = GM \frac{m_s}{m} \frac{1}{v_s r}$$

Thus, in equilibrium orbital states, momentum energy of the body in the local frame must be equal to the gravitational potential energy of the naked graviton. That way the body cannot escape but will also not de-orbit.

Note that in equilibrium $v = v_s$, but the orbital velocity does not have to be Keplerian in this interpretation. Conventionally, however, the m_s/m ratio is incorporated into M (why not into G ?), as *dark matter* (if velocity is higher than expected Keplerian velocity).

Here, v_s is initially equal to c , however, as the body gets entangled with the graviton, v_s decreases below c (while v is increasing).

For $m < m_s$, gravitons of space are effectively dragging matter, for $m > m_s$ (de-orbit occurs), the matter is dragging gravitons towards the centre of the gravitational well (at some point, however, entanglement may be lost, gravitons could decouple and return to the original orbit (range)).

Alternative solution The equation G1.2 is dependent on real mass m and may not be the appropriate interpretation in all cases, however, the alternative exists. Per the definition of a graviton, probability of gravitational coupling should be proportional to n , where n is an integer, equal to the dimensionality (complexity) of the non-localized graviton, making the intensity of gravitational coupling (strength of force) proportional to n . Additionally, gravitons can have different flavours (masses) and, thus, different ranges. Thus, the Newtonian gravitational acceleration should be generalized:

$$g = G_n M \tag{1}$$

$$G_n = G_0 \times I_n = G \times \frac{I_g(n)}{r^n}$$

$$I_g(2) \approx 1 m^{(n-2)} = 1$$

where G_0 is the gravitational constant (G), while I_n represents the intensity of coupling and is a function of n , while n itself can change with distance (r) from the source of gravity, M represents mass enclosed within r . Note that the unit of I_g is $m^{(n-2)}$ (metre to the power of $n-2$) and should represent a generalized Yukawa term (Yukawa potential has a unit of m^{-1}). Density of gravitons may decrease with distance, however, intensity of coupling can change relatively abruptly with the change in shape/mass of gravitons.

Any anomalous change in orbital velocity curves should then indicate a change in *energy level* (n). The distance where the shift occurs is equal to the range of the associated gravitons. From this range (reduced Compton wavelength), masses of gravitons can be determined:

$$m_g = \frac{\hbar}{\lambda_r c} = \frac{\hbar}{r_g c}$$

where \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, c is the standard speed of light, while r_g is the graviton range.

However, two interpretations are possible here. Instead of involving multiple *species* of gravitons with different ranges, change in coupling intensity (graviton dimensionality) with distance could be interpreted as a consequence of the oscillation of flavour of single species of a graviton. If the transition between flavour eigenstates is continuous (as it should be during motion) the transition between energy levels will be smooth, otherwise sharp. Note that one interpretation does not exclude the other, both could be true simultaneously.

The above may then explain all gravitational anomalies. For $dM/dr \approx 0$ (where M represents the mass enclosed within the orbital radius r), flat orbital velocity curves are obtained with $n = 1$. This explains the flatness of galactic rotation extending far out of the galactic edges[55] (where conventional dark matter theories fail). Linearly increasing velocities can be, for example, obtained with $n = 1$ and $dM/dr \propto r$, solving the core/cusp problem[54] (solid-body behaviour in galactic cores). Recent analysis of galaxies in SPARC (Spitzer Photometry and Accurate Rotation Curves) database shows that dark matter particles must have different masses to fit the observation[56], which is also going in favour of the hypothesis presented here. Note that (1) can be interpreted as a modification of the gravitational constant. Evidence exists, even within the Solar System, that this constant is not absolutely invariant[57], rather should be interpreted as a relative constant.

Increasing velocity with distance, however, does not have to imply increasing mass in the enclosed standard matter that is interpreted as the gravity source, it implies increasing density of gravitons. Such increase may be conventionally unexpected, however, it can be explained if the source of gravity is not localized, it rather represents a wave itself. Universe is showing self-similarity on various

scales and absolute scale invariance of physical laws is just an assumption that is probably incorrect. A supermassive black hole may represent a large scale graviton, in which case one should question how localized it is. Linear orbital velocity increases could be interpreted as a consequence of another gravitational maximum associated with this graviton - in other words, the associated waveform has radial nodes. Densities of gravitons of smaller scale which are coupling to celestial bodies would change at the maxima, and these small-scale gravitons could be interpreted as particles forming space of the large scale graviton.

7.5.3 Mechanism of exchange

Exchange of electro-magnetic potential for gravitational potential is done through the change of scale. In example, radii of charge maxima may be deflated with inflation of a mass radius of a gravitational maximum. This doesn't affect only orbital radii of gravitons but also spin radii of graviton quanta - effectively, charge is subdued with the inflation of mass (gravity).

Note that, seemingly, no extra energy is required as this is simply a change of species of force, not strength.

However, energy is needed to stimulate and process transformation, during which some energy may also be lost. The end product will then have different energy than initial total energy.

The triggers of exchange may be:

- annihilation of matter with anti-matter,
- critical temperature/density (extremely low, extremely high).

If transformation mechanism exists locally, external energy needed to stimulate exchange can be extremely low. This may simply be resonance or entanglement inversion.

Note that any entanglement decrease must be coupled with another entanglement increase.

The exchange of potentials of general force could thus be common in birth and death of bosons and boson (Bose-Einstein) condensates.

The equivalence of bosonovas and supernovas/novas, galaxies and quantum vortices, planetary systems and atoms, in that case, may go far beyond abstract similarity.

In any case, it should not be impossible, in any universe, to ensure conditions that would reduce the relativity of self-similarity (similarity to a universe of adjacent vertical scale) to a minimum.

7.6 Evaluation of G

Gravitational constant (G) is not fundamental and may be interpreted as:

$$G = \frac{1}{2} \frac{A_s v_s}{M T_s} = 2\pi \frac{R^2 v_s}{M T_s} = \frac{3\pi}{\rho} \frac{1}{T_s^2} = \frac{R}{M} v_s^2 \left[\frac{m^3}{kg s^2} \right]$$

A_s = surface area of the gravitational maximum [graviton]

R = radius of the maximum

M = gravitational mass of the maximum

ρ = mass density of the maximum

v_s = angular velocity of the maximum

T_s = period of rotation of the maximum

It is then relative to a particular graviton (gravitational maximum) and has its properties, such as mass, radius and velocity, built in. These are generally variable properties.

Even if, generally, all these variables are correlated in such a way that G remains constant, are they correlated (entangled) at all times and do changes propagate instantly?

In CR, instant propagation of information is [absolutely] impossible and some phase difference between changes in [G and] the variables will always exist. The G itself must oscillate.

Obviously, a gravitational maximum has a [changeable] spin momentum and this can further be complicated when it is evidently composed of multiple maxima.

Note that v_s here is Keplerian velocity. Assuming M is the mass of a graviton, non-Keplerian velocity may be interpreted as a difference in G (due to a difference in graviton mass).

While the 3-dimensional (spherical) form of one maximum may cloud the existence of inner maxima, outer maxima can have different spin momenta. Even if the whole system changes spin, changes cannot be instantaneous across all maxima, rather propagate in a wave-like nature.

7.6.1 Gravitational collapse (G collapse)

Rotational profiles of galaxies show that $1/R$ is often not proportional to v_s^2 . Even if outer maxima have collapsed (fragmented) to multiple satellite maxima of smaller scale, these cannot acquire [real] mass instantaneously nor they will always acquire [real] mass during collapse.

Although collapse requires energy, it doesn't necessarily have to come from real mass. Unlike in GR, gravitational collapse in CR is not reserved for massive bodies, the energy for collapse depends on the initial energy of the maximum.

Maxima can thus remain naked for relatively long times, proportionally to scale and inversely proportionally to mass (energy) field density, before [another] equilibrium is established and $1/R$ becomes proportional to v_s^2 .

Gravitational collapse in CR is localization of graviton momentum - e.g., a large scale graviton with a spin radius on the order of 10^6 km can collapse to form a graviton with a spin radius on the order of 10^3 km, sometimes with a former spin radius fossilized into orbital radius of a new body.

Real mass required for equilibrium can be obtained through conservation of angular momenta:

$$\begin{aligned} [m_{img}(n) + m_{re}(n)] v_n r_n &= [m_{img}(n-1) + m_{re}(n-1)] v_{n-1} r_{n-1} \\ &= M v_s R \end{aligned}$$

m_{img} = mass of the naked gravitational maximum = imaginary mass

v = orbital velocity of the maximum

r = radius of the maximum

m_{re} = acquired smaller scale mass = real mass

$v_s = v_{n-1}$ = spin velocity of the [collapsed] maximum

$R = r_{n-1}$ = radius of the [collapsed] maximum

$M = M_{n-1}$ = total mass of the [collapsed] maximum

where n is the scale of the maximum. In the above, dependence on scale has two equivalent notations:

$$m_{img}(n) = m_{img_n}$$

Collapse of a graviton to smaller scale generally can be a high energy or low energy collapse. In case of high energy collapse, accumulated real mass is lost (e.g., nova/supernova explosions) - decoupled from a collapsing graviton. In case of low energy collapse, the graviton is [relatively] naked and collapse occurs due to localized disturbance of its momentum with sufficient real mass for coupling on smaller scale.

Note that graviton may, instead of deflation, start inflating after decoupling. It will then continue inflating until it reaches maximum range - if it does not collapse and couple to another mass before that point is reached.

Maximum range becomes a relative term if graviton is losing energy with inflation - in that case, range would be expanding continuously. However, most energy is lost with coupling.

Regardless of interpretation, lost energy at the moment of coupling should be proportional to distance between inflation/emission (decoupling) and absorption/deflation (coupling) due to increasing distance in correlation between entangled constituent quanta of the wave (graviton) - the volume of entanglement cannot remain absolutely constant and it is unlikely to conserve constancy (oscillation average) with distance.

Note also that the collapse of a wave-form is only a relative collapse of

wave nature - difference between a particle and a wave is simply in the radius of the wavelike form. The inverse interpretation is also valid - in some reference frames, the larger wave-form may be interpreted as a particle.

In reference frames where the collapse is discrete, low energy collapse occurs when this is established:

$$m_{img}(n) = m_{re}(n - 1)$$

In other reference frames, collapse proceeds gradually and can start even before the above relation is established.

For a naked maximum, $m_{re}(n)$ is a relative 0. In high energy collapse, $m_{img}(n)$ must be decreased to match $m_{re}(n-1)$. This is synchronized with increase in $v_n r_n$ product.

There are no fundamental constants. All are fundamentally variable.

8 Scale and centre of the observable universe

For every universe there must exist a reference frame that universe is revolving about.

Given the determined scales of discrete vertical energy levels, it is reasonable to assume that the centre of the observable universe (*point* it is revolving about) is outside of it.

Thus, all observable galaxies collectively orbit a barycentre outside of the observable universe. This can be confirmed and approximated by observing galaxies on a different energy level of the same system.

Momenta of such galaxies should be correlated - in equilibrium state they orbit the centre in the same direction but with a calculable difference in speed and distance from the centre.

E.g., if one considers Milky way as a bound electron, the atom which Milky way is a part of should have a diameter on the order of 10 trillion (10^{13}) light years, 10^3 times the diameter of the observable universe. In that case, all other energy levels are outside of the observable universe.

However, considering the number of galaxies and the state of evolution, this is not the best interpretation (although some layering may be present).

Considering distances between atoms (planetary systems) and molecules (binaries and other strongly correlated systems) the observable universe is a gas bubble of extremely low density with particles concentrated in quantum vortices (galaxies).

This bubble or soup, however, cannot be completely homogeneous and it is only a matter of technology and proper interpretation whether one can observe

the difference between the closest and the furthest layers of this *gas* (layer) relative to the external central point.

The most appropriate interpretation of observable universe is a part of space of a large scale graviton, in a form of a torus - as stated already.

It may have been deflated from an even larger scale, however, evidence suggests it has been inflated from smaller scale, probably in an annihilation event.

9 Atomic property differentiation between systems

Vertical energy levels are entangled. This implies entanglement between equal species, but entanglement between different species of different scales is not forbidden either.

Increasing number of protons and electrons in an atom is splitting (or increasing) energy levels (layers) of the atom.

What if properties of standard atoms are strongly correlated with properties of U_1/U_{-1} systems (*atoms*) they are co-evolving with?

For example, radii of standard atoms may be correlated with [the density of] the gravitational well they are in.

Consider the Lyman (or any other) series for a hydrogen [like] atom - if density of series is not invariant to such correlation, one could have a distorted image of non-local reality, as the spectrum lines of standard atomic elements would be variable across time and planetary systems.

E.g., in a nitrogen-like system the Lyman series for hydrogen would have red-shifted frequencies.

One might even argue there are 6 distinct wavelengths (after 6th, the spectrum becomes continuous) in Lyman series and that such differentiation is a direct consequence of the Solar System being an *atom* with 6 protons and 6 electrons (carbon), or that series beyond the 6th may be correlated with more distant planetary systems.

10 Waves as particles as waves

All particles having a momentum always generate waves on some scale (because there is no absolutely constant momentum). A particle itself may be in wavelike or corpuscular form. This form, like everything, is relative. One observer may detect a wave while another may observe a particle form (both forms can even be observed at the same time). Forms are dependent on properties of local space, which may be affected by the observer too.

Generally, with more energy density, a corpuscular form is more likely to be detected. Waves may be coherent in space and/or in time. Coherence in both, space and time, will thus produce the most dense energy (e.g., laser light).

A waveform collapse may also be initiated by interaction with other waves (particles), but this will depend on energies involved and the properties of underlying space.

From our perspective, wave nature prevails on U_{-1} scale, particle/wave on U_0 , while on U_1 scale nature is observed generally as corpuscular. This is due to differences in average pressure/density and time dilation between these scales.

11 Evidence

Some evidence for complete relativity is presented in this paper. Additional evidence confirming complete relativity of universes is presented in follow-up/complementary papers. Mainly in the analysis of the Solar System in CR framework[20].

Of course, other researchers are welcome to confirm or refute the presented predictions and hypotheses in this and follow-up papers.

Due to inherent limits in observation, however, different interpretations are sometimes possible and some might prefer a less-intuitive interpretation of reality. This does not have to be an issue - there's no reason we should all believe in the same reality, especially the one on the scales which we cannot observe directly. Some *views*, however, may be limiting the *observer* of that reality.

12 Conclusion

Angular momentum seems to form the fundamental signature of energy. All energy is thus fundamentally correlated with frequency. Evolution might concentrate these energies into corpuscular forms of different scale, however, oscillation will always be relatively conserved and observable at all scales of space taking dilated time into account. But the single absolutely intrinsic property of a universe is relativity.

Everything must be completely relative in order to exist. And to conserve this relativity in both space and time, everything exists on different scales of energy and transforms on different scales of time.

Amenoum[58],
anno incarnati β 33.

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